

Cornelis de Wael, "To visit the Imprisoned", ca. 1640, oil on canvas, 99x152 cm, © Musei di Genova

Materiality and Confinements in the Medieval and Early Modern Eras

Objects, Actors, and Experiences

Book of Abstracts

Edited by Nathalie Dahn-Singh and Anna Clara Basilicò

Unil.

Atelier des histoires

About this Book of Abstracts

This Book of Abstracts is a collection of the abstracts provided by the participants to the international conference *Materiality and Confinements in the Medieval and Early Modern Eras: Objects, Actors, and Experiences*, which took place at the University of Lausanne, from 22 to 24 April 2026. The conference was organized by Nathalie Dahn-Singh (University of Lausanne) and Anna Clara Basilicò (FBK – Istituto Storico Italo Germanico) (see the conference program, p. 4-6, and the Call for papers, p. 7-11).

The abstracts are presented in alphabetical order according to the authors' names, followed by the conclusion.

Conference scientific committee:

Frances Andrews (University of St Andrews), Pascal Bastien (Université du Québec à Montréal), Falk Bretschneider (EHESS, Institut franco-allemand de sciences historiques et sociales de Francfort), Christian G. De Vito (University of Vienna), Joachim Eibach (University of Bern), Laurence Fontaine (EHESS), Anne Gerritsen (University of Warwick), Guy Geltner (Monash University), Johan Heinsen (Aalborg University), Marie Houlemare (Université de Genève), Élisabeth Lusset (Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne), Mary Laven (University of Cambridge), Ludovic Mangué (Équipe Damoclès, Université de Genève), Vincent Milliot (Université Paris 8 Vincennes-Saint-Denis), Renaud Morieux (University of Cambridge), Natalia Muchnik (EHESS), Xavier Rousseaux (Université catholique de Louvain), Riccarda Suitner (Ludwig Maximilians University Munich), Mathieu Vivas (Université de Lille).

Conference website:

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Wednesday 22 April

13:15 **Welcome coffee**

13:45 **Introduction**

-14:00 **Nathalie Dahn-Singh**
Université de Lausanne

Anna Clara Basilicò
Istituto Storico Italo Germanico

14:00 **Keynote lecture**

-15:00

Sophie Abdela
Université de Sherbrooke

***If These Walls Could Speak!
An Incursion in Paris'
Jailbreaks (1700–1790)***

15:00 **Coffee break**

15:30 **Panel 1. Spaces, Escapes,
and Power Relations**

-17:00

Chair: Nathalie Dahn-Singh
Université de Lausanne

Lucie Guignet
Université de Paris-Cergy
*Les objets de la résistance:
rescouses et évasions des
prisonniers du Lyonnais
(XIV^e–XV^e siècles)*

Noëmi Schöb
Universität Bern, Stadtarchiv
und Vadianische Sammlung der
Ortsbürgergemeinde St. Gallen
*Escapes from the Zucht- und
Waisenhaus St. Leonhard
in St. Gallen, 1663–1798*

Vincent Meyzie
Université Paris Nanterre
*Le juge et le prisonnier.
Proximités et promiscuités des
espaces judiciaires et carcéraux
(France, XVIII^e siècle)*

Thursday 23 April

09:00 **Panel 2. Graffiti
and Prisoners' Voices**

-10:30

Chair: Anna Clara Basilicò
Istituto Storico Italo Germanico

Fanny Lalande
Lab. de recherche historique Rhône-Alpes
*"S'ils se taisent, les pierres mêmes
crieront": les graffitis, une source de
l'expérience carcérale des Huguenots,
sous le régime de la Révocation de
l'Édit de Nantes*

Marco Albertoni
Università "G. D'Annunzio" di Chieti-Pescara
*Bones, Hair, Statuettes, Graffiti:
Preliminary Remarks for an
Archaeology of Magical Practices in
Italian Prisons (17th–18th Centuries)*

Giuseppe Mrozek Eliszezynski
Università "G. D'Annunzio" di Chieti-Pescara
*Nobility, Commoners, Bandits:
the Identities of Prisoners through
Graffiti*

10:30 **Coffee break**

11:00 **Panel 3. Objects and Forced
Labor in Mediterranean
Galleys**

-12:30

Chair: Giorgio Riello
European University Institute

Teresa Peláez-Domínguez
Universitat de València
*La chiourme, les statuts et les choses
dans les galères d'Espagne
(XVI^e siècle)*

Luca Lo Basso Università di Genova
*Les chaînes des galériens: matérialité
de la peine et vie quotidienne
sur les galères méditerranéennes
(XVI^e–XVIII^e siècles)*

Alexander Luca Coscarella
Università di Bologna
*"The Worthy Refreshment of those
Turks Enchained in the Galleys":
Selling and Consuming Coffee in an
Early Modern Mediterranean Port City*

Friday 24 April

12:30 **Lunch break**

14:00 **Panel 4. Gender, Agency, and Materiality**
-15:30

Chair: Natalia Muchnik

École des hautes études en sciences sociales

Maria Adank

Università di Verona

Visible but Constrained. Material Culture and the Dogaressa's Role in Venetian Politics

Claudia Stella Geremia

Università Ca' Foscari

Objects of Proof, Bodies in Exile: African and Afro-descendant Women before the Inquisition in the Canary Islands (16th-18th c.)

Francesca Ferrando

Università di Verona

Correcting Women: Gender, Discipline and Space in Genoa's Charitable Institutions

15:30 **Coffee break**

16:00 **Round table**

-17:30 **Frances Andrews**
University of St Andrews

Renaud Morieux

University of Cambridge

Natalia Muchnik

École des hautes études en sciences sociales

Giorgio Riello

European University Institute

19:30 **Conference dinner**

09:00 **Panel 5. Materiality and Confinement in Medieval and Early Modern Cloisters**
-10:30

Chair: Élisabeth Lusset

CNRS, Université Paris 1 Panthéon Sorbonne

Micol Long Università di Milano

"I Pace the Floor, Walking Round and Round": Approaching the Role of Materiality in the Cloistered Experience Through Comparative Textual Analysis (12th-13th Century)

Cristina Setti Università di Padova

Inside and Outside the Cloister: A Geography of Latin Devotion and of the Social Entanglements of the Franciscan Friars in 15th-century Venetian Crete

Michèle Steiner Universität Basel

The Materiality of Confinement: Gift-Giving and Conventual Networks in Early Modern Solothurn (17th and 18th Centuries)

10:30 **Coffee break**

11:00 **Panel 6. Health, Disease, and Everyday Life, Between Administration and Practices**
-12:30

Chair: Xavier Rousseaux

Université catholique de Louvain

Alessandra Celati Università di Torino

Everyday Materiality in Venetian Inquisition Prisons

Fleur Beauvieux Aix-Marseille Université

"Vingt-une paillasses, deux tours pour la soie, un fauteuil de bois de noyer...". Une histoire des femmes de l'hôpital de l'Entrepôt à travers les registres d'inventaire

Stefano Tomassetti Università del Molise, Laboratoire de recherche historique Rhône-Alpes

Air, soleil, murs. Enfermement et protection de la santé dans les Carceri Nuove de Rome (XVIII^e siècle)

12:30 **Lunch break**

14:00 **Panel 7. Between the Inside and the Outside: Prisoners' Experiences from Below**
-15:30

Chair: Renaud Morieux
University of Cambridge

Lorenzo Bonvicini Università di Torino
The Price of Guilt. Material Culture, Economy, and Power Relations in the Prisons of the Duchy of Modena and Reggio Emilia (17th-18th Centuries)

Kiran Mehta University of Leicester
Prison Letters: a History from Below in Eighteenth-century England

Leïla Cheurfa
Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne
Dans les tolbooths du nord de l'Écosse: matérialité et expériences de l'enfermement pour dette au XVIII^e siècle

15:30 **Coffee break**

16:00 **Panel 8. Between the Inside and the Outside: Circulations and the Management of Places of Confinement**
-17:30

Chair: Frances Andrews
University of St Andrews

Lorenzo Paveggio Università di Padova, Institut de recherche et d'histoire des textes de Paris
Objects of Exile: The Materiality of Theodulf of Orléans's Confinement (c. 818-821)

Hayrettin Yücesoy
Washington University in St. Louis
Solace of the Imprisoned: Abbasid Ethical Discourses on Incarceration

Nabhojeet Sen
Bonn Center for Slavery and Dependency Studies
Confinement(s) and Circulation: Prisons in Early Modern South Asia, 1600-1818

17:30 **Conclusion**

-17:45 **Xavier Rousseaux**
Université catholique de Louvain

The conference is free of charge and will be held in person and online. No registration is required to attend in person. To attend online, please contact nathalie.dahn-singh@unil.ch.

Organisers

Nathalie Dahn-Singh (Université de Lausanne), **Anna Clara Basilicò** (Istituto Storico Italo Germanico)

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N.B.: we replicate here the Call for Papers that we sent out in 2025, which received 58 proposals, out of which 24 were chosen (see the program on the conference website). The number of proposals, as well as the large array of topics, institutions and confined populations, indicates a very dynamic state of research and a strong interest in the material history of confinements in the medieval and early modern eras.

Call for Papers

Nathalie Dahn-Singh, University of Lausanne

Anna Clara Basilicò, FBK-Istituto storico italo-germanico

Since the theoretical debates that first emerged in the 1960s and subsequent foundational studies which launched lasting interest in the topic of prisons, various perspectives have expanded our understanding of carceral institutions and confinement practices.¹ The influence of social history and microhistory, as well as the spatial and archival turns, has allowed historians to open new fields of research into the topic and to explore new sources. In particular, the significant shift from a broader analysis of punishment institutions to a focus on “prison experiences” has shown the potential of carceral and penal institution archives to reveal aspects of everyday prison life.² Recent studies have advocated focusing on prisoners’ experiences and trajectories, using archival sources to uncover ordinary, daily events such as diet, the spread of disease, interpersonal relationships, riots, and escapes.³ And yet, even though objects and things are central to confinement experiences, the materiality of confinement remains largely understudied, except in a few studies.⁴ Confinement is defined by walls that separate individuals from society; these walls act as a spatial and administrative infrastructure which limits inmates’ physical or mental contact, both with the outside world and within the space of the institution itself. Beyond the mere walls, daily interactions between confined individuals, institutional authorities, and staff are largely paved and defined by a variety of things: food, water, books, graffiti, clothes, money, letters, official registers, medicine, punishment objects, etc. In this regard, and drawing on the material turn in history since the early 2000s, things – whether “tangible” things physically available to historians or “textual” things described in written sources – might offer an additional perspective on the history of confinements more broadly, especially when addressing forms of “prison before the prison”.⁵

¹ Erving Goffman, *Asylums: Essays on the Social Situation of Mental Patients and Other Inmates* (Routledge, 2017 [1961]); Michel Foucault, *Surveiller et punir. Naissance de la prison* (Gallimard, 1975); Michelle Perrot ed., *L'impossible prison. Recherches sur le système pénitentiaire au XIXe siècle* (Seuil, 1980); Michael Ignatieff, *A Just Measure of Pain. The Penitentiary in the Industrial Revolution 1750-1850* (Pantheon Books, 1980)

² Pieter Spierenburg, *The Prison Experience. Disciplinary Institutions and their Inmates in Early Modern Europe* (Amsterdam University Press, 2007); Guy Geltner, *The Medieval Prison: A Social History* (Princeton University Press, 2008); Mary Gibson, *Italian Prisons in the Age of Positivism, 1861-1914* (Bloomsbury Academic, 2019); Natalia Muchnik, *Les prisons de la foi. L'enfermement des minorités (XVIe-XVIIIe siècle)* (Presses universitaires de France, 2019); Sophie Abdela, *La prison parisienne au XVIIIe siècle. Formes et réformes* (Champ Vallon, 2019).

³ Sophie Abdela and Pascal Bastien eds., *Actes du colloque: Enfermements: Pratiques, expériences et parcours de détention (XVIe-XIXe siècles)*, *Criminocorpus* 23 (2023); Sophie Abdela, “Prisons on the Edge: Perspectives on the Late Medieval and Early Modern History of Confinement in the Francosphere,” *The English Historical Review* 139, no. 598-599 (2024): 868–87.

⁴ Gilly Carr, *A Materiality of Internment* (Routledge, 2025); Megan Cassidy-Welch, *Monastic Spaces and their Meanings: Thirteenth-century English Cistercian Monasteries* (Brepols, 2001); Megan Cassidy-Welch, *Imprisonment in the Medieval Religious Imagination, c. 1150-1400* (Palgrave MacMillan, 2011); Abdela “Prisons on the Edge”.

⁵ Anne E. Lester, “Introduction: Materiality and Methodology: Ways of Knowing and Narrating,” *The Medieval History Journal* 26, no. 2 (2024): 183–208, 191; Edward Peters, “Prison before the Prison: The Ancient and Medieval Worlds,” in *The Oxford History of the Prison: The Practice of Punishment in Western Society*, ed. N. Morris, and D. J. Rothman (Oxford University Press, 1997).

The international conference “Materiality and Confinements in the Medieval and Early Modern Eras: Objects, Actors, Experiences” examines confinements through the lens of their materiality. Drawing on a recent historiographical broadening of the field, the conference aims to address various forms of medieval and early modern confinement, both judicial and non-judicial: prisons, galleys, hospitals, workhouses, cloisters, monasteries, and the like.⁶ At the same time, it seeks to reflect on methodological questions pertaining to material history as an approach and to the sources that underpin it. “Material culture”, as Anne Gerritsen and Giorgio Riello summarised, “encompasses more than simply material objects. Objects have meanings for the people who produce and own, purchase and gift, use and consume them. Material culture therefore consists not merely of ‘things’, but also of the meanings they hold for people”.⁷ At the same time, one might add, they also carry a socio-economic dimension. Materiality might therefore open new ways of approaching and narrating the history of confinements, revealing “other registers and ways of knowing beyond the intellectual and cognitive”.⁸

1. Everyday life and sociability

Whether in prisons, hospitals, or convents, objects are used, exchanged, made, repurposed, allowed, forbidden: from books to food, work tools, letters, money, or beds, objects inform and impact everyday experiences. Recent studies have suggested that things “have the capacity... to shift social relations”.⁹ We welcome contributions on the materiality of everyday life and sociability. To what extent do things represent or affect confined individuals’ social lives (or lack thereof)? How do they impact their day-to-day agency? This research area might include various aspects of everyday life, from labour to spiritual exchanges, including the question of time in confinement. Contributions might also question the role that materiality played in sociability between inmates as well as with the various actors of confinement, both within and outside the walls – including visitors and confined individuals’ networks of solidarity.

2. Confinement spaces

While the question of the spaces of confinement has attracted some recent attention from historians in the wake of the spatial turn, it nevertheless remains widely understudied in history when compared to the more abundant research in the fields of sociology or geography.¹⁰ We welcome contributions focusing on the materiality and material culture of confinement spaces. This includes both the spaces within the walls – including the impact of architecture on confined experiences and the role that things play in the spatial separation (or lack thereof) of various confined populations – and around the infrastructure. This research area might question the architectural specificities of the medieval and early modern eras; for example, the adaptation of cloisters and the like to incarceration/penal purposes or the spread of specialised prison spaces for different social groups, crimes, genders, or ages. As both medieval and early modern confinement spaces were characterised by their porosity, contributions might also question connections between the inside and the outside (e.g., through the mobility of objects, such as letters) and activities that take place outside the walls, such as (forced) labour, economic transactions, family or church visits, or recovery leaves.

3. Administration and the transmission of knowledge and skills

Medieval and early modern confinement institutions were closely connected to the outside world on various levels, first and foremost administratively and financially.¹¹ From the keeping of prison registers to the bringing of food and the provision of beds, things were at the heart of keeping confinement institutions

⁶ Julie Claustre et al, eds. *Enfermements. Volume I : Le cloître et la prison (VIe-XVIIIe siècle)* (Éditions de la Sorbonne, 2011); Isabelle Heullant-Donat et al. eds., *Enfermements. Volume II : Règles et dérèglements en milieu clos (IVe-XIXe siècle)* (Éditions de la Sorbonne, 2015); Isabelle Heullant-Donat et al. eds., *Enfermements. Volume III : Le genre enfermé. Hommes et femmes en milieux clos (XIIIe-XXe siècle)* (Éditions de la Sorbonne, 2017).

⁷ Anna Gerritsen and Giorgio Riello, eds. *Writing Material Culture History* (Bloomsbury Academic, 2021), 3.

⁸ Lester, “Introduction”, 203.

⁹ *Idem*, 197.

¹⁰ Martine Charageat et al. eds., *Les espaces carcéraux au Moyen Âge*. Ausonius éditions, 2021 ; Abdela “Prisons on the Edge”; Falk Bretschneider, “Spatial turn et histoire de la justice pénale moderne,” *Crime, Histoire & Sociétés / Crime, History & Societies* 21, no. 2 (2017); Olivier Milhaud, *Séparer et punir. Une géographie des prisons françaises* (CNRS Éditions, 2017).

¹¹ Falk Bretschneider, *Gefangene Gesellschaft. Eine Geschichte der Einsperrung in Sachsen im 18. und 19. Jahrhundert*, (UVK, 2008).

operational. How might materiality inform us about the way that these institutions were economically, socially, or politically embedded in the societies to which they belonged?¹² Contributions might reflect on the concrete, day-to-day material running of the institutions and their actors (including merchants, entrepreneurs, or craftsmen) or on the administrative knowledge necessary to run them. The materiality of institutional archives and their preservation is also an important consideration. Furthermore, prisons, convents, hospitals, and other institutions of confinement were filled not only with knowledge and skills carried by various actors (doctors, priests, jailors), but also with things pertaining to that knowledge and skills: “an object’s materiality conveys myriad intersecting forms of knowledge”.¹³ What do things reveal in terms of knowledge and skills transmission within the walls and beyond? To what extent did confined individuals themselves produce knowledge? Contributions might focus on various types of knowledge and skills, including prison writings, medical skills, religious knowledge, work-related knowledge, and the like, whether carried into confinement or acquired there.

4. Power relations and violence

The vast majority of sources for the history of confinement were produced by institutional authorities. This conference aims to reflect on the potential of materiality to provide a perspective from below on individual experiences. Contributions might focus on confrontations with authority (for example, in terms of prison escapes, punishment, various cases of violence, etc.) and how objects framed power relations in confinement. As recent studies suggest, things likewise might construct and deconstruct social statuses.¹⁴ When it came to prison escapes, uprisings, or punishments, what role did the things available to inmates play in granting individuals their freedom? Contributions might also focus on the extent to which things defined the way in which authorities regulated confinement institutions (through violence and punishment, for instance).

We welcome proposals based on various types of tangible and textual sources (material, written, iconographic, archaeological) that focus on various confinement institutions and populations from across the medieval and early modern world (up to the end of the 18th century, i.e. up to, but not including, the revolutionary era). Proposals focusing on gender, religious, and social differences, as well as underexplored regions of the world, are especially welcome.

Keynote speaker

Sophie Abdela, Professor at the History Department of the University of Sherbrooke, Canada.

Selected Bibliography

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¹² Abdela, “Prisons on the Edge”.

¹³ Lester, “Introduction”, 187.

¹⁴ Simona Cerutti et al. eds. *La Cité des choses. Une nouvelle histoire de la citoyenneté* (Anacharsis, 2024).

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If these Walls Could Speak!

An Incursion in Paris' Jailbreaks (1700-1790)

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The history of prison escapes has long been marked by the great, epic escapes of the 18th century. It has focused on the stories of figures like Casanova, who escaped from the *Piombi* prison in Venice after months of planning; or Henry Masers de Latude, who managed to escape from both the Château de Vincennes and the Bastille. Historians' analyses have long sought to highlight the incredible exploits of these men and others and have viewed them as tales of resistance championed by "rebels".¹ Escape has been portrayed as "a material counterculture," "the revenge of the vanquished," "the most extreme form of rebellions against royal power."² Attempts have also been made to develop a typology of the phenomenon: in which seasons, at what times, with whose help, and by what means do escapes occur? But this approach, while it succeeds in painting a picture of escapes and escapees, does not seek to understand what the general phenomenon can teach us about the prison world. Rather, it views prison escape as a mere isolated "anomaly" which must be corrected.³

But a systematic study of prison escapes that took place in 18th-century Paris invites us to see things differently. By analyzing 81 trials involving 354 prisoners spread across a dozen prisons in the capital, this paper wants to show that escapes do not in fact appear as either an anomaly or an epic tale of resistance. What stands out at first glance is rather the opposite – namely, the incredible banality of escape. First, because, as a general rule, escapes are incredibly repetitive in the methods employed. The same actions are repeated over and over. Second, because there is absolutely nothing to suggest that escapes were acts of resistance or that the escapees have given any political meaning to their actions. Finally, because the trials reveal that escape is not simply a disturbance that arises out of nowhere. In fact, it is most often the consequence of entirely ordinary, everyday, and routine processes.

And so, this paper aims to find answers to the following questions: why do prisoners so often – perhaps even so easily – manage to escape from the prisons of the Ancien Régime? How, in short, can we reconcile the banality of escape with the basic function of the prison: to keep bodies confined? Is it possible that old regime prisons were simply not expected to prevent escapes?

Crumbling walls?

To answer these questions, I first examine the conditions of the buildings and what these escapes reveal about the authorities' priorities regarding the maintenance of prisons in the French capital. Unsurprisingly, the records show facilities that have long been neglected, and whose conditions directly undermine the very purpose of the incarceration. There is therefore no doubt that the prison structure itself provided opportunities for escape, even though its primary function was to prevent them. This is all the truer given that early modern prisons were often located right in the heart of urban areas. This proximity naturally had implications for prison security, especially when prison walls shared boundaries with neighboring buildings. Many escapes occurred through these points of contact.

Thus, the records confirm that the very structure and location of prison buildings were liabilities. And the authorities knew it. While they may have had a poor grasp of what happened in prisons on a daily basis, they understood very well that these prisons were in a miserable state. Moreover, the authorities did not show much harshness toward the guards who were responsible when escapes occurred. Very few were actually prosecuted, even if they had several escapes to their credit. This shows that it was considered a fool's errand to ask staff to completely prevent escapes given the state of the prisons. Here, as elsewhere, the administration wasn't simply being lax, but rather quite pragmatic.

When it comes to prisons of the Old Régime, the discussion usually ends right here. The association between the Ancien Régime and decay is so taken for granted that we don't really see the need to look any further. But to truly

¹ Marie Houlemare, "Des fers à l'évasion. Les rebelles dans les prisons royales à l'époque moderne," *Criminocorpus* (2014). <https://doi.org/10.4000/criminocorpus.2901>.

² Juliette Glikman, "Briser ses fers. L'évasion, revanche des vaincus en France au XIX^e siècle," in *Bois, fers et papiers de justice. Histoire matérielle du droit de punir*, eds. Michel Porret, Vincent Fontana and Ludovic Mangué (Georg, 2012), 266–281.

³ Gilles Chantraine and Tomas Max Martin, *Prison Breaks. Toward a Sociology of Escape* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2018).

understand escapes, I propose that we cannot limit ourselves to looking at the state of the walls: we must see what men have made of them.

Mixing men and walls

This paper aims to show that it is not the prison environment alone that can explain escape: this environment has forced staff to adjust and adapt. As a key characteristic, escapes are generally linked to situations that are absolutely and entirely ordinary – and thus, in this sense as well, completely mundane and banal. Therefore, I propose that the holes in the walls were often made possible not despite the prison's primary security mission, but precisely because people were trying to uphold that mission.

Staff are indeed especially well-placed to understand the harmful effects of prison on inmates. They are therefore compelled to try to correct the prison's unnecessarily harmful effects, without compromising security. The escape cases show them trying to correct the intolerable heat, the unbearable cold, the thick darkness or even the horrible stench of the rooms. What these cases reveal is that it's not the lack of light or the lack of air that leads to escape attempts; rather, it's their combination with, on the one hand, the agency of the prisoners and, on the other, the constant negotiations that staff members must engage in. These processes do not take the form of grand, epic acts of resistance, but rather of mundane, everyday gestures.

These adaptations are also intended to compensate for a constant shortage of staff. The constant lack of resources also compelled authorities to delegate whole responsibilities. Indeed, staff enlisted prisoners for daily tasks. Certain chores, especially cleaning duties, were entrusted to inmates, who may then abuse these positions to find a way to escape or to help others escape. Their responsibilities gave them unusual power, as they allowed them to move freely through various areas that were often inaccessible to others, and to enjoy greater autonomy and privileges. This made them prime middlemen frequently involved in escape attempts. And so, the conditions under which prison custody was carried out meant that guards had to rely on individuals or structures to ensure the smooth operation of the prison, but at the same time, they increased the prison's weakness.

In sociology and criminology, prison escapes tend to be viewed as spectacular revelations of organizational failure. But what can be seen in the jails of XVIIIth-century Paris is the staff fighting against the prison to achieve the prison's own objectives since the walls alone cannot ensure them. This forces the staff to innovate, to adapt, and to take risks. But on any given day, that is precisely what usually ensures the prison's success.

Diving into the very heart of the escapes themselves, examining them in sequence and dissecting them, makes things appear in a new light. And what is thus illuminated is the incredible incoherence in which the prison is anchored – that is, the incoherence between its mission to contain bodies and the material and human resources allocated to that mission. The prison world operates by relying on two realities that contradict and oppose each other: a goal – that of keeping bodies confined – and deficient material and human resources that prevent this from being achieved.

Visible but Constrained. Material Culture and the Dogaressa's Role in Venetian Politics

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In early modern republican contexts, unlike queens, princesses, or duchesses, the wives of political leaders did not provide heirs to a throne. For this reason, traditional historiography has generally treated their role as marginal, if not entirely irrelevant.

This paper focuses on Venice, one of the most enduring republics of early modern Europe, governed by an elected Doge – often described as a *primus inter pares* within a complex oligarchic system. Despite the absence of dynastic succession, the Dogaressa, as the Doge's wife, occupied a highly visible yet ambiguously defined position at the heart of Venetian political culture.¹

As part of my current Marie Skłodowska-Curie project OSpaMA (Objects, Spaces and Material Culture: Gender and Politics in Early Modern European Republics, Venice and Genoa, 15th–18th centuries), I investigate the agency of Doges' wives and their female relatives, focusing on the networks they sustained, the gendered spaces they inhabited and shaped, and the acquisition and display of objects within the Ducal Palace. The aim is to reconstruct forms of female influence, strategies of negotiation, and the promotion of both private and public interests within a political system that formally excluded them from power.

What emerges challenges the assumption of female marginality. A material culture approach – starting from objects, their uses, and their spatial configurations – reveals how things actively shaped social relations, identities, and hierarchies, rather than merely reflecting them. At the same time, recent scholarship has questioned the rigid opposition between private and public spheres, highlighting instead their permeability and the ways in which elite women operated across them.² Within this framework, the figure of the Dogaressa becomes particularly revealing: highly visible yet structurally constrained, she occupied a position in which material culture and spatial practices made both her prominence and her limits tangible.

Before turning to specific cases, a few remarks are necessary. First, as is often the case for women of the past, we lack ego-documents that might restore the Dogaressas' own voices. None of them left personal accounts through which we could access how they experienced, perceived, or interpreted their role.

Second, the official sources of the Venetian Republic offer only limited insight. Not only did Dogaressas hold no formal political authority, but the institutional narrative of the Republic, carefully crafted to project stability, tended to marginalize figures that did not fit this ideal. This absence makes material culture especially important, as it allows us to reconstruct forms of agency and constraint that remain otherwise unarticulated.

Finally, unlike royal consorts trained from an early age, Dogaressas typically assumed their role unexpectedly. The complex and unpredictable election of the Doge, designed to prevent dynastic power, meant that he – and consequently his wife – were usually of advanced age. Though members of the patrician elite with some economic autonomy, these women entered the role late in life and were abruptly required to leave their private residences – often large palaces along the Grand Canal – and relocate to the ducal apartments in the Palazzo Ducale. This shift entailed a

¹ On the traditionally assumed marginality of the Dogaressa, see: Mirella Pasquinucci and Olga Premoli Taiti, "La dogaressa," in *Il Serenissimo Doge*, ed. Ugo Franzoi (Canova, 1986), 253–283; Giovanni Scarabello, "Le dogaresse," in *I Dogi*, ed. Gino Benzoni (Electa, 1982), 163–182. The only more extensive study remains Holly S. Hurlburt, *The Dogaressa of Venice, 1200–1500: Wife and Icon* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2006), which, however, stops at 1500.

² For a material culture approach that foregrounds the active role of objects in shaping gender relations, see Leora Auslander, "Deploying Material Culture to Write the History of Gender and Sexuality: The Example of Clothing and Textiles," *Clio. Women, Gender, History* 40 (2014): 157–178. On the permeability of the boundaries between domestic and public space and women's agency within them, see Sandra Cavallo, "In and Out of the Baroque Palace: Noblewomen and Urban Space in Seventeenth-Century Rome," in *Liberty, Irreverence, and the Place of Women in Early Modern Italian Culture: Essays in Honour of Letizia Panizza*, ed. Stephen Clucas and Simone Testa (Springer, 2025), 83–109. For an overview of material culture as an interdisciplinary field and its methodological implications, see Anne Gerritsen and Giorgio Riello, eds., *Writing Material Culture History* (Bloomsbury, 2021), 1–19.

profound reconfiguration of space, possessions, mobility, and daily practices, reshaping their lives in direct relation to their husband's political elevation.

The first case study is situated in the mid-sixteenth century, when the dress of the Dogaressa was formally codified. In theory, she was the only woman – together with other female relatives residing in the Ducal Palace – exempt from sumptuary laws. In practice, however, this privilege did not translate into freedom. The codification of her attire imposed a rigid model, functioning as a ceremonial uniform. Rich and heavy garments constrained her body, limiting movement and prescribing posture and appearance. Even more concretely, the long train of the mantle could never touch the ground, meaning she could not move independently but always required attendants to carry it. Visibility thus came at the cost of autonomy.

This tension becomes particularly clear in the case of Zilia Dandolo. The only moment in which we hear her voice, albeit mediated through official records, is when she asked to attend religious services in St Mark's Basilica without full ceremonial display. Moving from the ducal apartments to St Mark – the Doge's chapel and a central stage of public ritual – normally required prescribed dress, a female entourage, and a highly choreographed procession. For a woman of around fifty, this repeated performance was a significant burden. Zilia was not allowed to dispense with ceremonial dress or protocol. Instead, the authorities created a private passage linking the Palace to the church. Her request was thus accommodated not by granting greater freedom, but by reshaping space to preserve the visual and political order.³

The second case concerns the Dogaressa Loredana Marcello Mocenigo, about two decades later. As Dorit Raines has shown, Loredana was aware of the constraints of public visibility and responded by withdrawing from it. Rather than residing in the ducal apartments, she chose to remain in her residence on the Giudecca, cultivating a more private life away from ceremonial obligations. Her case reveals a grey area within the institutional framework: while the Doge was bound to inhabit and perform power in the Ducal Palace, the role of the Dogaressa was less strictly defined. It was within this ambiguity that Loredana negotiated a degree of distance from the public stage.⁴

A third case, at the end of the sixteenth century, offers a strikingly different strategy. Morosina Morosini Grimani, wealthy and politically astute, actively supported her husband throughout his rise to the dogeship, contributing with her own resources and operating as part of a collaborative couple. Once Dogaressa, she embraced visibility to the fullest, seeking to give substance to a role that lacked formal political functions. Within the constraints of the Ducal Palace, she effectively "invented" a sphere of action, promoting music and the education of her maids of honour, drawing inspiration from the courts of Mantua and Ferrara. Yet this visibility also came at a cost. She could not freely choose whom to meet; she is absent from formal public banquets; and more broadly, her interactions and movements were carefully regulated. Even her material world was subject to control. A telling example is the Golden Rose bestowed upon her by the pope: a highly charged symbolic gift that she was allowed to keep only for the duration of her life, after which it had to be transferred to the public Treasury. Morosina accepted and worked within these constraints, but her case makes clear that even the most resourceful and prominent Dogaressa operated within a framework that ultimately limited her autonomy, in both space and possessions.⁵

The final case is that of Elisabetta Querini Valier, Dogaressa in the late seventeenth century. In a markedly changed social climate, in which elite women in Venice, as elsewhere, enjoyed greater mobility and sociability, Elisabetta appears acutely aware of the constraints imposed by her position. Confined within the ducal apartments and in a role that lacked a clear political function, she gradually reshaped both. With her husband's support, she began receiving foreign dignitaries and distinguished guests in a room reserved for her within the Ducal Palace – an innovation that would have been unthinkable a century earlier. She established a structured practice of audiences, exchanges of gifts, and highly codified uses of dress and insignia, deploying material culture as a form of political language.

Elisabetta also sought to loosen the spatial constraints of her position. A few months after her husband's election, he petitioned the pope on her behalf, asking that she be granted permission to visit convents "both out of devotion [...] and to relieve her from the continual solitude to which she is constrained by her rank as Princess according to the laws of this government." The language is revealing: solitude was not incidental but structural, a direct consequence of her institutional condition. The permission was granted, and Elisabetta began visiting monasteries across the city, accompanied by a small female entourage.

Yet this partial opening of space and movement provoked a strong reaction. While muted during the Doge's lifetime, it emerged forcefully after his death in 1700. New provisions explicitly prohibited future Dogaresses from receiving any

³ Maria Adank, "Vestire e comparire. L'abito della dogaressa Zilia Dandolo Priuli (1556–1566) tra codificazione ed esenzione dalle leggi suntuarie," in *Questioni di moda: fonti, storia, iconografia*, ed. Alessandra Zamperini (Il Poligrafo, 2021), 79–108.

⁴ Dorit Raines, "La dogaressa erudita. Loredana Marcello Mocenigo tra sapere e potere," in *Donne di potere nel Rinascimento*, eds. Letizia Arcangeli and Susanna Peyronel (Viella, 2008), 375–404.

⁵ Maria Adank, *I Grimani di San Luca. Cultura materiale, genere e potere nella Venezia del Cinque e Seicento* (Viella, 2025), 163–226.

public figures, restricted their movements, limited their entourage to family members, and subjected even visits to convents to prior approval by a large majority of the Senate. These measures directly targeted the practices she had introduced, effectively closing the experimental space she had opened. Her brief season of visibility and mobility was thus reabsorbed into a more rigid institutional framework.⁶

What emerges from these case studies is a fundamental tension. These women were not marginal: they belonged to the highest ranks of Venetian patrician society, were often extremely wealthy, and, as wives of the Doge, were in principle the most prominent women of the Republic. Yet the very space that elevated them – the Ducal Palace – and the role that defined them could become restrictive, even oppressive. The weight of ceremonial dress, the regulation of movement, the obligation of visibility, and the impossibility of acting freely within or beyond the palace generated forms of constraint that were at once material and symbolic. Certainly, these women were not forcibly confined in convents or prisons, as many less privileged women were; yet they were not only deprived of any formal political power – indeed often regarded as potential sources of instability for the Republic – but also constrained, and at times effectively confined, by subtler yet pervasive forms of material and spatial control.

⁶ Maria Adank, “La dogaressa Elisabetta Querini Valier (1694–1700) e un’inedita visibilità in Palazzo Ducale a Venezia,” in *La fama delle donne. Pratiche femminili e società tra Medioevo ed Età moderna*, eds. Vincenzo Lagioia, Maria Pia Paoli, and Rossella Rinaldi (Viella, 2020), 279–295. All the case studies discussed here, together with additional ones extending to the wives of ambassadors, procurators of San Marco, and other republican officeholders, form part of the monograph resulting from my fellowship.

Bones, Hair, Statuettes, Graffiti: Preliminary Remarks for an Archaeology of Magical Practices in Italian Prisons (17th-18th Centuries)

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When studying the records of trials for magic and witchcraft in early modern Italy, it is not uncommon to encounter material objects that were confiscated and included within judicial dossiers. Most frequently, these consist of prohibited books – either printed or manuscript – that function as the actual *corpus delicti* upon which the accusatory framework is built, or which are used to formulate new charges against individuals already in detention. In other cases, however, the same case files contain various types of objects that were confiscated directly from within prisons.

Indeed, prisoners themselves often reported their cellmates. This practice followed a utilitarian logic: as numerous cases attest, such denunciations could result in tangible benefits, including transfer to more comfortable cells or more favourable conditions of detention. In particularly significant cases – especially when alleged political conspiracies emerged – they could even lead to the granting of a pardon.

From this perspective, a particularly illustrative case is that of the priest Antonio Gaetano Albanelli, vicar of Puget-Théniers, who was imprisoned in Turin in 1721 for a dispute formally unrelated to magic, concerning the priorate of Roccastrone and the collection of certain debts. The investigation expanded while he was already in prison, and he became implicated in accusations of magical practices intended to harm the Savoyard ruler at a distance. The expansion of the inquiry began with the statements of a certain Onorato Daniele and gradually extended to other individuals. Among those interrogated were Albanelli's cellmate, Gabriele Peyron, as well as a prosecutor and a notary familiar with his past conduct. Based on the collected testimonies, the authorities searched his cell, where they discovered an animal bone (probably from a hare), a bag containing hair, and a breviary inside which slips of paper bearing magical formulas had been concealed. These objects are still preserved within the archival file. According to the testimony of his cellmate, Albanelli used these items to perform spells intended to harm designated victims, including members of the royal family. Albanelli and Peyron – considered an accomplice despite his testimony against Albanelli – were ultimately sentenced to life imprisonment and transferred to the prisons of Miolans. Onorato Daniele, by contrast, received a reduced sentence. It remains extremely difficult to determine whether Albanelli was genuinely involved in such practices or whether the material evidence found in his cell was fabricated by fellow prisoners seeking to obtain advantages.¹

Cases in which material evidence has been preserved are, however, relatively rare. Even today, archivists continue to debate how to classify and where to place such objects within archival systems. In many instances, traces of magical practices in prisons emerge only through interrogations and judicial records. A few years earlier, in the same city of Turin, a similar case had occurred: around 1707, in the senatorial prisons, a detainee accused his cellmate, Antonio Boccalaro – imprisoned for the murder of a state official – of performing harmful magic using wax statuettes, which he allegedly pierced with a fish spine in order to cause the death of Victor Amadeus II.² In this case as well, the statuettes were reportedly found, but no trace of them remains in the case file. Nor is it possible to determine whether the accused had actually performed such rituals or had instead been used as a scapegoat for others seeking personal advantage. Boccalaro was ultimately executed, and a column of infamy was erected against him.³

A third, closely related episode took place in the same Turinese prisons during that same period. Testimonies recorded under interrogation in 1717 reveal that two female prisoners accused one another of having drawn figures of devils on the prison walls. According to their accounts, these images were instrumental to a magical ritual believed to have caused the sudden and inexplicable death of the young prince Vittorio Amedeo Giovanni Filippo of Savoy (1699-1715). One of the women testified that the alleged perpetrator had explained how she had created the images: by incising the

¹ Massimo Centini, *Streghe, roghi e diavoli: i processi di stregoneria in Piemonte* (L'arciera, 1995): 156–158.

² Sabina Loriga, "Un secreto per far morire la persona del Re. Magia e protezione nel Piemonte del '700," *Quaderni storici* 53, no. 2 (1983): 529–552.

³ Marco Albertoni, *Storia delle colonne infami: giustizia e memoria in età moderna* (Bibliopolis, 2023), 125.

figures with a pin used to fasten hair and adding inscriptions drawn with charcoal. The main accused, Clara Ribolletta, was ultimately executed for witchcraft.⁴

Magical practices in prison, however, served multiple purposes and were not limited to harmful magic. Another case, different in nature but particularly revealing of the underlying dynamics of such practices, concerns Michele Tomassi, detained in the prisons of the Caetani castle in Sermoneta. In this instance, the risk that the accusation of magic was unfounded or fabricated for personal gain can be excluded, as the circumstances are entirely different. On 28 May 1595, the *podestà* Giulio de Angelis reported in a letter sent to the Caetani family in Rome that he had subjected Michele Tomassi – accused of theft – to the torture of the strappado. What struck the judges was the prisoner's impassivity: despite the violence of the torture, he did not confess and appeared, in the magistrate's words, "like a piece of wood," entirely insensitive to pain.

Such an anomalous resistance aroused suspicion that some form of trick or device was involved. Having ruled out the presence of hidden instruments on his body, the authorities hypothesized that he possessed a magical means capable of neutralizing the effects of torture. A thorough search of his cell was therefore conducted, during which three small wax pellets were found among his clothing. Inside these pellets were small slips of paper bearing incomprehensible names and arcane words, immediately interpreted as evidence of magical practices.

Under renewed interrogation, Tomassi stated that the pellets had been given to him by a relative, with precise instructions: he was to ingest one when he realized he was about to be tortured, to prevent himself from confessing. The belief in the efficacy of this remedy – shared both by the judges and by the accused himself – appears to have produced a powerful autosuggestive effect, enabling him to withstand torture to an extraordinary degree. Even after being administered a purge intended to neutralize the supposed enchantment, Tomassi continued to endure the torture without yielding. This suggests that he may naturally have possessed an unusually high pain threshold or a form of neurological insensitivity to pain. The episode was instead interpreted as evidence of the spread of diabolical practices in the territory of Sermoneta, prompting a broader investigation and the consultation of a theologian tasked with determining the nature of the formulas found in the pellets. The documentation breaks off at this point and does not preserve the objects, as the surviving records consist of correspondence rather than a formal trial dossier.⁵

In a society deeply marked by fear and uncertainty – often addressed through practices labelled "superstitious" by authorities – it is therefore unsurprising that such rituals also found space within prisons. Even in the absence of material evidence, the widespread occurrence of trials for magic and superstition – sometimes opportunistic, at other times genuinely believed by the accused – makes it plausible that these same beliefs remained active within carceral contexts.

A survey of magical manuals from the period – often circulating clandestinely, in manuscript or printed form, and compiled from heterogeneous materials drawn from both magical texts (such as the *Clavicula Salomonis*) and religious sources (psalms, consecrated objects, holy water) – reveals that such practices required objects that were easily obtainable: wax, hair, animal bones, paper, breviaries. These were therefore materials accessible even within a prison. In the absence of paper, or for specific ritual purposes, some texts also prescribe the drawing of geometric figures, symbols, or inscriptions on walls or on the ground. It is thus not surprising that certain grimoires include rituals intended to secure release from prison through the invocation of supernatural entities, sometimes conceived as "specialized" in this domain.⁶

These same texts also provide means to fulfil desires that are particularly understandable in a carceral context: harming an enemy at a distance, binding another person emotionally, or foretelling the future. Such aspirations are echoed in early modern prison graffiti, where expressions of hostility toward those responsible for one's imprisonment or of grief over the loss of emotional bonds frequently emerge.

Regarding graffiti, while the presence of esoteric elements in certain complex religious representations in the Steri prison in Palermo remains a matter of debate, it is nevertheless documented that some prisoners were involved in necromantic practices, including the creation of wax figurines and the invocation of demons.⁷

⁴ Loriga, "Un segreto".

⁵ Riccardo Mannelli Galilei Riccardi, *Nozze di Sermoneta-Antinori. Istruzioni ed atti relativi ad un procedimento inquisitoriale di stregoneria nella terra di Sermoneta, l'anno 1575: lettere degli cardinali di Pisa e Sermoneta al vicario Gio. Francesco Bonamici commissario dell'Inquisizione di Roma a Sermoneta* (Tipografia Giuntina, 1920).

⁶ Federico Barbierato, *Nella stanza dei circoli: Clavicula Salomonis e libri di magia a Venezia nei secoli XVII e XVIII* (Sylvestre Bonnard, 2002); Aurelio Rigoli, *Magia e etnostoria* (Boringhieri, 1978), 18–48.

⁷ Pier Luigi Mannella, "Dalla carta al muro: graffiti e rituali nelle segrete dello Steri," *Etnografie del contemporaneo* 4 (2021): 155–199; Pier Luigi Mannella, "Prodotti esoterici di matrice rituale nelle testimonianze grafiche delle carceri dello Steri," in *Magnis tempora currunt*, ed. R. Perricone (Edizioni Museo Pasqualino, 2024), 261–292; Gianclaudio Civale, *Descendit ad inferos: i graffiti dei prigionieri dell'Inquisizione allo Steri di Palermo* (Palermo University Press, 2018); Gianclaudio Civale, "Authorship Under Confinement. Wall Writing, Carceral Iconography and Inquisitorial Power in Early Modern Palermo," *Visual History* 11 (2025): 89–115, 101–105, Rita Foti, *I graffiti delle*

It is also plausible that such practices could function as a form of economic or symbolic resource within prison: just as some individuals practiced magic outside prison, they could do so within it, receiving payment or credit from fellow inmates. Their authority as “magicians” or “necromancers” was, paradoxically, reinforced by the very fact of their imprisonment for such activities.

Moreover, the accidental discovery of knots, small bags, bone fragments, and other enigmatic objects within the crevices of the walls of a former prison in the province of Asti suggests that such items may have been used in magical rituals.

Finally, on the basis of all these accounts, it appears plausible that a number of graffiti – especially figurative ones, whether drawn or carved in bas-relief – which I have identified in several early modern Italian prisons, may have had magical purposes.

In conclusion, the combination of these narratives, the objects recovered in prisons and archives, and the graffiti still visible within cells constitutes a corpus of sources for an archaeology of prisons that remains largely neglected by early modern historical research. Historiography often remains exclusively anchored to archival documents. Although it is clear that the interpretation of such material traces raises complex methodological issues, it is precisely in this direction that new avenues of research may be opened, analogous to those developed in disciplines that, in the absence of written sources, have necessarily relied almost entirely on material evidence.

Carceri segrete del Santo Uffizio di Palermo. Inventario (Palermo University Press, 2023); Giovanna Fiume, *Del Santo Uffizio di Sicilia e delle sue carceri* (Viella, 2021), 307–310.

« Vingt-une paillasses, deux tours pour la soie, un fauteuil de bois de noyer... ». Une histoire des femmes de l'hôpital de l'Entrepôt à travers les registres d'inventaire

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En 1640, et suite au vœu des consuls de faire cesser la peste de 1630, est créé l'Hôpital Saint-Joseph à Marseille, plus communément appelé Maison du Refuge. Il est à destination des filles et femmes condamnées pour débauche et prostitution ou qui demanderaient par elles-mêmes d'y être recluses afin d'échapper aux tentations du monde. Plus d'une quarantaine d'années après, en 1688, une autre institution est établie, accolée et incluse dans la structure du Refuge : l'hôpital de l'Entrepôt. Voué à l'accueil et la claustration des femmes enceintes non mariées, c'est cette structure et ses résidentes qui seront au centre de notre communication. Alors que ces deux institutions peuvent facilement être rattachées au mouvement de « grand renfermement » défini naguère par Michel Foucault et différents historiens des années 1980, nous baserons notre étude à partir de l'analyse d'une source particulière, produite par l'institution : les registres d'inventaire des deux maisons. Composés régulièrement entre 1735 et 1772, souvent lorsqu'il y a un changement de la mère supérieure qui chapeaute l'établissement, ces registres ont la particularité d'appartenir à la catégorie des choses « textuelles », institutionnelles puisqu'ils sont rédigés par les directeurs des lieux, mais qui renferment quantité d'informations sur les choses « tangibles » au sein de ceux-ci. Sous forme de longues listes, est décrit dans le menu détail l'ensemble de ce que contiennent les différentes pièces de l'Entrepôt, hôpital largement délaissé par l'historiographie contrairement au Refuge. Nous prendrons ainsi comme point de départ de notre propos différents objets mentionnés dans cette archive d'histoire matérielle, qui ne sera croisée avec d'autres que pour des compléments d'information. Ces objets vont nous permettre de reconstituer le parcours-type d'une femme enfermée à l'Entrepôt : arrivée, vie quotidienne au sein de l'établissement et « dénouement » avant sa sortie prochaine probable lors de l'accouchement.

La première partie reviendra sur l'établissement de l'hôpital de l'Entrepôt. Un objet en particulier signe l'arrivée des femmes au sein de la structure, et apparaît dans l'inventaire de 1772 : dans « un prie Dieu bois de noyer avec sa serrure » se trouve un « guichet en bas servant pour fermer les registres des femmes enceintes qui vien[n]ent à l'Entrepost ».¹ Il s'agira ainsi, à partir de ce registre, de se questionner sur l'acte de claustration à l'origine de l'entrée des femmes dans l'hôpital – soit le fait qu'elles soient enceintes. Dès le XVI^e siècle au cours des règnes d'Henri II puis III, est adoptée l'obligation pour les femmes non mariées de déclarer leur grossesse. En 1708, un édit de Louis XIV rappelle cette contrainte, la déclaration devant dorénavant être réalisée devant le lieutenant-général criminel. L'évêque de Marseille Henri de Belsunce la réitère de son côté dans une ordonnance religieuse en 1712, tandis que quelques années plus tard, en 1745, le Parlement de Provence ordonne la séquestration systématique des femmes enceintes suite à leur déposition. La déclaration de grossesse étant très souvent accompagnée d'une plainte en séduction puisque la plupart des exposantes ne sont pas mariées, les femmes qui suivent l'ordre encourent le risque de se retrouver enfermées à l'Entrepôt, « hôpital-prison » géré quotidiennement par des religieuses, dont l'existence a pour but de prévenir un possible infanticide. Il s'agit ainsi d'un enfermement préventif, qui débute pour les futures parturientes après leur transfert du Bureau de police à l'hôpital grâce au port d'un billet d'entrée, pour un crime qui n'a pas encore été commis (et qui n'aurait peut-être pas eu lieu). Ce sont les enfants à naître qui sont protégés dans ces différents édits, non les femmes qui les portent qui sont considérées comme suspectes, voire coupables. La polysémie du mot « hospital » à l'époque moderne est ainsi notable : il ne s'agit pas seulement d'un terme employé pour un lieu de soin mais également d'une maison d'accueil pour les populations pauvres, qui ne peuvent, une fois entrées, en sortir. L'hôpital de l'Entrepôt répond dès lors à des logiques à la fois pénitentiaire, monastique et hospitalière. Généralement plus subi que choisi pour les femmes auxquelles il est destiné, la frontière entre ces deux notions devient particulièrement floue en ce qui

¹ Archives départementales des Bouches-du-Rhône (ADBdR), 8 HD E 42, Inventaires et règlements (1735-1777), inventaire de l'Entrepôt du 1^{er} septembre 1772.

concerne les femmes enceintes, qui n'ont bien souvent pas d'autres endroits où aller. L'architecture de ce « lieu de justice [...] de la sanction » nous est également accessible grâce aux inventaires, qui détaillent les objets et les choses pièce par pièce : une cartographie déductive de cette maison sur deux étages complètera cette première partie de présentation générale du lieu.²

Nous aborderons ensuite le quotidien des femmes enfermées, grâce à certaines parties détaillées de cette source particulière. Ressort en effet la multifonctionnalité de cet espace, pensé comme un lieu d'enfermement mais également de vie collective, au sein duquel différentes activités occupaient les captives. Si aucun emploi du temps précis ni règlement spécifique à l'Entrepôt ne nous est parvenu, il est possible de déduire différents pôles d'activités qui scandaient la journée des femmes enceintes : le travail textile de la laine, de la soie, du chanvre et du coton ; la prière et le dévouement religieux ; les repas et la préparation de ceux-ci ; la nuit et le sommeil. Les femmes pouvant être admises à n'importe quel moment de leur grossesse et non pas seulement lors du dernier trimestre, ce quotidien pouvait pour certaines d'entre elles s'étendre sur de longs mois. La lecture détaillée des inventaires montre une vie sommaire avec de fortes disparités selon le statut social : le confort était uniquement réservé aux sœurs (mère et tourière), recluses avec les femmes enceintes (elles sont par exemple les seules à bénéficier d'un matelas et de couvertures de qualité). Une salle supplémentaire pour les femmes « qui payent pension pour y faire leurs couches » est mentionnée dans le dernier inventaire de l'Entrepôt, illustrant la prise en compte progressive de différents cas de grossesse et l'accueil de femmes qui ont des ressources économiques diverses à mesure que le XVIII^e siècle se déroule.³ L'association des femmes enceintes sous la plume des directeurs qui signent ces inventaires avec les « condamnées » au Refuge (l'autre catégorie étant composée par les « religieuses & domestiques ») ne laisse cependant pas de doute quant à la vision morale péjorative de leurs contemporains masculins.⁴

La dernière partie de cette communication se concentrera enfin sur l'action principale pour laquelle les femmes sont mises à l'Entrepôt, avant d'en être relâchées : l'accouchement. Sera ainsi abordée la présence, parfois discrète, d'objets nécessaires à la mise au monde des enfants dans les lignes des inventaires. En effet, si ceux-ci sont essentiellement emplis de meubles qui ne bougent que peu de l'établissement et sont présents de façon continue entre 1735 et 1772, certains font directement référence ou sont clairement dédiés à la grossesse et l'accouchement : un grand tableau représentant la Vierge et sainte Marguerite ; différents fauteuils de bois de noyer dès les années 1760, permettant des accouchements assis ; ou encore un banc de bois blanc « servant à faire la visite des femmes », soit un certain suivi gynécologique.⁵ D'autres éléments dont l'usage n'est pas précisé ouvrent la voie à des interprétations plurielles, telle la « chaîne de fer posée contre le mur », dont on ne sait si la présence est destinée à des punitions corporelles ou pour permettre des accouchements plus physiologiques et donc possiblement moins douloureux.⁶ Une chambre spécialement dédiée « pour les accouchées » apparaît en effet dans la seconde moitié du XVIII^e siècle, séparant les parturientes des autres femmes enceintes. Dès lors, si les inventaires détaillés nous renseignent sur les espaces disponibles, l'organisation interne du lieu et les choses qui restent dans la maison, on note l'absence d'objets qui ne sont peut-être pas présents en continu, tels les médicaments. Ceux-ci, tout comme les instruments obstétricaux destinés à aider les femmes à accoucher, sont-ils mobiles et présents uniquement lorsque les personnels de santé (sage-femme, apothicaire, chirurgien dans les cas de complications), tous extérieurs à l'établissement, sont sur place ? Travailler sur l'hôpital de l'Entrepôt induit dès lors de retrouver la place de ces acteurs au sein de l'établissement où résident en continu uniquement les religieuses et les femmes enceintes. Nous terminerons notre communication par des questions plus ouvertes sur l'existence d'une sage-femme municipale dédiée à cet espace, la place de l'hygiène dans l'établissement où la mortalité est très peu élevée et le lien, constant, avec l'Hôtel-Dieu, en cas de maladies en cours de grossesse ou pour la suite de couches. Au carrefour de l'histoire du genre, de l'assistance hospitalière et des enfermements, notre travail vise ainsi à réfléchir aux espaces institutionnalisés dédiés à l'accouchement avant l'invention des maternités en tant que telles, tout en interrogeant, en creux, la place de la naissance dans les lieux de réclusion.

² Xavier Rousseaux, « Crime et justice au prisme de l'histoire visuelle et matérielle, » *Crime, Histoire & Sociétés* 21, no. 2 (2017): 324.

³ ADBdR, 8 HD E 42, Inventaires et règlements (1735-1777), inventaire de l'Entrepôt du 1^{er} septembre 1772.

⁴ ADBdR, 8 HD E 42, Inventaires et règlements (1735-1777), Règlements pour la maison du Refuge que Mrs les Recteurs doivent faire observer, 1735.

⁵ ADBdR, 8 HD E 42, Inventaires et règlements (1735-1777), inventaire de l'Entrepôt du 1^{er} septembre 1772.

⁶ *Idem*.

The Price of Guilt. Material Culture, Economy, and Power Relations in the Prisons of the Duchy of Modena and Reggio Emilia (17th–18th Centuries)

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This paper aims to analyse the economic cost of guilt and its implications for the daily lives of prisoners, taking as a case study the Duchy of Modena and Reggio Emilia between the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. The Este duchy constitutes a particularly interesting context of analysis: a small state located in the heart of northern Italy, where the investigation of prison practices — justice in action — has received only marginal attention in historiography. The analysis focuses on two interconnected axes: on the one hand, the administrative and economic functioning of prisons, understood as microstructures integrated into urban society and the economy of local communities; on the other, the material culture of inmates, shaped by practices of survival, sociability, and limited agency within prison walls, practices often intertwined with financial concerns.

During the early modern period, the financing of prisons and the maintenance of prisoners represented a constant problem for both civil and ecclesiastical authorities. The Ancien Régime prison system was largely based on self-financing, placing the economic burden of detention directly on the prisoner: food, medical care, and legal expenses were formally costs borne by the inmate. However, a significant portion of the prison population consisted of indigent individuals unable to sustain such expenses. This often led to spirals of indebtedness and prolonged imprisonment well beyond the conclusion of legal proceedings, while local and charitable institutions disputed the allocation of unpaid costs. The chronic nature of these problems reveals how poverty was not an incidental variable of the penal system, but rather an integral component of it, also reflecting the broader social reality of the Ancien Régime.

The proportion of indigent prisoners was usually very high. Prison registers from the Municipal Palace of Modena in the second half of the eighteenth century provide a clear example: on average, at least 50% of prisoners lived on charity (in some cases, the percentage even approached 90%). Este's documentation offers further eloquent testimony of this condition: in 1628, for instance, the *podestà* of Carpi wrote to the government urging the swift resolution of cases involving poor prisoners, since they had no means of support, except for the small amount of alms provided by the Confraternity of San Giovanni, otherwise they would die of sheer starvation.

The visitation of prisoners and their sustenance—the sixth corporal work of mercy identified by Christian tradition—was one of the tasks performed by charitable institutions and religious confraternities. These associations, which emerged during the late Middle Ages, played a central role in the Ancien Régime prison system. They were frequently entrusted with the onerous duty of assistance, carried out through the distribution of food, wine, bundles of firewood, and medicines to poor inmates. In Modena this task was entrusted to various institutions, including the *Confraternity of San Giovanni decollato*, which also had the task of comforting those condemned to capital punishment. In the prisons of Reggio Emilia, the task was carried out by the charitable institution called Pia Casa della Carità. Citizens donated to charitable institutions through testamentary bequests, allocating funds to improve the material and spiritual condition of prisoners, for example by setting aside sums for the release of debtors or for celebrating masses on behalf of inmates. However, support for prisoners was not always unconditional. In more than one case, the charitable institutions protested to authorities or refused to cover expenses for various reasons.¹ For instance, in 1630 the Pia Casa della Carità of Reggio Emilia refused to pay for a prisoner's food because he was a foreigner, while in 1683 it argued that it was not obliged to contribute to the expenses of prisoners who had already been convicted.

The process of regulating and controlling confraternities became more pronounced during the eighteenth century. In the Duchy of Modena, as in other contexts, within the broader framework of increasing state, fiscal, and administrative

¹ A practice also found in other European contexts, albeit with evident differences, as in the case of the Compagnie de Charité of Paris. Simon Castainé, "Releasing Debt Prisoners. Study of an Economy of Charity in 18th Century Paris," *Quaderni storici* 58, no. 2 (2023): 391–424. <https://doi.org/10.1408/113414>; Richard Thomas Bell, "Charity, debt and social control in England's early modern prison," *Social History* 47, no. 1 (2022): 1–34. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03071022.2022.2009690>.

centralization, the freedom of action of confraternities was progressively curtailed and many were suppressed.² Charitable institutions were also reformed and incorporated into the administrative.³ For example, with the reform of 1789, the Pia Casa della Carità was assigned responsibility for funding indigent prisoners and paying the salary of the *Procuratore dei poveri*, a publicly appointed magistrate.⁴

The maintenance of prisoners, however, was not entrusted solely to confraternities. Citizens could actively participate through spontaneous almsgiving when passing near prisons, thereby performing a concrete act of charity toward inmates. In Modena, one such form of assistance was the offering box placed at the end of the staircase of the Municipal Palace. The money collected, regularly emptied by the *podestà*, was allocated for prisoners held *alla segreta*, in isolation. Indeed, alms boxes—not only for prisoners—were commonly found in other urban spaces as well.⁵

Money appears frequently in the sources. For instance, during the search of an arrested individual in Reggio Emilia in 1638, part of the money he carried was deposited with the prison keeper, while other coins were left to him and he took them into his cell, where they were later stolen by a fellow inmate.⁶ Moreover, the conditions of imprisonment for both men and women depended not only on personal status but also on economic means. Networks of familial and social solidarity, both inside and outside prison, were essential and enabled prisoners to obtain goods and money.⁷ Money was thus physically present and circulated both inside and outside prison walls.

As noted, the cost of imprisonment could become a financial trap for a large part of the population. One mechanism for escaping this difficult situation was recourse to the sovereign's grace, a «strumento di potere che viola il sistema giuridico garante della giustizia», widely used in the early modern period.⁸ Particularly in the field of criminal justice, the practice illustrates the «differenza tra norma (giuridica) e prassi criminale» that permeated Ancien Régime society.⁹ Yet while grace constitutes a power resource for rulers, signifying submission to authority, it could also be exploited by subjects as a resource to pursue their own interests.¹⁰ Through petitions, often relying on intermediaries, prisoners and convicts could seek remission or reduction of their sentences or debts by appealing to the supreme authority of the sovereign, who could override the strict application of the law through discretionary power.¹¹

Recourse to ducal grace appears in some cases as the decisive solution for prisoners trapped in seemingly inescapable situations, as in the case of two men from Quattro Castella imprisoned for nearly five months in Reggio Emilia. They were sentenced to a monetary fine of 200 gold scudi for smuggling calves into the neighbouring state of Parma and were held in prison pending payment. Their survival within prison walls, however, was entrusted to the Casa della Carità due to their total destitution and inability to pay the cost of their offense. To resolve the impasse, the *Procuratore dei poveri* proposed their release through ducal grace: continuing to detain them would result in a double loss, as justice would not recover the fine, and the Casa della Carità would have to continue feeding them at the expense of other needy prisoners. They were thus pardoned on Easter Day 1760, on condition of exile from the state at the duke's discretion.¹²

The payment of expenses was therefore a major issue, to the extent that the Codice Estense, a body of legislation promulgated in 1771, stipulated that judges could not detain prisoners beyond the term of their sentence for the payment of court expenses. In particular, pardoned prisoners were released from all expenses, except for the food received¹³. While in urban contexts the cost for indigent prisoners was largely borne by charitable institutions, in

² Elio Tavilla, "Confraternite e riforme nel Settecento estense," in *Condividere la fede. Archivi di confraternite dell'Emilia Romagna*, ed. G. Zacchè (Mucchi editore, 2009), 25.

³ In the Belgian context of the early nineteenth century, during the years of French occupation, "les confrères sont assimilés à des 'agents' de l'État". Xavier Rousseaux. "Prendre soin du détenu, surveiller l'enfermement. Les Compagnies de la Miséricorde dans l'espace belge de l'Ancien Régime aux Révolutions (1600-1830)," *Criminocorpus* 23 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.4000/criminocorpus.13498>.

⁴ *Riforma delle Opere Pie di Reggio ordinata da S.A. Serenissima [...] Ercole III [...]* (Dalla stamperia di Giuseppe Davolio, 1789), fol. 7.

⁵ In the case of the "Prigioni della Piazza" in Reggio Emilia, there are even references to prisoners lowering bags from the prison windows into which passers-by would directly place alms. See A. Balletti, *Storia di Reggio nell'Emilia*, (L. Bonvicini e soc. Coop. Lav. Tipografi, 1925), 348.

⁶ Archivio di Stato di Reggio Emilia (ASRE), Fondo Curie della Città, Indizi, b. 106 (1638-1639), fols. 203r - 204v, Nov. 3, 1638.

⁷ Natalia Muchnik, "«A Whore entering into prison is a Honey-pot». Les geôles au féminin (xvi^e-xviii^e siècles)," *Criminocorpus* 23 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.4000/criminocorpus.13258>.

⁸ "An instrument of power that undermines the legal system that guarantees justice" (the law). Karl Härter, "Grazia ed equità nella dialettica tra sovranità, diritto e giustizia dal tardo medioevo all'età moderna," in *Grazia e giustizia. Figure della clemenza fra tardo medioevo ed età contemporanea*, ed. C. Nubola and K. Härter (Il Mulino, 2011), 46.

⁹ "The difference between (legal) norms and criminal practice". Härter, "Grazia ed equità", 51.

¹⁰ Härter, "Grazia ed equità", 47.

¹¹ In the Este states, as in other contexts, in addition to occasions linked to joyful events concerning the ducal family, acts of grace toward criminals were frequently granted on the occasion of major Christian festivities: Easter, Christmas, and the Octave of Saint Geminianus, patron saint of the city of Modena.

¹² Archivio di Stato di Modena (ASM), Fondo Archivio Segreto Estense, Condanne e condannati, b. 12.

¹³ *Codice di leggi e costituzioni per gli Stati di Sua Altezza Serenissima*, vol. 1, (Modena: 1771), fols. 44-49.

provincial communities—where these networks were absent or less structured—the burden often fell on the prisoner’s community of origin, often leading to legal disputes with the ducal treasury for reimbursement.

The prison thus emerges as a privileged observatory for reflecting on the interactions between economy, spaces of confinement, and everyday experiences in an Ancien Régime state. It was not merely an institution reflecting the administration of justice, but a nexus of social, economic, and political relations that cut across society, situated at the intersection of assistance and punishment, poverty management and territorial governance.

The prison emerges as a lived space, a theatre of daily practices, negotiations, and resistances: it is within this framework that the present contribution is situated, with the aim of enriching knowledge of the Este prison system. The transformations of this local system may be placed in dialogue with the broader reality of Italian and European penal systems between the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries.

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Everyday Materiality in Venetian Inquisition Prisons

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Inquisition sources provide significant insights into the materiality of everyday life and the sociability of people imprisoned as alleged witches and/or heretics during the Sixteenth and Seventeenth centuries. While trials have long attracted scholarly attention, prisons themselves—seen not only as spaces of coercion but also as arenas of interaction and negotiation—remain less explored. This paper asks: how did material conditions shape the experiences, relationships, and self-perceptions of inmates in Venetian Inquisition prisons?

Drawing on case studies from Venetian archives and considering figures ranging from men of culture to social marginals, from famous courtesans to unknown poor women, the paper examines prisons as dynamic environments in which materiality mediated social relations. Within these spaces, money, food, books, ideas, disease, and even sex circulated, though access to such resources was uneven and structured by cultural, class, and gender dynamics. These factors could soften or exacerbate confinement and shaped relationships among prisoners, with jailers, and with the outside world.

Inquisition sources are particularly valuable both for the pleas addressed by inmates to the judges—offering direct insight into their material experiences—and for trial records, which illuminate exchanges, hierarchies, and forms of agency within and beyond prison walls.

Every-day «purgatories»: inmates' pleas

The first section of the paper focuses on inmates' petitions as privileged access points to the everyday materiality of confinement. Although shaped by rhetorical strategies aimed at eliciting mercy, these pleas are precious as they open a window on the *things* that were available to confined individuals, fulfilling one of the main goals of material history.¹ Moreover, as sources produced by the inmates themselves, they provide insights into another dimension of the everyday materiality, namely that of their own bodies: their (deformed) shapes, (rancid) smells, (creepy) sounds.

Venetian prisons were notoriously overcrowded and unhealthy environments, characterized by filth, extreme temperatures, and lack of hygiene.² Angelica Spadaro's case, incarcerated as an anabaptist along with her four-year-old daughter in 1551, offers a particularly vivid example.³ In her plea she described herself as «buried alive,» weakened by hunger and illness, while her child's body became «putrid» due to filth and neglect. In her plea, Angelica suggested that, being ill, she could «no longer help herself» (*mi atrovo si mal conditionata che non me posso più aggiutar*). This implies that her condition had worsened over time, and that in the early months she may have found ways to obtain what she needed—perhaps by negotiating with other prisoners, jailers, or people from outside. When she entered prison, she was six months pregnant: it is plausible that during her pregnancy the authorities may have provided her with additional food to preserve the innocent life she was carrying but reduced it afterwards. That she received some care as a pregnant woman is indicated by the fact that she was allowed to give birth outside the prison and was only brought back one month after the birth. This shows that also material biological conditions structured access to resources.

Her husband too, Zuan Giacomo, who was arrested with her and remained in jail for 13 years, sent several pleas to the judges⁴. In such documents he described confinement as a form of «purgatory,» a suspended condition between life and death. His references to hunger, disease, and overcrowding are accompanied by descriptions of forced proximity—eighty or more inmates sharing space, noise, and stench. Beyond describing materiality as deprivation, his attempts to engage in informal labour suggest that economic activity persisted inside prison walls.

Dramatic pleas, useful for reconstructing the everyday materiality of prison life, were also submitted by the inmate Girolamo Donzellini, a physician who was tried five times by the Inquisition during the sixteenth century and ultimately executed in 1587.⁵ A particularly extensive one is the petition he wrote during the plague of 1575, which burst out when

¹ Leora Auslander, "Material Culture and Materiality," in *Travelling Concepts for the Study of Culture*, ed. B. Neumann and A. Nünning, (De Gruyter, 2012), 353–70, 354.

² Giovanni Scarabello, *Le prigioni di Venezia. Carcerati e carceri dal XII al XVIII secolo*, (Supernova, 2016).

³ Archivio di Stato di Venezia (ASV), Sant'Uffizio, Processi, Processus contra anabatistas, Busta (b.) 11.

⁴ *Idem*.

⁵ *Idem*, Contro Girolamo Donzellini, b. 39.

he was serving a life sentence.⁶ Describing the altered conditions of his imprisonment during the epidemic Donzellini implicitly refers to ordinary conditions of confinement, thereby shedding light on everyday prison life.

Inside and outside

The following section of my paper shall address the relationship between the prison's interior and exterior spaces. Prisons were not closed systems but porous spaces in which material exchanges structured daily life. Food in particular constituted the essential medium of interaction between inside and outside. Since Venetian authorities provided only minimal sustenance, inmates depended heavily on external networks of support.

Evidence shows that these exchanges were widespread and socially diverse. The prostitute Lunarda Furlana received food from her clients during imprisonment, while Caterina la Sartora maintained a long-term relationship with the inmate Publio Francesco Spinola, her mentor in heresy, providing him not only with food but also bed linen.⁷ These exchanges reveal how material goods were embedded in affective, economic, and sometimes instructional relationships that resisted detention.

The case of Bellina Loredana, imprisoned multiple times for witchcraft, further demonstrates the durability of such networks over time.⁸ Even in old age and under life imprisonment, she mobilized long-standing relationships to obtain food and assistance. Some witnesses described providing her with meat «for God's sake,» while others acknowledged ongoing material support. Her case reveals how social capital accumulated outside prison could be reactivated within confinement.

Information also circulated through these channels. Prisoners communicated across cells and with the outside world via intermediaries, shaping both legal strategies and everyday survival. In some cases, inmates coordinated responses to interrogations or prepared witnesses in advance, demonstrating that confinement did not interrupt but rather reconfigured communication networks.

Crucially, prison officials played a decisive role in regulating these flows. The case of the Captain of the Inquisition Hieronimo Vitrario, he himself denounced for corruption to the Holy Office in 1588, illustrates how access to food, movement, and even temporary release could be transformed into an economy of favours.⁹ Wealthier inmates could secure privileges through payment, while poorer prisoners were excluded even from basic rights. Confinement thus appears as a stratified system in which material inequality was continuously reproduced and reinforced.

Sex and the prison

Within this economy, sexual relations constituted another form of material exchange, which the paper will address. Far from being incidental, sexuality functioned as a resource that could secure food, protection, or improved living conditions. Prostitutes and courtesans, who often were put on trial for witchcraft, were particularly positioned within these dynamics, as their social identities enabled them to mobilize sexual capital both inside and outside prison.

Cases such as Lunarda Furlana's show how sexual relations inside prison were directly connected to survival, as her partners (other male prisoners) provided material support in exchange for intimacy. Similarly, courtesans such as Angela Giustiniana, tried in 1625, benefited from preferential treatment, including relocation to safer and more comfortable spaces, reportedly due to sexual relationships with jailers.¹⁰

In other cases, sexuality intersected with institutional power. Relationships facilitated by the above-mentioned Captain Hieronimo between inmates and external partners demonstrate how sexual access could be mediated and controlled by prison authorities.

Objects' meaning in confinement

Another section of this paper examines the shift in meaning that objects underwent in conditions of confinement. In the prison context, objects were never neutral. Their meanings altered according to judicial interpretation and material conditions. Food, for example, could transform from sustenance into evidence of deviance: when consumed in violation of fasting rules, it became a marker of heresy. Similarly, food provided by outsiders to prisoners could be reinterpreted as proof of ideological complicity.

⁶ The plea is published entirely in Alessandra Celati, "The Experience of the Physician Girolamo Donzellini in the 1575 Venetian Plague: Between Scientia and Heterodoxy," in *Scientiae in the history of medicine*, ed. F. Baldassarri and F. Zampieri (L'Erma di Bretschneider, 2021), 189–216.

⁷ ASV, Sant'Uffizio, Processi, Contro Lunarda Furlana, b. 29; ASV, Sant'Uffizio, Processi, Denuncia contra Caterina moglie de m.o Francesco Sartor [in Contro Giambattista Gemma], b. 37

⁸ *Idem*, Contro Bellina Loredana, b. 77.

⁹ *Idem*, Denuntia per Horatii Dandoli, b. 61.

¹⁰ *Idem*, Contra Angelam Iustinianam meretricem, b. 66.

Even beyond the problematic interpretation of objects by judges and their use as indicators of guilt in trials, the issue of the status and meaning of *things* in prisons touches on deep personal/emotional and social dimensions. Since human beings tend to objectify themselves in something durable and non-transient, they elevate certain possessions to a higher status, subtracting them from common usage. Even ordinary objects, when charged with affective significance through close contact with their owners, can become «individualized goods».¹¹ In the context of confinement, such objects acquire an even stronger identity-related significance - as will be shown referring again to the case of Girolamo Donzellini.

Objects removed from utilitarian functions become *semiophores* connecting the individual sphere with invisible dimensions such as beauty, the sacred, or other abstract meanings.¹² My sources show that also allegedly marginal women like Bellina Loredana could subject their possessions to this process. Paintings, household goods, and ceramics were preserved by Bellina as carriers of meaning and of self-identity. Nevertheless, in confinement such process of meaning-making was interrupted by another form of materiality: that of deprivation, and objects returned to being commodities. While drafting her last will in prison, Bellina claimed ownership of several items, held by debtors or stored with acquaintances, demanding their return.¹³ Yet her aim was not to pass them on to relatives, but to assign them to her lawyer and to the daughter of her jailer as a dowry—a way to improve her conditions of detention in the final years of her life. In this sense, her possessions were ultimately reactivated as instruments of exchange, no longer preserving identity meaning but mobilized to negotiate better living conditions in confinement.

Deviance

The last part of the paper will address how *illicit things* - ideas, books, practices - circulated within Venetian prisons. Indeed, far from suppressing religious deviance, confinement often facilitated its transmission and replication. Books, oral teachings, and magical practices linked inmates together. In one case, Marcantonio Prata adopted heretical ideas after prolonged exposure to fellow inmates.¹⁴ Similarly, cases involving the circulation of Agrippa's works, or the practice of using beans for divination among female inmates, reveal how prisons operated as unexpected nodes of knowledge exchange.¹⁵ These processes suggest that prisons not only contained deviance but paradoxically ended up reproducing and intensifying it.

Taken together, these perspectives reveal how the material conditions of confinement shaped not only daily survival, but also systems of meaning, exchange, and interaction, in a world in which deprivation and negotiation coexisted.

¹¹ Renata Ago, *Il gusto delle cose. Una storia degli oggetti nella Roma del Seicento* (Donzelli editore, 2006), XXVIII.

¹² *Idem*, XXVI.

¹³ ASV, Notarile, Testamenti, Testamento di Bellina Loredana, b. 86.

¹⁴ ASV, Sant'Uffizio, Processi, Contro Guido Antonio De Prata, b. 32.

¹⁵ *Idem*, Contro Giovan Battista Capponi, b. 61. Giuseppina Minchella, "Pratiche di magia nella Repubblica di Venezia in età moderna," in *Magia, superstizione, religione. Una questione di confini*, ed. M. Caffiero (Edizioni di storia e letteratura, 2015).

Dans les *Tolbooths* du nord de l'Écosse : Matérialité et expériences de l'enfermement pour dette au XVIII^e siècle

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Walter Scott, dans *The Heart of Midlothian*, décrit la prison du XVIII^e siècle, et plus particulièrement *The old tolbooth* d'Édimbourg, comme « une espèce de lieu où l'infortune est heureusement confondue avec le crime, et où tous ceux qui y sont enfermés désirent en sortir ». ¹ Les infortunés dont il est question dans cet extrait sont les débiteurs qui occupent un grand nombre des cellules écossaises au cours du siècle. La pénurie monétaire généralisée fait des relations de crédit interpersonnelles une nécessité pour chaque échange du quotidien, autant dans les grandes villes que dans les petites communautés villageoises. Le droit écossais, conservé malgré l'Union de 1707 avec l'Angleterre, permet aux créanciers de suivre toute une procédure avant de pouvoir enfermer leurs débiteurs dans les prisons locales jusqu'au remboursement de la dette. ² Les barreaux de la *tolbooth* créent une frontière fermée et une mise à l'écart de l'individu avec sa communauté. Or, dans cette communication, je souhaite interroger la porosité de cet emprisonnement pour dette, à travers notamment la matérialité des lieux, des pratiques judiciaires et des relations sociales qui s'infiltrent à travers les cellules.

C'est dans le nord de l'Écosse que je tente d'observer les conditions locales qui façonnent l'enfermement pour dette. Je m'intéresse tout particulièrement à la société rurale de l'Aberdeenshire et des Highlands. Cette région est au cœur de changements profonds au cours de l'époque moderne et tout particulièrement au XVIII^e siècle avec la transition d'une société fortement clanique vers le développement de grandes propriétés foncières soutenant les améliorations agraires. L'organisation sociale est très hiérarchisée, avec à son sommet les landlords, puis les *tacksman* qui sous-louent les terres et prélèvent les loyers au principal tenant. Pour autant, la majorité des habitants de ces contrées sont des petits *subtenants* ou bien encore, au plus bas de l'échelle sociale, des *crofters*. ³ Il y a également les habitants des villes qui sont au cœur des échanges économiques cet espace : les marchands, les boutiquiers, les artisans, ou bien encore les domestiques. Or, les individus sont loin d'être apathiques et s'emparent de leurs droits afin d'emprisonner les mauvais payeurs, qu'ils soient leurs voisins, leurs employeurs, ou bien même d'une catégorie sociale plus élevée que la leur. Je m'intéresse également aux îles des Orcades et des Shetland, où les relations de crédit sont d'autant plus complexes que leur éloignement de l'Écosse continentale est fort. L'insularité pose la question de l'isolement de ces sociétés et des adaptations locales en ce qui concerne la gestion des débiteurs sur place.

Régler ces litiges économiques sur la place publique, via le recours aux institutions judiciaires, produit une matérialité du conflit avant l'enfermement. Comme l'explique Xavier Rousseaux, il est possible de penser conjointement la production écrite autour du règlement du litige et les rituels publics qui rendent visibles pour l'ensemble de la communauté l'exécution du jugement. ⁴ Il est ainsi possible de faire dialoguer les nombreux écrits des intellectuels qui établissent des traités de droit écossais et la production des documents de l'exercice de la justice, créant une véritable matérialité du processus judiciaire. Parallèlement, les rituels de performance sont également d'une grande importance en rendant la justice visible. Cette visibilité s'incarne dans une série de rituels publics, depuis l'annonce faite par un crieur du défaut de paiement, qualifiant le débiteur de rebelle devant toute la communauté, jusqu'à la mise en scène de l'arrestation, en passant par la vente aux enchères des derniers biens du débiteur. Le caractère visible de la dette et de sa condamnation renforce le poids de la sanction.

¹ Walter Scott, *The Heart of Mid-Lothian* (Tauchnitz, 1858).

² *An Introduction to Scottish Legal History*, vol. 20 (Stair Society, 1958); *An Introductory Survey of the Sources and Literature of Scots Law*, vol. 1 (Stair Society, 1936).

³ Bruce Lenman, *An Economic History of Modern Scotland, 1660–1976* (Batsford, 1977); T. M. Devine, *The Scottish Clearances: A History of the Dispossessed, 1600–1900* (Allen Lane, 2018).

⁴ Xavier Rousseaux, "Crime et justice au prisme de l'histoire visuelle et matérielle," *Crime, Histoire & Sociétés / Crime, History & Societies* 21, no. 2 (2017): 321–334.

Une fois en prison, les conditions matérielles de l'enfermement des corps pouvaient être extrêmement éprouvantes. Les pétitions des débiteurs auprès des magistrats, les rapports médicaux témoignant des décès en prison, ainsi que les traces archéologiques, permettent d'avoir accès à la brutalité qu'exerce l'emprisonnement sur les corps. Il fallait endurer le climat de ces régions septentrionales, subir la propagation des vermines, et cohabiter régulièrement dans la même cellule, indépendamment du sexe, du motif de l'emprisonnement, ou bien de l'état de santé des prisonniers. La surpopulation se fait sentir si intensément après la défaite de Culloden (1746) que les autorités d'Aberdeen se retrouvent obligées de créer une prison éphémère en face de la *tolbooth*.

Ainsi, ces prisons locales sont exiguës et ne permettent que rarement la séparation des prisonniers. De plus, l'architecture de ces espaces est le reflet d'adaptations locales aux contextes historiques et géographiques. La privation de liberté est ainsi inscrite dans le paysage communautaire. Si les *tolbooth* d'Inverness et d'Aberdeen ont été construites dès le XVI^e et le XVII^e siècle, il faut attendre le milieu du XVIII^e siècle pour que Kirkwall, aux Orcades, se dote d'une prison sécurisée. Avant cela, les débiteurs étaient faits prisonniers dans le château du comte puis dans la maison d'un bourgeois de la ville. Ce sont les fuites récurrentes qui obligent les autorités à se doter finalement d'un lieu désigné pour accueillir les prisonniers. Les plans de cette prison font l'objet de plusieurs concertations. Lorsqu'au début du XIX^e siècle certains détenus se plaignent des conditions inhumaines dans lesquelles ils évoluent, les magistrats y répondent en témoignant des quelques rénovations qui ont pu y être faites et en rappelant que la prison n'est pas faite pour devenir un espace accueillant et où il fait bon vivre. Toutefois, ils accordent à ces derniers la possibilité d'être transférés dans une autre *tolbooth* plus près de chez eux s'ils le souhaitent.

En effet, ces bâtiments sont tous situés au cœur de la ville. La prison est dès lors créatrice d'une certaine distance dans la proximité, puisque les débiteurs sont loin d'être complètement mis au ban de la société, séjournant au plus près des activités communautaires. La proximité du débiteur en prison avec son réseau de soutien est une obligation légale écossaise. L'objectif de l'incarcération pour dette est avant tout que le débiteur rembourse la somme due. L'emprisonner près de sa résidence lui permet d'essayer d'améliorer sa situation financière depuis sa cellule. Le confort de ces prisonniers particuliers dépend alors étroitement de leurs capitaux matériels et relationnels à l'extérieur des murs, dont la porosité est à questionner. Natalia Muchnik, dans son ouvrage sur l'enfermement des minorités entre le XVI^e et le XVIII^e siècle, témoigne de cette porosité des espaces carcéraux de l'époque moderne.⁵ Elle exprime l'idée que les geôles constituent paradoxalement des espaces de liberté et d'autonomie pour les minorités religieuses. L'historienne explique alors qu'il n'est pas rare de voir des allées et venues en prison. Le caractère urbain de la geôle permet ainsi de multiplier les contacts avec l'extérieur. Les débiteurs doivent réussir à gérer leurs affaires, rembourser leur dette et subvenir à leurs besoins en prison.

Si les institutions judiciaires écossaises n'abordent pas la question des visites, cela ne signifie pas qu'elles sont absentes. La *tolbooth* est loin d'être complètement isolée de l'extérieur et les murs ne demeurent pas hermétiques. L'isolement est relatif et dépend d'un débiteur à l'autre. Il y a une dépendance aux ressources extérieures, créatrice d'inégalités en prison. Alors que certains peuvent vivre assez confortablement, comme le Lord Arbuthnot dont la mère se démène pour lui faire parvenir les meilleures denrées en prison, d'autres se retrouvent affamés et obligés de faire une pétition dans l'espoir que leur alimentation en prison soit prise en charge par leur propre créancier.

À cela s'ajoute la question des libérations temporaires accordées par le droit écossais aux prisonniers malades. La mention de ces *Sick Bills*, attestée par un *act of sederunt* de 1671, apparaît également dans les traités de droit, comme dans *An Institute of the Law of Scotland* de John Erskine.⁶ Néanmoins, tous les prisonniers malades ne peuvent pas en bénéficier puisque le détenu doit être considéré en danger de mort s'il demeure confiné dans sa geôle. L'application réelle de ce principe demeure à la discrétion des magistrats locaux puisque les archives témoignent de débiteurs malades ne bénéficiant d'aucun secours, tandis que d'autres profitent d'une libération anticipée. Le débiteur reste théoriquement libre jusqu'à ce qu'il soit guéri et que son créancier demande à nouveau aux magistrats son incarcération. Toutefois, dans certains cas, dès sa mise en liberté, le débiteur doit promettre solennellement de revenir de lui-même en prison, une fois son état de santé rétabli. Négociations, sorties temporaires et circulations rythment ainsi la vie de la prison. La matérialité des espaces d'emprisonnement crée un lieu à part, qui exacerbe d'une nouvelle manière les inégalités entre les individus.

C'est également le cas lors de la libération du débiteur puisque la sanction ne disparaît pas. S'il y a un remboursement de la dette ou une renégociation avec le créancier, alors il faut pouvoir se réintégrer dans les circuits d'échange malgré l'humiliation publique subie par le passage en prison. Si la libération des débiteurs les plus pauvres s'obtient par le don de tous leurs biens au créancier, ils peuvent également être obligés de porter un habit stigmatisant, renforçant ainsi la sanction hors des murs de la prison. Cette matérialité est pourtant difficile à appréhender.

En effet, comme l'écrit l'historienne Sophie Abdela, la difficulté des archives est un fait : « non seulement sont-elles rares et éparées, surtout pour les époques médiévale et moderne, mais elles sont presque toujours produites par les

⁵ Natalia Muchnik, *Les prisons de la foi. L'enfermement des minorités (XVI^e–XVIII^e siècle)* (Presses universitaires de France, 2019).

⁶ John Erskine, *An Institute of the Law of Scotland* (Bell & Bradfute, 1773).

autorités ».⁷ Afin d'étudier les débiteurs incarcérés dans le nord de l'Écosse, je m'appuie en effet en particulier sur les fonds d'archives des cours de justice des baillis et des shérifs d'Inverness, de Kirkwall et de Lerwick, sur des archives policières de la fin du XVIII^e siècle, ainsi que sur les registres de la prison d'Aberdeen. Ces documents sont avant tout produits par les autorités. Ils éclairent la matérialité de l'administration carcérale mais ne mettent pas au centre de leur discours les expériences vécues par les prisonniers. Il faut alors chercher entre les lignes pour avoir accès à la voix des débiteurs détenus. L'analyse de rares archives privées, en particulier des lettres (famille, partenaires commerciaux, avocat, médecin), permet de pallier les limites des archives institutionnelles et ainsi de mettre en lumière la matérialité des échanges et des pratiques qui structurent l'expérience de l'enfermement pour dette.

⁷ Sophie Abdela, "Vivre l'enfermement : pratiques, expériences et parcours de détention (XVI^e-XIX^e siècles)," *Criminocorpus* 23 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.4000/criminocorpus.13169>.

“The Worthy Refreshment of those Turks Enchained in the Galleys”: Selling and Consuming Coffee in an Early Modern Mediterranean Port City

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In 1683, Lorenzo Gonieri *turco*, a ‘Turkish’ galley slave from Pylos who ran a coffee stall (*botteghina*) in Livorno’s port, was arrested on suspicion of owning a *stiletto* dagger.¹ About two years earlier, he had converted to Christianity and taken on his godfather’s name and surname: Lorenzo Gonieri, an important official in the local slave prison (the *bagno*) and galleys. In a letter sent to Secretary of War Francesco Panciaticchi (d. 1701), Gonieri asked that his ‘Turkish’ namesake be found innocent and exempted from paying the fees deriving from his arrest and incarceration, as he was destitute and had a family to support.² While Panciaticchi’s reply does not tell us how the trial went, it does offer an interesting insight: the Secretary of War was not worried about the slave escaping while awaiting his sentence, since “he has a wife and children, as well as an open stall.”³ Such an observation opens up a series of questions regarding the relationship between slaves, coffee and society. This study aims at deepening our knowledge of this relationship by analysing how “Turkish” slaves in Livorno made use of an element of their foodways to interact with their host society and negotiate their socioeconomic standing through the production and consumption of coffee.

Lorenzo Gonieri *turco*’s case was far from an exception in late 17th and early 18th century Mediterranean port cities. Salvatore Bono and Lucette Valensi have shown precisely how enslaved Ottoman subjects negotiated and affirmed their presence in their captors’ cities.⁴ Building on Vittorio Salvadorini’s research, Cesare Santus and Stephanie Nadalo have provided historians with crucial details on the everyday lives of these slaves in Early Modern Livorno, which at the time housed one of the largest Muslim slave populations in Europe.⁵ The individuals that made up this community were mostly victims of Christian corsairs, who preyed on Ottoman vessels and coastal towns throughout the 16th-18th centuries.⁶ Although a violent and predatory phenomenon, Giovanna Fiume has described corsair warfare’s contribution to Mediterranean trade networks by making a continuous exchange of people, money and goods possible.⁷ On a related note, Giulia Bonazza and Andrea Zappia have pointed out the value in studying the mobility – both of goods and of people – inherent to corsair warfare to better grasp the degree of globalisation affecting Early Modern Mediterranean port cities.⁸

The relationship between coffee and the slave community in Livorno, as studied by local historians Michele Montanelli and Clara Errico, aptly highlights the role played by ‘Turkish’ slaves in turning coffee into one of Livorno’s staple drinks.⁹ By adopting Giorgio Riello and Anne Gerritsen’s approach to material culture, which integrates global trajectories into the “social lives” of things, coffee will thus be analysed here in one of the first

¹ Archivio di Stato di Firenze (ASFi), Mediceo del Principato (MdP) f. 2099, c. 519.

² ASFi, MdP f. 2099, c. 519.

³ Archivio di Stato di Livorno (ASLi), Compagnie Soppresse f. 226, c. 189, also found in Vittorio Salvadorini, “Traffici con i paesi islamici e schiavi a Livorno nel XVII secolo: problemi e suggestioni di Vittorio Salvadorini,” in *Atti del convegno “Livorno e il Mediterraneo nell’età medicea”* (U. Bastogi editore, 1978), 241.

⁴ Salvatore Bono, *Schiavi: una storia mediterranea (XVI-XIX secolo)* (Il Mulino, 2021); Lucette Valensi, *Ces Étrangers Familiers: Musulmans En Europe (XVIe-XVIIIe Siècles)* (Payot, 2012).

⁵ Salvadorini, “Traffici”, 206–55; Cesare Santus, *Il Turco a Livorno* (Officina Libraria, 2019), 40–52; Stephanie Nadalo, *Constructing Pluralism in Seventeenth Century Livorno: Managing Religious Minorities in a Mediterranean Free Port (1537-1737)*, PhD dissertation (Northwestern University, 2013), 226–72.

⁶ Santus, *Il Turco*, 28–33.

⁷ Giovanna Fiume, *Mediterraneo Corsaro: Storie di schiavi, pirati e rinnegati in età moderna* (Carocci editore, 2025), 32.

⁸ Giulia Bonazza and Andrea Zappia, “Mobilità e stanzialità nello spazio portuale tra Mediterraneo e Atlantico (secoli XVII-XIX). Introduzione,” *Proposte e ricerche. Rivista di storia economica e sociale* 46, no. 90 (2023): 21, https://doi.org/10.48219/PR_0392179490.

⁹ Michele Montanelli and Clara Errico, *Il caffè a Livorno nei secoli XVII e XVIII* (CtI editore, 2019).

steps of its “global life.”¹⁰ To this end, how the economic and cultural relationships in Livorno signified coffee will be studied to read its production and consumption as a means employed by slaves for shaping and interacting with their surroundings.¹¹ Such interactions could even breach the physical and legal barriers between galley slaves and the rest of the port city’s population: in 1671, Cardinal Domenico Magri spoke of how the slaves of La Valletta’s *bagno* would regularly receive locals who sought to taste their drink.¹² A similar situation seems to have existed in the Livornese *bagno*, where the rest of the population could “go and do business with the crews so as to buy from them, sell or visit them.”¹³

The role of coffee in mediating interactions between ‘Turkish’ slaves and Livornese society cannot be fully understood without focusing on instances of autonomous slave labour. More precisely, this presentation will integrate instances of coffee *botteghe* and stalls run by slaves ashore with other establishments where they sold food and drink, such as the shacks in the inner harbour (*darsena*) and in the *bagno*. Following Zappia’s suggestion, slave-run businesses will be analysed to contribute to recent historical works that seek to go beyond the dichotomy between freedom and enslavement in studying both labour and slavery.¹⁴ This approach is particularly fruitful for the case of Livorno, where in 1701 several ‘Turkish’ slaves employed free Christians as apprentices in their shops.¹⁵ In practical terms, when analysing slave-run coffee businesses in Livorno, this presentation will differentiate the slave’s absence of liberty as a worker from their absence of liberty as human beings.¹⁶

As coffee circulated in Livorno, it accumulated many meanings. First and foremost, it was a tool of economic and legal emancipation for slaves like Mustafa Topal, who bought his own freedom with the earnings made from running a coffee *bottega*.¹⁷ Secondly, coffee consumption could also have figured as an act of displacement, as the familiar taste and its symbolic ties to the slaves’ native cultures could allow them brief sensorial escape from the confined, unsanitary environment of the galleys and the *bagno*.¹⁸ Thus, the ties between slaves, their foodways and their senses could also be mobilised by the former to foster instances of communal identity. An eloquent example of such a dynamic occurred on the night of 15 January 1678, when a burglary was committed next to a coffee *bottega* managed by two private slaves – Ali Bais d’Amorato di Aden and Maomet d’Alì di Costantinopoli – and frequented by many other slaves who would spend their time there drinking, singing and playing games “*alla Turchesca*.”¹⁹ Such a qualitative approach benefits from the employment of contemporary ego-documents, as they offer a vivid, if sometimes crude, insight into everyday life in Livorno. However, similar sources need to be integrated by administrative and judicial documents in the Tuscan archives. Letters sent by Livornese officials like Gonieri to the Granducal court and appeals (*suppliche*) penned by slaves have offered a more nuanced picture of the labour relations and the social dynamics that the sale of coffee by enslaved individuals engendered in Livorno.

Through the combination of these sources, it has been possible to identify the crucial role played by the *de facto* legal and economic representative of the ‘Turkish’ slave community in Livorno: the *Capo Mercante dei Turchi*.²⁰ In fact, *suppliche* and letters on criminal and civil affairs have shown how this individual benefited from the management of several *botteghe* in the city, including a coffee *bottega* in *via San Giovanni*. Indeed, the *Capi Mercanti* built communitarian and personal ties with this establishment, as one *Capo* claimed in 1704 that it had been passed on from successor to successor for years “as if they had acquired for this reason a pre-emption right.”²¹

¹⁰ Anne Gerritsen and Giorgio Riello, *The Global Lives of Things* (Routledge, 2016); for the original concept of the “social life of things”, cf. Arjun Appadurai (ed.), *The Social Life of Things: Commodities in Cultural Perspective* (Cambridge University Press, 1986).

¹¹ Pamela Smith, “Itineraries of Materials and Knowledge in the Early Modern World,” in *The Global Lives of Things*, eds. A. Gerritsen and G. Riello, 49.

¹² Domenico Magri, *Virtù del Kafe’ Bevanda introdotta nuovamente nell’Italia* (Per Michele Hercole, 1671).

¹³ ASFi, MdP, f. 2132, Costituzioni, et ordinationi dell’offitio del Capitano del Bagno, cap. 13.

¹⁴ Andrea Zappia, “Il mestiere che facevo era di servire il mio padrone in quello mi comandava. Quotidianità, coercizione e lavoro dei captivi cristiani nel Nord Africa barbaresco (XVII-XVIII sec.),” in *Libertà e coercizione: il lavoro in una prospettiva di lungo periodo*, eds. G. Bonazza and G. Ongaro (New Digital Frontiers, 2018), 97–122; Benedetta Chizzolini, “Navigating Ambiguities: Fluid Identities and Legal Nuances among Galley Rowers (Great Duchy of Tuscany, 16th–18th centuries),” *Journal of Global Slavery* 10, no. 1 (2025): 53–79, <https://doi.org/10.1163/2405836X-01001001>.

¹⁵ ASFi, MdP f. 2222, c. 438, cited in Lucia Frattarelli Fischer, “Ebrei a Pisa e Livorno nel Sei e Settecento tra Inquisizioni e Garanzie Granducali,” in *Le inquisizioni cristiane e gli ebrei* (Accademia nazionale dei Lincei, 2003), 292.

¹⁶ Zappia, “Il mestiere,” 120.

¹⁷ Salvatore Bono, *Schiavi musulmani nell’Italia moderna: Galeotti, vu’ cumpra’, domestici* (Edizioni Scientifiche Italiane, 1999), 342.

¹⁸ Nicholas Terpstra, *Senses of Space in the Early Modern World* (Cambridge University Press, 2024), 48.

¹⁹ ASLi, Capitano, poi Governatore Auditore Vicario (Capitano), f. 311, negozio 70 anno 1677.

²⁰ On this figure, cf. Santus, *Il Turco*, 46.

²¹ ASFi, MdP f. 2269, 19/05/1704.

As for studying the materiality of slave-run businesses and how they impacted everyday life, iconographic sources and inventories of coffee *botteghe* allow crucial insight. One example is represented by an anonymous 18th century painting, *La darsena livornese*, which gives a colourful and detailed representation of how one of the slave stalls in the Livornese inner harbour operated. It shows how the *darsena* was a bustling contact zone characterised by liminality, where sailors, slaves, officials, dockworkers and merchants would engage in economic and social interactions. One of the most profitable stalls in this space was managed by 'Turkish' slaves, who were even exempted from galley service given its importance for the Tuscan coffers.²² Alongside meat, this stall sold many other foodstuffs and drink, as well as fostering instances of sociability.²³ Analysing similar establishments allows us to draw parallels with the management and regulation of slave-owned coffee *botteghe* and port *botteghini*, as in Gonieri *turco's* case. Moreover, as Huguenot galley slave Jean Marteilhe (d. 1777) observed in 18th century Marseilles, 'Turkish' slaves serving coffee from makeshift stalls in the inner harbour could have been a familiar sight in Early Modern Mediterranean port cities.²⁴

The spatial and economic liberty that slaves benefitted from in Livorno allowed them to affirm their presence through autonomous labour practices, above all through the profitable retail sale of food and drink.²⁵ Through the sale of coffee, slaves mobilised elements of their native material culture out of economic and social considerations, thereby introducing new cultural practices.²⁶ However, the scope of their autonomy in social and labour relations cannot be studied in isolation from the dynamics of coercion that constantly shaped their lives from the galleys to their businesses in and out of the *Bagno*. In fact, Livornese authorities sought to curtail both the autonomy and profits of slaves operating shops and stalls by controlling the spatio-temporal aspects of their lives. In particular, this was done by locking them in the *Bagno* at night and heavily regulating their commercial and social contacts with free Christians.²⁷ Moreover, given the competitive nature of the coffee business in Early Modern Livorno, it is highly likely that the average slave running a coffee stall or *bottega* would be struggling to make a living, much like in Gonieri's case.²⁸ In this picture, heavily shaped by the dialectic between autonomy and coercion, the economic, social and legal precarity experienced by slaves in running their coffee businesses emerges as one of the distinguishing features of autonomous slave labour in this port city.

²² *Idem*, 08/05/1701.

²³ Lucia Frattarelli Fischer, *L'Arcano del mare* (Paini editore, 2018), 105.

²⁴ Jean Marteilhe, *Mémoires d'un galérien du Roi-Soleil*, ed. André Zysberg (Mercure de France, 2004), 341–4.

²⁵ Andrea Zappia, in his work on Christian slave communities in the Barbary *bagno*, observes the profitability of slave businesses involved in the sale and preparation of foodstuffs, cf. Zappia, "Il mestiere," 111–3.

²⁶ Salvatore Bono, *Schiavi: una storia mediterranea* (Il Mulino, 2021), 166.

²⁷ Chizzolini, "Navigating," 3; for an example of the fears tied to slaves and free Christians mingling, cf. ASLi, Capitano f. 3174, cc. 775, 827.

²⁸ On competition and class composition of coffee *bottega* owners in Livorno, cf. Francesca Bregoli, *Mediterranean Enlightenment: Livornese Jews, Tuscan Culture* (Stanford University Press, 2019), 175.

Correcting Women: Gender, Discipline and Space in Genoa's Charitable Institutions

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This paper explores the material and everyday dimensions of discipline and coercion within two charitable institutions of early modern Genoa: the *Albergo dei Poveri* and the *Conservatorio di virtù* managed by the *Ospedale di Pammatone*. Between the second half of the seventeenth and the eighteenth century, these institutions confined women and minors within a system that combined assistance, correction, and punishment. While conceived as spaces of care, they operated through a dense set of practices that regulated behaviour, restricted movement, and imposed obedience.

As Susan Amussen has shown, "violence" in the early modern age did not possess a fixed or intrinsic meaning but took on different connotations depending on the context and the individuals involved. Not all forms of physical abuse were necessarily perceived or condemned as violence, as their legitimacy depended largely on the social and familial relationships between those involved. The use of force was embedded in hierarchical structures and generally tolerated when exercised by figures of authority — such as heads of households or masters over apprentices — so long as it was understood as corrective and proportionate to the fault committed. Only those actions deemed excessive or inappropriate in relation to shared norms were identified and prosecuted as acts of violence. While this framework helps to explain domestic forms of discipline, it risks obscuring other forms of coercion, particularly in contexts where the asymmetry between individuals was so pronounced as to make any form of complaint or recourse effectively impossible. This was the case within charitable institutions, where inmates were often deprived of family support or patronage. In the absence of mediators able to negotiate their position — what Angela Groppi has defined as an "exchange game"— institutional authorities exercised extensive control over both bodies and everyday life, contributing to what Mary Gibson has described as a blurring of the boundaries between charity and punishment. To this must be added a further, intrinsic feature of charitable intervention: practices of confinement and discipline were framed as corrective and even salvific, aimed at reforming behaviour and restoring moral order. Yet, when considered through the material conditions of confinement, these same practices also reveal forms of coercion that can be understood as violence.

The *Albergo dei Poveri* of Genoa, a massive building spanning over 20,000 square metres, was founded by the *Magistrato dei Poveri* in 1656 to address the shortcomings of the city's welfare system, catering to a wide range of needs. It was intended to function simultaneously as a hospital for beggars, a house for catechumens, a conservatory of virtues, a hospice for the elderly, and a refuge for women with troubled marital histories. Each category of the poor was assigned to a specific dormitory, characterised by different degrees of isolation from the outside world and by forms of labour tailored to the gender and age of the residents.

Alongside the quarters designated for the "deserving poor", the institution also included two correctional quarters that housed, often for a fee, individuals deemed deviant and in need of moral reform. Requests for confinement could originate from private citizens — concerning adulterous women, unmarried pregnant girls, or undisciplined children — or from magistrates of the Republic. Confinement was frequently combined with forced labour in textile workshops, creating a regime structured around work, prayer, and discipline. Material elements were central to this system. Chains were commonly imposed, even during labour; internal prisons were used for more serious infractions; dormitories were locked, and windows secured with bars. These objects and spatial arrangements did not merely accompany discipline, but actively structured it, shaping both the experience of confinement and the exercise of authority. Punishment could also assume public and performative forms. Individuals sentenced by magistrates might be whipped along routes crossing the city before being transferred to the *Albergo*. In 1701, Chiara Maria Sessarego, accused of sodomy, was publicly flogged before being imprisoned for life, while the fifteen-year-old Giovanni Burone, in 1692, was forced to pass above the galleys of the fleet before his confinement. Within the institution, punishments also targeted the body as a site of correction: women could be humiliated through the ritual cutting of their hair in front of the community. At the same time, everyday life was regulated through a strict system of rules — silence during meals and work, gender segregation, controlled recreation — and constant surveillance by nuns and staff. Minor infractions could result in deprivation of food or beatings, while more serious cases were judged by the governors, who, acting as "social fathers", exercised broad disciplinary authority. Attempts to escape further reveal how confinement was experienced by the inmates. In this sense, the very material constraints of the institution — walls, height, barred windows — also defined

the forms and limits of resistance. Women in the correctional quarters tried to flee by descending from upper-floor windows using ropes or knotted bedsheets, despite the height — up to ten metres — and the risks involved. These attempts were often unsuccessful and could result in serious injuries, as in the case of Laura Caterina, who fractured her leg during her escape. The motivations behind these acts illuminate the concerns and aspirations of the women involved: one sought to recover money she feared would be taken by her husband, while another attempted to leave in order to marry a man she believed would offer her a better future. These episodes point to a persistent desire for autonomy that clashed with the institutional objective of enforcing obedience and controlling behaviour.

The *Conservatorio di virtù* of Pammatone, where abandoned girls were raised after their period of wet-nursing in foster care, offers a particularly clear perspective on the relationship between confinement, material conditions, and resistance. In February 1741, a revolt broke out following the death of a young girl named Desideria, allegedly caused by beatings inflicted by a sewing mistress. When the governors attributed the death to natural causes and refused to intervene, the girls locked themselves inside the workshop and refused to continue working. The response was immediate: the leaders were arrested and transferred to the prisons of the *Albergo dei Poveri*, and new instruments of punishment, including chains for hands and feet, were introduced to reinforce discipline. This episode makes visible how practices presented as corrective could be perceived by inmates as forms of abuse, revealing the tension between institutional intentions and lived experience. Coercion was thus intensified in reaction to disobedience, and the aim of enforcing “perfect resignation” was pursued through both physical punishment and intimidation. Control extended not only to actions but also to desires. In 1755, the governors obtained permission to close a road running alongside the conservatory in order to prevent contact between the girls and young men who gathered near the building, even though the windows were already secured with grates and the space was heavily guarded. Isolation was therefore reinforced to eliminate even the possibility of interaction.

In this perspective, the analysis suggests that early modern charitable institutions should not be understood simply as spaces of care, but as structured environments in which practices presented as corrective relied on material arrangements that were fundamental to both productive labour and the shaping of gendered discipline, while also generating forms of constraint and tension.

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Objects of Proof, Bodies in Exile: African and Afro-descendant Women before the Inquisition in the Canary Islands (16th–18th c.)

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This paper examines the intertwined dynamics of exile, confinement, and material culture in the prosecution of African and Afro-descendant women before the Inquisition in the Canary Islands between the sixteenth and eighteenth centuries. Located off the north-western coast of Africa, only a short distance from the Sahara Desert and the Moroccan coast, the Canary Islands must be understood not as a peripheral European space but as part of the African Atlantic. Their geographical position — at the intersection of African, European, and Atlantic routes — made them a crucial laboratory of early colonial experimentation. Following the Castilian conquest in the late fifteenth century, the archipelago was rapidly integrated into the expanding Atlantic world as a strategic colonial outpost between Europe, Africa, and the Americas. The development of a plantation-based economy, particularly centred on sugar production, generated a growing demand for labour, which was met through the forced displacement and enslavement of populations from North Africa and sub-Saharan Africa.¹

As a result, Canary Islands society became deeply heterogeneous from an early stage, comprising Indigenous Canary Islanders, enslaved Africans, converted Jews, Muslims, and Iberian settlers. This complex coexistence prompted the early establishment of mechanisms of religious and social control. In 1505, the Spanish Crown instituted in the archipelago the first overseas tribunal of the Inquisition, designed to regulate a profoundly mobile and multicultural society. The Holy Office thus functioned not only as a religious institution, but as a colonial instrument aimed at disciplining bodies, beliefs, and practices across a fragmented insular geography.² In this sense, inquisitorial power can be understood within broader regimes of discipline that operate through surveillance, classification, and punishment.³

Within this context, exile — understood not merely as displacement but as a structured form of punishment — functioned as a key mechanism through which the Inquisition regulated, displaced, and attempted to neutralise forms of knowledge embodied by African and Afro-descendant women. In an archipelagic setting such as the Canary Islands, exile did not simply remove individuals from a fixed centre; rather, it produced a condition of controlled mobility, transforming the geography itself into a carceral space. Bodies were displaced across islands, confined through circulation, and subjected to continuous surveillance.

For enslaved individuals, however, confinement did not begin with the prison. The condition of enslavement itself imposed a regime of restricted mobility, surveillance, and bodily control, effectively constituting a prior and continuous form of incarceration. In this sense, slavery functioned as a foundational carceral structure, within which the Inquisition operated not as an exception, but as an extension and intensification of already existing regimes of constraint.⁴

This perspective invites a reconsideration of the relationship between carceral space and insular geography. In the Canary Islands, the prison cannot be understood as a closed and isolated structure; rather, it extends outward into the very fabric of the archipelago. Exile, surveillance, and forced displacement transformed the islands into a diffuse carceral

¹ Germán Santana Pérez, "Black People in the Canary Islands," *Anais de História de Além Mar* 19 (2018): 109–136; Manuel Lobo Cabrera, *La esclavitud en las Canarias* (Cabildo Insular de Gran Canaria, 1982); Juan Manuel Santana Pérez and Germán Santana Pérez, *Puertas en el mar* (Tirant Humanidades, 2022).

² Francisco Fajardo Spínola, *Las víctimas de la Inquisición en las Islas Canarias* (Lemur, 2005); Francisco Fajardo Spínola and Luis Alberto Anaya Hernández, "Los estudios sobre la Inquisición de las Islas Canarias: Estado de la cuestión y perspectivas," in *Mentalidad e ideología en el Antiguo Régimen* (Universidad de Murcia, 1992), vol. 2, 149–161; Claudia Stella Geremia, "El legado de las mujeres africanas en las colonias atlánticas. Un análisis a través de los registros inquisitoriales del caso de Canarias," *Sociedades Precapitalistas*, 14 (2024): 85. <https://doi.org/10.24215/22505121e086>.

³ Michel Foucault, *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*, trans. Alan Sheridan (Pantheon Books, 1977).

⁴ Orlando Patterson, *Slavery and Social Death: A Comparative Study* (Harvard University Press, 1982); Achille Mbembe, "Necropolitics," *Public Culture* 15, no. 1 (2003): 11–40.

landscape, where movement was both imposed and controlled. Confinement thus operated not through immobility alone, but through regulated circulation. Within this expanded carceral geography, the body itself emerged as a crucial site of control and resistance: displaced, monitored, and inscribed with meanings imposed by judicial authority, yet still capable of movement, escape, and the transmission of knowledge across spaces.⁵

The case of María Felipa de la Cruz exemplifies this form of punitive exile as a central strategy of inquisitorial control. A Black woman born in Tenerife at the end of the seventeenth century to enslaved African parents, María Felipa lived a life marked by constant displacement across the archipelago — Tenerife, La Palma, El Hierro — and beyond. Her repeated prosecutions between 1714 and 1718 reveal how exile operated not as an exceptional measure, but as a recurring condition structuring her existence. At one point, the commissioner of Santa Cruz de Tenerife, acting on his own initiative, ordered her removal to the Americas. María Felipa was thus deported to the Indies and embarked for Havana, where she spent several days in the Hospital of San Francisco de Paula before being sent back to the Canary Islands. Once returned, she was imprisoned again in La Laguna and subsequently banished to El Hierro, where she survived by grinding and roasting gofio to sell.⁶

This sequence makes visible a punitive geography that extended far beyond the prison or even the archipelago itself: exile functioned here as a mechanism of colonial circulation, displacing her body across Atlantic spaces while attempting to strip her of stability, livelihood, and social ties.

Yet her trajectory also reveals the instability of this system. María Felipa repeatedly escaped—from prison, from hospital confinement, and from insular exile—demonstrating how the boundaries imposed by the Holy Office could be negotiated and, at times, subverted. Her movements were not solitary acts: they relied on local networks that included figures embedded within structures of authority, such as clergy and medical practitioners. These dynamics suggest that inquisitorial control was never absolute but continuously contested within everyday social relations.⁷

Her persecution must also be situated within a broader conflict over knowledge and authority. As a healer, María Felipa practiced forms of care that combined herbal remedies, animal substances, and ritual gestures, likely rooted in Afro-Atlantic traditions. Her ability to attract numerous patients placed her in direct competition with licensed male practitioners. Accusations that she cured “by bad art” reveal not only religious suspicion, but also an epistemic and economic struggle in which embodied, experiential, and gendered forms of knowledge were delegitimized in favour of institutional, male-dominated medicine aligned with colonial and ecclesiastical power.

The expanded carceral framework can be further illuminated through a case from the early seventeenth century. In Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, two enslaved youths—a thirteen-year-old Black girl and a sixteen-year-old “mulatto” boy — escaped from the secret prisons of the Holy Office by crossing rooftops at night and moving through the city toward a sugar plantation in the island’s interior. Their flight reveals how confinement extended beyond the prison walls and intersected with other spaces of discipline, including the master’s household and the plantation. In this sense, the inquisitorial prison, the master’s household, and the plantation cannot be understood as separate spaces, but as interconnected nodes within a broader carceral continuum, where different forms of discipline operated on the same racialized bodies.⁸

Alongside the trajectories of bodies, this paper places particular emphasis on materiality as a key analytical lens. Objects such as *bolsas*, amulets, coins, and inscribed papers did not merely accompany these women’s practices; they constituted active components of ritual knowledge, functioning as portable technologies of protection, healing, and agency within embodied and relational epistemologies.⁹

Bolsas, in particular, were small ritual bundles typically worn on the body or kept in close contact with it, often containing a combination of organic and inorganic materials—such as herbs, roots, animal parts, stones, written prayers, or inscribed papers. Circulating across Afro-Atlantic contexts—from West African spiritual practices to Brazil and the Iberian Atlantic—they operated as condensed sites of power, where protection, healing, and communication with the spiritual realm were materially enacted. Their efficacy relied not only on their contents, but on their proximity to the body and their activation through gesture, speech, and ritual practice. In this sense, *bolsas* can be understood not simply as objects, but as mobile nodes of ritual knowledge, carrying within them both memory and power across the Atlantic.

⁵ Ruth Wilson Gilmore, *Golden Gulag: Prisons, Surplus, Crisis, and Opposition in Globalizing California* (University of California Press, 2007).

⁶ Carolin Schitzmz, “‘Discurso de Su Vida’: A Black Woman Healer’s Biography,” *Medicine and the Making of Race, 1440–1720*, <https://www.mmor.co.uk/blog/discurso-de-su-vida-a-black-woman-healers-biography>.

⁷ Saidiya V. Hartman, *Lose Your Mother: A Journey Along the Atlantic Slave Route* (Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2007).

⁸ Gilmore, *Golden Gulag*.

⁹ Arjun Appadurai, ed., *The Social Life of Things: Commodities in Cultural Perspective* (Cambridge University Press, 1986); Giorgio Riello, *The Global Lives of Things: The Material Culture of Connections in the Early Modern World* (Routledge, 2016); Claudia Stella Geremia, “Cultura materiale e mobilità della nuova società canaria,” *Società e Storia*, 189 (2025): 571–592.

When intercepted by inquisitorial authorities, however, these objects underwent a radical transformation. Removed from their original contexts of use, they were reclassified as material evidence of deviance. The passage of these objects from the body into the archive marks a critical shift: from lived practice to criminalised artefact.

The archive must therefore be understood not as a neutral repository, but as an active agent in the production of marginalisation, where material traces are inseparable from the coercive processes that generated them and from the epistemic violence embedded within colonial systems of knowledge.¹⁰

By juxtaposing the circulation of objects with the trajectories of bodies, this paper demonstrates how the Inquisition in the Canary Islands produced a system of confinement that combined imprisonment, exile, forced mobility, and epistemic control. Yet this system was never total. The persistence of movement, ritual practice, and social networks reveals the limits of inquisitorial authority.

Ultimately, this study contributes to a broader rethinking of the Atlantic world by positioning the Canary Islands as a central space within the Black Atlantic.¹¹ It foregrounds the body as an archive and material culture as a site of both repression and agency.

¹⁰ Carlo Ginzburg, *Il formaggio e i vermi* (Einaudi, 1991); Walter D. Mignolo, *The Darker Side of Western Modernity: Global Futures, Decolonial Options* (Duke University Press, 2011).

¹¹ Paul Gilroy, *The Black Atlantic: Modernity and Double Consciousness* (Harvard University Press, 1993).

Les objets de la résistance : rescousses et évasions des prisonniers du Lyonnais (XIV^e-XVI^e siècles)

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En octobre 1418, à Saint-Symphorien-le-Château, le prisonnier Jean Perrot nous offre l'exemple d'une résistance inépuisable et protéiforme.¹ Il adopte d'abord une stratégie défensive en restant mutique pendant les interrogatoires puis offensive en brisant les prisons une première fois. Il est finalement repris et torturé. Il décide alors de contourner les règles en acceptant de témoigner tout en livrant des aveux partiels et mensongers. En contexte carcéral, la résistance des prisonniers et prisonnières s'exerce dans une grande diversité de modalités et de degrés d'opposition, depuis les défiances routinières et infimes, jusqu'aux oppositions affichées, en passant par le contournement des règles. Les évasions, les révoltes et les plaintes appartiennent à la catégorie des oppositions véritables, celles qui laissent le plus de traces dans nos sources. L'évasion constitue la principale forme de résistance carcérale, que celle-ci se déroule pendant la prise ou pendant la détention. Dans les deux cas, l'*agency* des prisonniers s'illustre par la pluralité des méthodes employées, attestant de la capacité des détenus à interagir avec le contexte et l'espace carcéral et à mobiliser les ressources sociales et matérielles dont ils disposent. Résister situe notre analyse du côté de l'action mais soulève aussi la question des moyens et des objets qui servent la rébellion des prisonniers.

Nous nous intéressons ainsi aux objets de la résistance, pris dans leur diversité fonctionnelle, usuelle et symbolique. Ces objets sont tout à la fois ceux utilisés par les prisonniers pour s'évader et briser les murs ; les objets transportés et importés dans les prisons ; les objets produits ou à l'inverse détruits. Ces objets de la résistance des prisonniers et prisonnières nous révèlent, en miroir, les conditions matérielles de l'emprisonnement. L'espace carcéral est un espace perçu, construit et vécu, au sein duquel les objets ne sont pas un simple élément de paysage mais les véritables médiateurs de cette appropriation de l'espace. Ce rapport aux territoires carcéraux est en effet déterminé par les objets mis à disposition des prisonniers ou soustraits à leur vue ; par les objets en état ou au contraire vétustes et cassés ; par les objets fabriqués et confectionnés ; et, enfin, par les objets détournés de leur usage initial. Les modalités de résistance des prisonniers dans le Lyonnais à la fin du Moyen Âge procèdent d'un rapport stratégique aux objets carcéraux, articulant contraintes matérielles spécifiques et *agency* des judiciaires. L'objet carcéral désigne toute chose matérielle saisie dans l'espace de la prise et de la prison qui en redéfinit les fonctions usuelles et symboliques. Il s'agit tout à la fois des infrastructures, des ressources existant en contexte carcéral et des biens qui circulent en prison et avec la société péri-carcérale. La résistance procède d'une appropriation stratégique de ces objets qui tend à reconfigurer les matérialités carcérales et l'espace de la prison lui-même.

L'histoire de la culture matérielle invite à interroger les méthodes de l'enquête historique, dans la mesure où les sources disponibles émanent principalement des autorités judiciaires, et très rarement des détenus eux-mêmes, hormis quelques témoignages littéraires ou graffiti. Dans le cas lyonnais, de tels récits de prisonniers ne nous sont pas parvenus. Le corpus mobilisé se compose dès lors essentiellement de sources judiciaires, appréhendées dans leur diversité — interrogatoires, registres, rapports de visites de prison, entre autres. Comment écrire l'histoire matérielle des résistances carcérales *from below* à travers des sources produites *from the top* ? Pour pallier cette difficulté, nous proposons une attention marquée aux témoignages qui retranscrivent la parole et le point de vue des prisonniers et des briseurs de prison, bien que nécessairement biaisés et tronqués. Il s'agit plus généralement d'utiliser la densité des descriptions et des récits d'évasion qui va paradoxalement de pair avec des lacunes et des silences. Nous adoptons une méthode qualitative, basée sur des études de cas, afin d'entrer dans la profondeur des sources.

Nous verrons dans un premier temps que la résistance passe par le détournement fonctionnel d'objets banals ou d'objets du quotidien. Dans un univers carcéral marqué par le dénuement matériel, les prisonniers mobilisent-ils les ressources disponibles pour résister. Lors de la prise, les prisonniers font feu de tout objet car la résistance est souvent fortuite. Ils mobilisent alors les ressources environnantes et constitutives du paysage, comme les pierres et les rochers. Mais les prisonniers recourent également aux objets qu'ils portent avec eux, une arme s'ils n'ont pas été désarmés ou encore leurs simples vêtements. Une fois enfermés, les prisonniers ne disposent pas d'armes ni d'outils spécifiques. Leur évasion résulte souvent de la mobilisation des ressources disponibles dans la cellule. En 1391, l'évasion de Jean de

¹ Archives départementales du Rhône (ADR), 10G 2933, Saint-Symphorien-le-Château, pièces 2 et 3, 1415.

Sanzi du château de Rochefort où il est détenu pour adultère se déroule en plusieurs temps.² Il brise d'abord ses fers et la fenêtre de sa cellule avec une pierre qui se trouvait là. Ensuite, il rejoint la cellule de son amante pour s'emparer de ses draps et confectionner une corde de fortune. Sa stratégie repose alors non seulement sur le détournement fonctionnel des draps mais aussi sur l'évaluation de l'espace carcéral lui-même. Le prisonnier a dû estimer la solidité de la verrière, quantifier la hauteur du mur entre la fenêtre et le sol, examiner la solidité des draps. Les récits de bris de prison nous renseignent donc, en miroir, sur les conditions de détention des prisonniers. La présence de pierres dans les cellules résulte probablement de la dégradation des prisons médiévales. En se détachant de son mortier, la pierre devient un outil lourd et contendant. Réciproquement, ces évasions semblent avoir des conséquences matérielles sur les espaces carcéraux. Les fenêtres brisées, les portes rompues et les sols décaronnés décrits interrogent sur les processus et les usages qui ont pu conduire à cet état de vétusté. Nous pouvons alors formuler l'hypothèse d'un espace qui a été abîmé par les bris de prison. De même, l'espace carcéral est organisé de telle sorte que les prisonniers n'aient pas accès aux objets de torture comme les cordes et les poids. Ainsi, si les objets du quotidien peuvent être mobilisés pour résister et s'évader, l'espace carcéral reste relativement vide, pauvre en objets. L'évasion repose alors souvent aussi sur la capacité des prisonniers et de leurs complices à introduire en prison des outils et des armes.

Le succès d'une évasion repose souvent sur la capacité à mobiliser et introduire des objets dans les prisons. On sait que sous l'Ancien Régime, l'espace carcéral est poreux, ouvert sur la société qui l'entoure. Ce continuum social se traduit notamment par les échanges variés entre la société carcérale et péri-carcérale, structurée par les réseaux d'interconnaissances et par les sociabilités entre les prisonniers et leurs visiteurs.³ En fonction du statut sociologique du prisonnier et de la prison dans laquelle il se trouve, des objets, mobiles et immobiles, peuvent être introduits en prison. Les résistances carcérales sont souvent collectives, appuyées par les amis et les parents. Leur aide est avant tout logistique : il s'agit de pénétrer dans les prisons avec des objets stratégiques et adaptés à l'évasion. L'interrogatoire d'un des briseurs de prison de George et de sa mère Françoise détaille le parcours d'un marteau et de la tenaille qui ont servi à les libérer, depuis l'atelier du ferrailleur jusqu'aux prisons.⁴ La résistance peut aussi se cacher derrière une visite banale et prendre la forme d'un don de nourriture. L'objet donné, porté jusqu'à la prison et introduit au sein de l'espace carcéral, fonctionne alors comme un cheval de Troie. En 1321, Jean Girond est gardé prisonnier à Saint-Martin-d'Ainay pour le vol d'une hache. Son entretien est assuré par son fils, Pierre Girond, ainsi que son valet, Thomas Salvas, qui lui portent des vivres en prison. Un vendredi soir, ils déguisent leur tentative d'évasion derrière une banale visite et distribution de pain et de vin.⁵ Il s'agit de dissimuler l'évasion collective derrière une assistance commune. Enfin, un détour par les sources hagiographiques nous permet de questionner l'influence des récits de miracle dans l'évasion des prisonniers. L'étude de ces récits par See Sargent et Megan Cassidy-Welch montre que l'intervention du saint est le plus souvent médiatisée par des moyens matériels.⁶ Loin de libérer instantanément le prisonnier, il s'agit de lui porter assistance en lui fournissant les moyens nécessaires à son évasion. Celles-ci restent contingentes aux conditions matérielles de la détention et reposent sur une circulation d'objets, qu'elle soit réelle ou miraculeuse.⁷ Si on ne s'évade au Moyen Âge que de très peu de manières, c'est donc aussi probablement en raison de la diffusion de modèles narratifs d'évasion qui nourrissent l'imaginaire des prisonniers.⁸ Ainsi, les objets circulent entre la ville et la geôle et ces réseaux de circulation sont investis lorsqu'il s'agit de s'évader. Toutefois, circulent aussi des paroles, des requêtes, des doléances. Dans ce contexte, la stratégie des prisonniers repose sur leur capacité à produire des documents utiles à leur cause ou, au contraire, à les détruire quand ils la desservent.

Enfin, nous étudierons les formes de la résistance documentaire, c'est-à-dire les actions reposant sur la production de documents ou, au contraire, leur destruction. Témoigner au sujet des conditions de détention, formuler des plaintes et des revendications constituent une autre manière de résister à la justice depuis les prisons. Il s'agit alors moins de changer l'ordre carcéral que d'obtenir la miséricorde du juge au procès. Ces mots se partagent d'abord entre habitants de la prison, entre les prisonniers et leurs visiteurs, avant de finalement parvenir à la cour où ils s'incarnent dans des documents. La transcription des paroles du prévenu et des témoins exerce un véritable pouvoir d'action sur les décisions de justice, bien qu'elle implique une mise à distance de la réalité et du témoignage oral. Il existe une performativité de l'écrit par rapport à l'oral dans la mesure où l'écrit fait preuve et donc a la force de dire le vrai. La matérialisation des plaintes, ainsi que le témoignage de la souffrance physique et morale liée à la détention en vue de leur inscription dans un document judiciaire, constituent un enjeu majeur pour le justiciable. Après une tentative d'évasion ratée, le prisonnier Martin Carol utilise ses conditions de détention sordides afin de susciter la clémence du

² ADR, 10G 2551, pièce 2, 19 mars 1391.

³ Philippe Combessie, *Prisons des villes et des campagnes : étude d'écologie sociale* (Les Éditions de l'Atelier, 1996), 213.

⁴ ADR, 10G 2639, pièce 14, 18 août 1520.

⁵ ADR, 11G 692, fol. 41v, 1321.

⁶ See Sargent, *Religion and Society in Late Medieval Bavaria: The Cult of Saint Leonard, 1258-1500* (University Microfilms, 1982), 292; Megan Cassidy-Welch, *Imprisonment in the Medieval Religious Imagination, c. 1150-1400* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2011), 46-47.

⁷ Romain Telliez, "Geôles, fosses, cachots," in *Enfermements. Volume I*, éd. J. Claustre et al. (Éditions de la Sorbonne, 2011), 171.

⁸ Ce lien entre tentatives « réelles » d'évasion et récits de miracle est exploré par Françoise Michaud-Fréjaville à travers l'exemple des deux tentatives d'évasions de Jeanne d'Arc après sa capture en 1430, lorsqu'elle est enfermée à Beaulieu puis à Beaufort dans Françoise Michaud-Fréjaville, "Sainte Catherine, Jeanne d'Arc et le saut de Beaufort," *Cahiers de recherches médiévales* 8 (2001) : 73-86.

juge. Ce dernier mobilise une quinzaine de témoins, décrivant tous l'enchaînement régulier et la lourdeur des fers. En outre, ils dépeignent un espace carcéral extrêmement sale, rempli de fange et d'excréments de porcs.⁹ Ces témoignages redoublent donc la voix du prisonnier qui prend ensuite une forme concrète à travers le document de justice. Cette matérialisation offre un levier d'action pour le prisonnier dans le but de modérer sa peine ou d'obtenir son élargissement. Après l'échec de son évasion, le prisonnier adopte une stratégie licite et institutionnelle, témoignant de sa maîtrise des rouages judiciaires. À l'inverse, se débarrasser des pièces d'un procès équivaut à faire disparaître la culpabilité du criminel voire le crime lui-même. Les procès, interrogatoires et témoignages sont aussi des objets matériels dont on peut s'emparer et que l'on peut détruire. Dans le cas du bris de prison collectif orchestré par les habitants de Saint-Andéol pour libérer George et Françoise Nouvelle, prisonnières dans le cadre d'un procès pour infanticide, l'évasion est protéiforme. La résistance ne se limite pas ici à briser les serrures du château : les prisonnières et leurs complices s'emparent également des interrogatoires, confessions et autres pièces du procès. Le document de justice n'est plus une simple trace du procès, mais, dans sa dimension matérielle, un registre papier ou un rouleau de parchemin, que l'on peut voler et détruire.

En définitive, cette communication explore la matérialité des résistances carcérales dans leur diversité et ambitionne d'analyser comment les prisonniers mobilisent les ressources matérielles, sociales et juridiques à leur disposition pour se libérer de l'emprisonnement ou plus largement de la justice. Les objets de la résistance sont d'abord les objets trouvés en contexte carcéral qu'il a fallu détourner de leur fonction initiale. Ce sont aussi les objets importés en prison, grâce à l'intervention de complices ou de saints protecteurs, ainsi que les documents de justice eux-mêmes, que l'on produit ou détruit.

⁹ ADR, 10G 2634, Saint-Andéol-le-Château, pièces 13 et 13bis, 10 janvier 1455.

« S'ils se taisent, les pierres mêmes crieront » : les graffitis carcéraux, une source de l'expérience de l'enfermement des prisonniers protestants pour l'historien. Le cas de l'étude historique de corpus de graffitis – château de Beauregard / Tour de Constance (Languedoc, 1690-1770)

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La révocation de l'édit de Nantes, promulguée par Louis XIV en octobre 1685, interdit le protestantisme dans le royaume de France et touche une minorité religieuse de quelques 800 000 hommes et femmes. Les abjurations, fortement contraintes par une législation toujours plus privative depuis 1660 et une violence étatique incarnée par les Dragonnades, n'empêchent ni l'exil, pourtant interdit, ni le développement de pratiques de résistances, spontanées et prophétiques, armées, ou du quotidien, qui finissent par se structurer en une église du Désert à partir de 1715. Les répressions qui en découlent, notamment menées dans le Languedoc par les Intendants des provinces, s'appuient sur une diversité de pratiques, des exécutions aux amendes collectives, qui visent toutes à invisibiliser le protestantisme, pour en effacer l'éclat dans la sphère publique. Les édits et déclarations royales ont ponctué les règnes de Louis XIV et de Louis XV, marquant plusieurs décennies de périodes de persécutions plus ou moins intenses, qui finissent par s'éteindre à la fin des années 1760, mais qui ont pour point commun le nécessaire recours à l'enfermement, quelle que soit sa forme.

Si l'identité huguenote s'est construite en partie sur la mise en récit de ces persécutions collectives, centrée sur la figure des martyrs et de la résistance silencieuse, la recherche historique a tardé à s'intéresser aux prisons de la foi.¹ Cette répression, vécue sur un temps long, a pourtant eu pour conséquence le développement d'îlots carcéraux dans les provinces où le protestantisme est bien implanté. Cette diversification des lieux d'enfermement s'appuie sur les couvents pour les jeunes enfants et particulièrement les jeunes filles, les galères pour les hommes, les déportations au-delà de l'Atlantique, le recours aux prisons empruntées pour les nombreux transferts de prisonniers, les forts militaires et sur les prisons d'État pour les jugements ou encore l'enfermement des femmes. Alors que les galériens ont fait l'objet de travaux de recherche et que l'étude des institutions hospitalières continue à interroger l'enfermement des jeunes hommes et femmes, le renouvellement de l'historiographie carcérale, en interrogeant les prisons sous l'angle de l'expérience carcérale, demande un élargissement de la recherche sur l'enfermement des protestants.² Les prisons de la foi restent à étudier dans leur matérialité, au ras du sol, dans leur diversité de formes et de modalités, interrogeant la dynamique de ces espaces d'enfermement, et plus particulièrement les prisons d'État, au cœur de la politique répressive royale. Cette communication se propose d'étudier le cas de l'enfermement des prisonniers de la religion prétendue réformée dans les prisons d'État du Languedoc, plus particulièrement le château de Beauregard (Saint Péray - Vivarais protestant) et la Tour de Constance (Aigues-Mortes). La prison d'État du château de Beauregard est ainsi mise en place par la Royauté et les États du Vivarais à partir de 1691, devant l'afflux de prisonniers pour religion, et connaît ses derniers enfermements pour religion dans les années 1760. La Tour de Constance a fait l'objet de nombreuses monographies, notamment autour de la figure de la prisonnière Marie Durand, mais nous souhaitons la réinterroger plus largement : la Tour de Constance connaît ainsi deux périodes distinctes, une première d'intenses enfermements, de 1685 à 1715, pour les hommes et les femmes arrêtés au lendemain de la révocation et des suites de la guerre des camisards, et une seconde où elle n'accueille que des femmes condamnées à l'enfermement, de 1715 à la fin des années

¹ Patrick Cabanel, *La fabrique des huguenots : une minorité entre histoire et mémoire (XVIIIe-XXIe siècle)* (Labor et Fides, 2022); Natalia Muchnik, *Les prisons de la foi. L'enfermement des minorités (XVIe-XVIIIe siècle)* (Presses Universitaires de France, 2019).

² Gaston Tournier, *Les galères de France et les galériens protestants des XVIIe et XVIIIe siècles*, 3 vols. (Presses du Languedoc, 1984); Catherine Martin, *Les Compagnies de la propagation de la foi (1632-1685)* (Droz, 2000).

1760.³ Le Languedoc, Province royale marquée par une communauté protestante importante et active, fournit ainsi un espace que l'on peut qualifier de laboratoire carcéral.

Le regard porté à présent sur l'expérience carcérale nécessite un pas de côté pour l'historien, ou plutôt un contournement par les marges, pour identifier des sources produites par les Huguenots depuis leurs cachots de l'époque moderne, afin d'étudier la dynamique de ces espaces d'enfermement. Billets secrets échangés avec des co-détenus, psaumes griffonnés sur de la vaisselle, écritures codées, graffitis, la minorité protestante accède plus largement à l'écriture par sa pratique quotidienne de la Bible et elle mobilise les écrits en période de répression et en contexte carcéral.⁴ Parmi ces sources à la marge, les graffitis de prison font l'objet de recherches actuelles qui les placent au rang des écritures carcérales qui font source, non sans interroger les méthodes de l'historien, dans une démarche collective et interdisciplinaire.⁵ Concernant les graffitis relevés dans les prisons utilisées dans la question protestante, on note quelques articles depuis le XIX^e siècle, offrant des relevés voire des descriptions, dans une sorte d'exception de l'historiographie carcérale, qui s'est longtemps détournée d'une source qui ne fait pas consensus.⁶ Toutefois, ces études n'ont pas interrogé la question de la dynamique des espaces carcéraux, dans une perspective plus matérielle de l'enfermement, proposant davantage une dimension résistante, portant la focale sur les messages, notamment religieux, qui s'en dégagent, au détriment des lieux et de l'expérience de l'emprisonnement. À présent, dans la continuité des travaux engagés par Luc Bucherie au tournant du XXI^e siècle, il s'agit de mobiliser l'ensemble de ces archives murales pour interroger l'emprisonnement des membres de la minorité protestante, dans une démarche au ras du sol, ou plutôt, au ras des murs.⁷ Parce qu'ils échappent en partie aux stratégies nécessaires dans le cadre des correspondances avec l'extérieur, parce qu'ils ne sont pas réécriture a posteriori comme peuvent l'être les récits de captivité, parce que leur présence est banale dans les lieux d'enfermement à l'époque moderne, les graffitis de prison laissés par les prisonniers huguenots directement sur les murs de leurs cellules offrent un accès à l'intérieur de la prison, à ses acteurs, à son quotidien et aux dynamiques qui s'y développent.⁸

Cette étude se propose ainsi d'étudier en quoi les graffitis carcéraux, par leur matérialité, participent de la compréhension de l'expérience carcérale de la minorité protestante dans le royaume de France sous Louis XIV et Louis XV. Elle s'appuie sur le cas de l'étude historique de deux corpus de graffitis, l'un récemment découvert dans le château de Beauregard étudié à l'été 2025, et l'autre issu d'un relevé complémentaire réalisé dans la salle haute de la Tour de Constance à l'automne 2025. Ces importants corpus, relevés dans une démarche exhaustive et interdisciplinaire, permettent de repenser l'enfermement comme une dynamique et non comme un état immobile entre l'arrestation et le temps de la peine. Ils offrent un accès à la prison comme un espace où se vivent les relations des hommes au lieu et à l'autre, qu'il s'agisse de la relation à soi-même, par l'expérience intime du corps enfermé, ou de la relation à l'autre, comme membre de sa communauté religieuse mais aussi l'autre rencontré en prison.

³ Charles Bost, *Les martyrs d'Aigues-Mortes* (Editions Ampelos, 2022 [1922]); Céline Borello, Marie Durand, *Résister. Lettres de la Tour de Constance* (Editions Ampelos, 2018).

⁴ Chrystel Bernat, "Une foi au secret ? Captivité, hommage à Dieu et clandestinité protestante (1685-1791)," *Revue de l'histoire des religions*, 228 (2011): 175–205, <https://doi.org/10.4000/rhr.7771>; Philippe Martin et al., "L'écriture du croyant," in *Les écrits du for privé en France, de la fin du Moyen-Âge à 1914*, eds. E. Arnoul et al. (Éditions du Comité des travaux historiques et scientifiques, 2014), 223–251.

⁵ Anna Clara Basilicò, *Voci prigioniere. Carcerati e graffiti nelle prigioni del Sant'Uffizio in Umbria e Sicilia*, PhD dissertation (Università di Padova, 2025), <https://www.research.unipd.it/handle/11577/3558220>; Guillaume Calafat, "Enfermement et graffiti : Des palimpsestes de prison aux archives murales (note critique)," *Annales. Histoire, Sciences Sociales* 78, no. 4 (2023): 735–59, <https://doi.org/10.1017/ahss.2024.4>; Philippe Hameau et al., "Cicatrices murales : Les graffiti de prisons," *Le Monde alpin et rhodanien* 32 (2004): 150, <https://doi.org/10.3406/mar.2004.1833>; Philippe Hameau et Fanny Lalande, "Actes des journées d'études : Graffitis carcéraux, ombres et lumières de l'enfermement des hommes," *Criminocorpus. Revue hypermédia* 28 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.4000/14mea>; Guillaume Calafat, "Enfermement" : 736 ; Fanny Lalande et al., *Comprendre et reproduire le graffiti carcéral : une expérimentation* (MSH LSE, 2024), 32 min 57, <https://cnrs.hal.science/hal-04994327v1>.

⁶ Charles Bost, "À la tour de Constance, une inscription huguenote," *Le Christianisme au XX^e siècle* (1935) ; Jean-Paul Chabrol, *Résister : petite histoire d'un graffiti célèbre, Aigues-Mortes* (Ampelos, 2023), 9 ; Jean-Claude Vimont, "Graffiti en péril ?," *Sociétés & Représentations* 25, no. 1 (2008): 193–202. <https://doi.org/10.3917/sr.025.0193>.

⁷ Luc Bucherie, "La prison de Crest (Drôme) : graffiti religieux, graffiti politiques," *Le Monde alpin et rhodanien. Revue régionale d'ethnologie* 32, no. 1 (2004): 47–61, <https://doi.org/10.3406/mar.2004.1836>; Luc Bucherie, "Les graffiti des remparts d'Aigues-Mortes," in *Actes du colloque International de Glyptographie de Pontevedra*, vol. 2 (1987): 515–37; Anne Monjaret, "À l'ombre des murs palimpsestes. Les graffiti carcéraux ou faire avec les aveux de l'histoire," *Gradhiva* 24 (2016): 164–89. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.4000/gradhiva.3288> ;

⁸ Jean-Pierre Cavallé, "Écrire de la prison et sur la prison sous l'ancien régime," in *L'écriture emprisonnée*, eds. J. Bessière et al. (L'Harmattan, 2007), 53–60.

Les chaînes des galériens : matérialité de la peine et vie quotidienne sur les galères méditerranéennes (XVI^e-XVIII^e siècles)

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La toile d'Alessandro Magnasco conservée au Musée des Beaux-Arts de Bordeaux montre, sur le quai du port de Gênes, des hommes conduits vers les embarcations qui attendent. Au centre de la composition apparaît un objet précis : la chaîne. Elle relie les corps, organise l'espace du quai et marque le moment où le condamné entre dans un dispositif collectif de contrainte. Giacomo Casanova, dans *l'Histoire de ma vie*, décrit la même expérience à Corfou : « Il m'envoya [...] à l'endroit où le chef de Scala me fit asseoir, et allonger le pied pour enclouer le fer ». Le récit souligne la dimension presque routinière du geste - le corps immédiatement traité comme élément d'un dispositif - sans en restituer la durée. C'est précisément cet écart entre représentation et expérience qui fonde la démarche adoptée ici.

La chaîne n'est pas seulement le signe visible de la peine : c'est un objet matériel complexe, doté d'un poids, d'une forme, d'un coût, d'un mode de fabrication et d'un entretien. Elle agit sur les corps, organise l'espace de la galère et structure les relations sociales. En ce sens, elle constitue un point d'entrée privilégié pour une histoire matérielle de la contrainte. Passer d'une « histoire des choses » à une « histoire à partir des choses », selon la distinction proposée par Giorgio Riello, permet de faire des objets des révélateurs de pratiques sociales. La chaîne, envisagée comme un « document matériel » au sens de Gianenrico Bernasconi, incorpore des gestes techniques, impose des contraintes physiques et rend visibles des formes d'expérience que les sources narratives ne décrivent qu'indirectement. À travers l'analyse croisée des inventaires notariés, des règlements d'arsenal, des correspondances administratives et des récits de galériens, il s'agit de restituer la chaîne comme un dispositif total - à la fois technique, disciplinaire et social - au cœur du fonctionnement des galères méditerranéennes entre le XVI^e et le XVIII^e siècle.

I. La chaîne comme objet

Les inventaires d'armement offrent une première entrée dans cette matérialité. En 1575, le notaire génois Domenico Tinello dresse l'inventaire des galères Lomellini : à bord de la *Capitana* étaient enregistrés quarante-huit *brancos de cadenas*, dont le poids total atteignait vingt-deux quintaux espagnols - environ une tonne de fer - auxquels s'ajoutaient deux cent soixante et onze entraves de cheville et quatre-vingt-quatre paires de menottes. Un second inventaire de 1582, pour les galères du prince de Melfi, confirme ces proportions. Ces chiffres révèlent l'existence d'une véritable infrastructure pénale flottante : la galère n'était pas seulement une machine de guerre, mais un espace de détention dont le fonctionnement reposait sur une logistique complexe du fer.

Les archives vénitiennes confirment la dimension économique de cette gestion : en mai 1693, les *Provveditori all'Armar* achètent six cents chaînes pour les condamnés en même temps que mille cinq cents paires de chaussures pour les chiourmes. Cette juxtaposition révèle que le corps du galérien faisait l'objet d'une gestion matérielle globale, dans laquelle la chaîne occupait une place aussi structurante que les éléments nécessaires à sa subsistance. L'approvisionnement en fer relevait d'une économie publique intégrée aux dépenses ordinaires de la flotte. La chaîne apparaît ainsi comme un objet produit en série, standardisé, comptabilisé et renouvelé, dont la présence massive à bord constitue la condition matérielle du système galérien.

II. La chaîne comme peine

Le manuscrit de 1697 conservé dans l'Archivio Durazzo Giustiniani constitue une source exceptionnelle pour comprendre la chaîne dans sa dimension technique. Il décrit un système de calibration du confinement fondé sur la mesure, l'assemblage et la surveillance des éléments métalliques. Au cœur de ce système se trouve la *branca* - un anneau fixé solidement au banc de nage qui constitue le point d'articulation entre la structure du navire et les corps des rameurs. La chaîne n'unit pas seulement les galériens entre eux : elle ancre physiquement leur corps à l'architecture même de la galère. Chaque chaîne obéit à une standardisation précise - « toutes doivent être de dix-neuf maillons » - dont le dernier est rivé à la manille fixée à la cheville. Ce rivetage doit être exécuté de manière à rendre toute tentative d'ouverture difficile, soulignant que la sécurité du dispositif repose autant sur la qualité du travail technique que sur la masse du fer.

Cette standardisation s'accompagne d'une différenciation rigoureuse : les chaînes les plus lourdes – les *calzette* – sont réservées aux forçats les plus dangereux ou les plus lourdement condamnés, tandis que des chaînes plus légères sont attribuées aux *buonavoglia* et aux esclaves. La chaîne devient ainsi une variable mesurable de la peine, modulée selon les statuts et les besoins productifs. Le manuscrit prescrit en outre des inspections régulières, « deux ou trois fois par nuit », afin de vérifier l'intégrité des maillons et des points de fixation – contrôles qui répondent aux pratiques bien connues des galériens, qui « commencent à scier le maillon ou le pivot [...] puis remplissent de cire la partie déjà entamée » pour dissimuler la faiblesse du métal.

Les sources toscanes confirment la logique différenciée de la peine : en 1720, un chef de tumulte reçoit « une chaîne de dix-huit maillons » ; en 1699, le scribe général Vitolini fait « mettre en chaîne tous les esclaves » du bague de Livourne pour faciliter la recherche d'objets volés, transformant la chaîne en instrument de discipline préventive collective ; en 1701, l'esclave Ametto de Tétouan demeure « toujours à la chaîne en raison de sa pauvreté », incapable de payer l'amende nécessaire à sa libération : la chaîne devient ici la matérialisation d'une dette non acquittée. La peine des galères ne se présente donc pas comme une condition uniforme, mais comme un système différencié, inscrit dans la matérialité même du fer.

III. La chaîne comme expérience vécue

Le témoignage de Jean Marteilhe montre que la chaîne n'est jamais un simple instrument d'immobilisation : elle doit être calibrée de manière à contraindre sans détruire la capacité productive. Une chaîne trop lourde « gêne le meilleur sujet de son lot pour la rame » - remarque qui révèle un principe fondamental : la contrainte matérielle est pensée en fonction du rendement. Élie Neau décrit une chaîne pesant plus de dix kilogrammes, fixée à la cheville gauche, dans un espace de travail extrêmement restreint où cinq hommes partagent un même banc, la proximité des corps réduite à quelques centimètres. Dans cet espace saturé, la chaîne ne se contente pas de limiter les mouvements : elle organise les gestes, impose des rythmes, conditionne la posture. Le corps du galérien est pris dans une double contrainte, mécanique et collective – il ne peut ni se mouvoir librement ni se soustraire à la cadence imposée par les autres rameurs.

Cette condition produit des effets physiques durables : douleurs aux chevilles, plaies causées par le frottement du fer, engourdissement des membres, fatigue chronique. Mais elle affecte également la perception du corps et de l'espace. Le galérien n'habite plus un espace ouvert : son horizon se réduit à la longueur de la chaîne, à la surface du banc, à la présence immédiate des autres corps enchaînés. Le fer devient ainsi une médiation permanente de l'expérience, interposé en permanence entre le corps et le monde. Le galérien ne perçoit pas seulement le fer comme poids ou douleur : il finit par l'incorporer comme une condition permanente de l'existence, une frontière invisible qui redéfinit ses possibilités d'action et ses rapports aux autres.

Dans ce contexte, la contrainte génère des formes d'adaptation. Les galériens développent des techniques précises pour affaiblir les chaînes : entailler progressivement un maillon, combler la trace avec de la cire, attendre le moment propice pour rompre le fer. En 1769, le forçat Giuseppe Venzi réussit à s'évader après avoir scié la *maniglia* ; en 1757, Francesco di Vincenzo dit « il Peloso », déferré pour travailler à l'arsenal, profita de l'oubli de réenchaînement pour s'enfuir. La révolte de Civitavecchia en 1770 montre ce que devenait cette résistance à l'échelle collective : les forçats de la *San Petronio* brisèrent leurs fers et se jetèrent à l'eau ; la réponse des autorités fut le doublement des chaînes pour tous les repris.

Ces stratégies de rupture ne constituent toutefois qu'un aspect des réponses possibles. La consommation d'opium, attestée par plusieurs sources judiciaires, doit être comprise dans cette même perspective : elle permet d'atténuer la douleur liée au port du fer, de réduire la sensation de fatigue et de suspendre temporairement l'humiliation produite par l'enchaînement permanent. L'opium agit comme un instrument de régulation du corps contraint – il ne libère pas le galérien, mais modifie son rapport à la chaîne, en altère la perception, en amortit les effets. Sa diffusion malgré les interdictions répétées révèle l'existence d'une économie clandestine structurée et d'un savoir empirique du corps par lequel les galériens cherchent à maîtriser, autant que possible, les effets du dispositif auquel ils sont soumis.

IV. La chaîne comme site de négociation

La chaîne ne constitue pas un dispositif immuable appliqué uniformément. Elle s'inscrit dans un système de régulation dynamique, au sein duquel elle peut être modulée, allégée, renforcée ou suspendue en fonction du statut juridique, du comportement, de l'utilité économique ou de circonstances conjoncturelles. Les archives médicéennes en offrent l'observation privilégiée. En février 1728, le responsable du bague de Livourne recommande la grâce en faveur de Sole de Macametto de Constantine : l'argumentation combine des considérations morales, disciplinaires et économiques - la souffrance déjà endurée, la capacité productive de l'homme jugé « utile pour la rame », et la crainte du suicide, qui révèle la perception par l'administration des effets psychologiques de la contrainte prolongée.

Ces exemples montrent que la chaîne fonctionne comme une variable ajustable dans l'économie de la peine : être déferré signifie accéder à une mobilité relative, à des formes de travail moins contraignantes, voire à des circuits économiques parallèles, sans pour autant sortir du système. Cette plasticité fait de la chaîne non seulement un instrument de contrainte, mais un véritable site de négociation entre autorités et individus. La négociation ne se joue pas seulement entre l'individu et l'institution, mais aussi entre les galériens eux-mêmes, à travers des hiérarchies

informelles, des solidarités et des échanges - rappelant, dans une perspective différente, ce que Daniel Hershenzon a montré sur la capacité des objets à changer de signification selon qui les détient et dans quelle position.

Conclusion

Suivie à travers les inventaires notariés, les règlements d'arsenal, les correspondances administratives et les récits de galériens, la chaîne apparaît comme le cœur matériel d'un dispositif dans lequel s'articulent étroitement technique, discipline et exploitation des corps. Le principe fondamental en est la calibration : la chaîne n'immobilise pas de manière absolue, elle contraint sans annuler la capacité productive du rameur. Les dix-neuf maillons standardisés, les différences de poids entre les chaînes, les possibilités de déferrage partiel, les ajustements liés au statut juridique - autant d'éléments qui témoignent d'un système finement réglé. La galère n'a pas besoin de corps brisés, mais de corps soumis et fonctionnels.

Le système galérien apparaît ainsi comme un moment intermédiaire particulièrement révélateur : loin de relever encore du modèle du supplice, mais sans appartenir non plus à celui d'une discipline désincarnée, il met en œuvre une forme de contrainte où le corps reste central tout en étant déjà mesuré, ajusté et intégré à une logique productive. En ce sens, l'analyse de la chaîne invite à déplacer - plutôt qu'à invalider - les catégories foucaaldiennes : les techniques disciplinaires ne s'exercent pas ici dans l'abstraction de la norme, mais dans la matérialité précise du fer, du rivetage, du poids des maillons. C'est dans cet écart entre norme et matière que réside la spécificité du système galérien.

Mais la chaîne ne doit pas être envisagée uniquement du point de vue de l'institution. Elle constitue également le point autour duquel s'organisent les expériences vécues des galériens - résistances, adaptations, négociations - qui révèlent les limites mêmes du pouvoir : la chaîne doit être entretenue, surveillée, réparée ; elle peut être affaiblie, contournée, négociée. En partant de cet objet, il devient possible de proposer une lecture renouvelée du système des galères méditerranéennes : celui-ci ne repose pas uniquement sur la violence ou la discipline, mais sur une combinaison étroite de savoirs techniques, de pratiques administratives et d'expériences corporelles. La chaîne en constitue l'élément nodal - un artefact à la fois simple et extrêmement sophistiqué, capable d'organiser à lui seul un espace, un temps et une forme de vie.

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“I Pace the Floor, Walking Round and Round”: Approaching the Role of Materiality in the Cloistered Experience Through Comparative Textual Analysis (12th–13th Century)¹

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“I have to ring the chapel-bell, to chant the psalter over and over [...] I’d get hold of a necklace, if I could – and what joy to wear ermine furs! I pace the floor, walking round and round”.² In these excerpts from a well-known late 11th- or 12th-century text, a nun laments her unhappy life in a monastery, from which she hopes to be delivered by a young man. Despite its literary and fictional nature, it offers a good example of the importance of multisensory perception in the cloistered experience, and of how the material environment (understood in a broad sense, not only as architecture but also, for example, as soundscape) influenced behaviors, emotions, and cognitive processes.

In my paper, I present some preliminary results of an ongoing comparative analysis of medieval narrative texts which attest to how individuals interacted with their material environment and how it affected them. As such, my research situates itself at the intersection between different study traditions and academic trends: the history of mentality, of emotions, and of experience, the spatial turn (for the importance granted to spaces), the material turn (for the active role attributed to the material environment), and the cognitive turn in historical and especially medieval studies.³

From a methodological point of view, particularly important for the purpose of this paper is the notion of environmental affordances, proposed by James Gibson in 1979; this term indicates what the environment “offers the animal, what it provides or furnishes, either for good or ill”.⁴ In other words, affordances correspond to “action possibilities resulting from animal-relative, biomechanical properties”.⁵

In a case such as the one mentioned above, this theoretical framework helps us to observe how the context of a medieval monastery determined its inhabitants’ daily gestures, both enabling certain actions (ringing the chapel-bell, walking round and round within the enclosed space) and constraining others (wearing necklaces or furs, going out of the enclosed space). The importance of multisensory perception and its effect on individual emotions appears even clearer in other passages of the *Plantus*: the sensory experience offered to (or rather enforced on) the woman is presented as unpleasant (“I am defeated by the wretched, bitter fare, tasting of a little flour and cheese”, “within these muddy walls – woe is me – there’s a stench of filth in my delicate hair”), whereas it is implied or even clearly stated that different actions and different sensory experiences would make that same person happier (“it would delight me to wear fur and ermine”).

The idea that sensory perceptions, feelings, emotional expressions, gestures, behaviours and thought processes are inextricably linked should not be surprising, considering the medieval perception of mind and body as interconnected, and the attention granted to the role of sensory perceptions in imagination, memory and thought processing.⁶ On the

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² I use here the English translation by Peter Dronke, *Medieval Latin and the rise of European love-lyric* (Clarendon Press, 1996), vol. 2, 357–359. For a recent contribution see Jesús Alturo i Perucho and Tània Alaix i Gimbert, “A new critical edition of the Vatican *Planctus monialis* and another unknown *Planctus monialis* from Obarra,” *Mittellateinisches Jahrbuch* 54 no. 2 (2019): 299–314.

³ On this last trend, which is the least well-known, see Jill Stevenson, *Performance, Cognitive Theory, and Devotional Culture: Sensual Piety in Late Medieval York* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2010); Michelle Karnes, *Imagination, Meditation, and Cognition in the Middle Ages* (University of Chicago Press, 2017); Miranda Anderson and Michael Wheeler, eds., *Distributed Cognition in Medieval and Renaissance Culture* (Oxford University Press, 2019); Victoria Blud and Juliana Dresvina, *Cognitive Sciences and Medieval Studies: An Introduction* (University of Wales Press, 2020) and the issue 232 (2022) of *Groniek*, entitled “Cognitive Turn”.

⁴ James Gibson, *The Ecological Approach to Visual Perception* (Taylor and Francis 2015), 119.

⁵ François Osiurak et al., “What is an Affordance? 40 Years Later,” *Neurosciences & Biobehavioural Reviews* 77 (2017): 403–417, 409.

⁶ Carolyne Larrington, “The Psychology of Emotion and Study of the Medieval Period,” *Early Medieval Europe* 10 (2001): 251–56; Victoria Blud, “Emotional Bodies: Cognitive Neuroscience and Mediaeval Studies,” *Literature Compass* 13 (2016): 457–66; Katie

basis of both this awareness and the research results of modern cognitive sciences, which have called attention to the embodied, embedded, enacted and extended nature of cognitive processes, I aim to investigate how individuals were affected by their environment behaviourally, emotionally and cognitively.⁷

While this research can address a variety of medieval environments, medieval monasteries appear particularly suitable for multiple reasons. First, their perception is well attested by a variety of written sources. Furthermore, the monastic experience is defined in no small measure by the specific material environment in which it takes place, both in theory and in practice (since each monastery has its peculiarities). In theoretical texts, the material environment can be represented as an active force, able to affect and even transform the individual.⁸ And indeed, living in a monastery represented an experience able to profoundly affect the individual, as is normally the case with “total” disciplinary institutions (defined by Erving Goffman as places “of residence and work where a large number of like-situated individuals, cut off from the wider society for an appreciable period of time, together lead an enclosed, formally administered round of life”).⁹

In consideration of this and of the topic and aim of the conference, among the various material elements that could be considered for comparative analysis, I focus my analysis on three architectural elements which are interrelated and particularly relevant for the notion of confinement, that is walls and their openings (doors and windows).

The importance of these elements in the medieval monastic experience can be inferred from their mention (or implied reference to) in normative texts, from the Caesarius of Arles’ Rule to the Benedictine Rule and to Rule of Clare of Assisi.¹⁰ In narrative texts, openings in the walls of the monastery are often represented as weak point in the defence against the devil. For example, Caesarius of Heisterbach’s *Dialogus miraculorum* (ca. 1240) contains the story of a nun who “when she was looking out of the dormitory window”, saw “a demon in the form of a youth, standing near a well close to the dormitory wall; who, when he caught sight of her, put one foot on the railing which surrounded the wall, and throwing out the other as if he were flying, placed it on the ledge of the window itself. Then he stretched out his hand and tried to seize her by the hair”.¹¹ Here, the fact that the window allows one to see outside of the monastery and to be seen is linked in a very direct way to the peril of being dragged out of what the author considers the protective enclosure of the monastery, and surely damned.

In another story in the same collection, a nun who wanted to escape from the monastery is said to have come “to a certain door which led to the cemetery, where she intended to climb over the wall and so go back to the world. In God’s providence it happened that she struck her head so violently against the upper lintel that she fell back with concussion of the brain and lay for a long time as one dead”.¹² Once again, an opening (the door leading to the cemetery) and the act of climbing over the wall offer the opportunity for something dangerous and reprehensible. But in this case, the material environment itself plays an active role, physically striking the nun to prevent her from leaving.

The examples could be multiplied, but even these few texts attest to the important and often active role played by the material environment in the cloistered experience, and to the awareness of it among some medieval authors. Furthermore, the analysis offers insights into how this effect was exerted, that is, through environmental affordances which determined action possibilities and sensory perceptions, and – through them – influenced behaviours, gestures, emotions and thoughts.

One final dimension warrants reflection, that is the reciprocal nature of this individual/environment interaction: if the material environment could influence the individual experience, it is also true that the individual experience and mindset influenced how the environment was perceived. The same monastery walls could be perceived as protective, ensuring peace and quiet, as attested by numerous medieval texts, or as oppressive and suffocating as attested or implied by

Barclay and Bronwyn Reddan, eds., *The Feeling Heart in Medieval and Early Modern Europe: Meaning, Embodiment, and Making* (De Gruyter, 2019) and Michelle Karnes, “Images and Imagery in Medieval Christian Devotion,” in *The Senses, Cognition and the Body in Medieval Devotional Practice*, ed. P. Boonstra et al. (Brepols, forthcoming).

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⁸ See Micol Long, *Learning as Shared Practice in Monastic Communities, 1070-1180* (Brill, 2021), 63–65.

⁹ Erving Goffman, *Asylums: Essays on the Condition of the Social Situation of Mental Patients and Other Inmates* (Anchor Books, 1961), 11. For an in-depth analysis of monasteries as total institutions, see Wojtek Jezierski, *Total St Gall: Medieval Monastery as a Disciplinary Institution*, PhD Dissertation (Stockholm University, 2010).

¹⁰ For an overview on the concept of enclosure see Jean Leclercq, “Clausura”, in *Dizionario degli Istituti di Perfezione*, ed. Guerrino Pelliccia and Giancarlo Rocca (Edizioni Paoline, 1975), vol. 2, 1166–83; Jane Tibbets Schulenburg, “Strict Active Enclosure and Its Effect on the Female Monastic Experience (ca. 500-1100)”, in *Medieval Religious Women*, eds. J. A. Nichols, L. T. Shank (Cistercian Studies Series, 1984), 51–86 and, for a recent contribution see Silvia Carraro, “Behind the Cloister Wall. The Power of Female Enclosure in the Middle Age,” in *Within Walls: Experience of Enclosure in Christian Female Spiritualities (From Late Antiquity to Early Modern Period)*, eds. J. Lewandowska and A. Rosillo-Luque (Brepols 2025), 77–95.

¹¹ For the Latin text see Caesarius Heisterbacensis, *Dialogus Miraculorum*, eds. N. Nösges, H. Schneider (Brepols, 2009), 542; for the English version see Caesarius of Heisterbach, *The Dialogue on Miracles*, transl. H. von Essen Scott and C. C. Swinton Bland (Harcourt, Brace and Company, 1929), vol. 1, 140.

¹² Caesarius Heisterbacensis, *Dialogus Miraculorum*, 808–810; Caesarius of Heisterbach, *Dialogue On Miracles*, vol. 1, 253–254.

others. Similarly, openings in those walls might be seen as weak points in the defence, which leave people exposed to danger, or offer hope of escape, at least in imagination. The material environment and its affordances are the same, but the individual perception and experience of it can be very different.

Le juge et le prisonnier. Distances, proximités et promiscuités des espaces judiciaires et carcéraux (France, XVIIIe siècle)

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En 1776, les officiers de la sénéchaussée royale et ducale de Montélimar adressent des « remontrances » au duc de Valentinois et prince de Monaco pour demander la construction d'un nouveau palais de justice et de nouvelles prisons. En effet, ils déplorent l'inadaptation fonctionnelle des actuels espaces d'enfermement et y dépeignent leur expérience d'une proximité perturbatrice : « la cuisine du geôlier est le seul endroit où il [le juge] puisse s'asseoir pour parler au nom de la Loy : son esprit est tendu par l'infection qu'il respire et par le peril auquel il est exposé n'y ayant aucune barriere qui empeche le prisonnier de s'elancer sur lui, le secret de l'instruction arrive jusqu'aux complices s'il y en a. Enfin la majesté de la Justice est compromise, la Loy y est trahie, ses Ministres y sont en danger, l'homme y gemit sous mil instruments de douleur ». Ce mémoire corporatif condense des éléments matériels et idéels d'une distance problématique, placée sous la double menace des prisonniers et des miasmes : manque de la chambre criminelle contraignant le juge à travailler dans un environnement matériel impropre à instruire de sang-froid ; promiscuité du lieu contraire à la décence nécessaire à un édifice public dans lequel s'exerce le pouvoir judiciaire. Outre les thématiques usuelles de l'inconfort, de l'insécurité et de l'insalubrité perçues à l'aune des conceptions aëristes et humanitaristes, le mémoire met en exergue la question fondamentale de la distance. La notion, polysémique, intègre ici à la fois la distance spatiale et physique (relations entre palais de justice et prisons, fréquemment imbriqués ; proximité risquée avec les prisonniers), la distance sociale et la distance symbolique (configurée par le modèle du parfait magistrat catholique), la distance procédurale (vis-à-vis de l'ordonnance criminelle de 1670).

Notre communication étudie la matérialité des dimensions relationnelles entre prisons ordinaires et édifices judiciaires dans des villes françaises petites et moyennes, en plaçant l'espace et le fonctionnement de l'État royal au cœur des analyses en congruence avec la double perspective pratiquée par la récente historiographie des prisons¹. Les analyses attentives aux formes matérielles de l'urbanisme et des bâtiments, à leurs usages professionnels et sociaux, à leurs représentations culturelles se fondent sur un corpus d'une douzaine de cas d'édifices abritant des présidiaux, sénéchaussées ou bailliages et, fréquemment, des prisons royales au sein de quatre provinces : Aquitaine (Condom, Nérac, Périgueux, Sarlat), Auvergne (Aurillac, Clermont, Riom), Dauphiné (Embrun, Gap, Montélimar, Valence), Limousin (Limoges, Tulle)².

La communication présente les principales contraintes matérielles des relations entre espaces judiciaires et espaces d'enfermement, leurs enjeux et le rôle actif des compagnies officières pour élaborer des solutions pratiques. La pratique de la consultation des compagnies judiciaires par les ingénieurs du roi et experts est notable lors des visites collégiales afin d'identifier inadaptations et dégradations matérielles. Elle intervient lors de la rédaction d'états d'édifices, de devis estimatifs des travaux ou encore pour la constitution d'apanages ou d'échanges. Dans ce cadre normé du transfert de biens immobiliers du domaine royal, les visites sont alors, sinon guidées, du moins orientées. Lors de l'inspection pièce par pièce des bâtiments, les officiers de judicature présents font, si nécessaire, remarquer aux experts et au représentant du prince apanagé les dégradations ou insuffisances du bâti à prendre en compte. Cette activité, aux traces archivistiques souvent discrètes, des magistrats à la tête des compagnies ou du parquet participe pleinement de leur rôle dans l'administration de la justice royale : elle vise à adapter au mieux les espaces à leurs fonctions respectives, souvent dissociés de celles-ci.

¹ Sophie Abdela, "Prisons on the Edge: Perspectives on the Late Medieval and Early Modern History of Confinement in the Francosphere," *The English Historical Review* 139, no. 598-599 (2024): 868-87, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ehr/ceae116>; Sophie Abdela, *La prison parisienne au XVIII^e siècle. Formes et réformes* (Champ Vallon, 2019); Renaud Morieux, *The Society of Prisoners. Anglo-French Wars and Incarceration in the Eighteenth Century* (Oxford University Press, 2019).

² Vincent Meyzie, "La matérialisation contrariée du pouvoir monarchique dans la cité: le cas des édifices de la justice royale de rang second au XVIII^e siècle," in *Les justices locales et les justiciables. La proximité judiciaire en France du Moyen Âge à l'époque moderne*, ed. Marie Houlemare and Diane Roussel (Presses universitaires de Rennes, 2015), 141-54, <https://books.openedition.org/pur/93954>; Vincent Meyzie, "Mobilisations corporatives et aménagements urbains dans la France du XVIII^e siècle: les compagnies judiciaires de second rang d'Aquitaine et d'Auvergne et leurs édifices," in *La ville est à nous ! Aménagement urbain et mobilisations sociales depuis le Moyen Âge*, eds. Isabelle Backouche, et al. (Éditions de la Sorbonne, 2018), 119-36.

Contrôler les circulations des prisonniers entre espaces judiciaires et espaces d'enfermement représente une contrainte majeure. Le cas de Clermont montre les limites de la sécurisation des prisons par une politique de réparations entravée par les contraintes de la « disposition », terme émique se référant à la fois à la configuration architecturale interne des lieux et à leur insertion dans le bâti ancien. De façon usuelle, plusieurs murs mitoyens favorisent la porosité entre l'intérieur et l'extérieur. Difficiles à contrôler même en les surhaussant, ils permettent d'introduire au sein des prisons divers objets (limes, ciseaux...). Le cas de Riom est représentatif d'une petite cité judiciaire : l'ancien château ducal regroupe six institutions, distribuées dans quatre corps de bâtiments et deux cours. L'ensemble se caractérise par la pluralité de localisation des espaces carcéraux, complexifiant leur sécurisation et leur surveillance. La question des circulations tient une place notable dans les projets de construction ou de reconstruction des édifices. Le projet architectural concernant le présidial et l'élection de Condom en 1776 - une reconstruction de l'ancien palais associée à un agrandissement par achat de maisons - se caractérise à la fois par la nette séparation entre espaces judiciaires et espaces carcéraux et par la fine prise en compte des circulations des prisonniers entre les deux parties. Le plan du projet, très fonctionnel, livre plusieurs apports : l'affectation du rez-de-chaussée aux espaces d'enfermement, de surveillance et du pénal ; la création au premier étage d'une chambre de l'instruction pour les affaires criminelles, inexistante dans l'ancien palais selon une situation courante ; l'espace réservé à la circulation des prisonniers de leurs cellules vers les espaces du pénal ou les tribunaux du présidial et de l'élection. Empêcher l'introduction et la circulation d'objets aidant aux évasions constitue une autre contrainte essentielle et un paramètre notable des travaux à réaliser. À Riom, déplacer l'emplacement d'une fenêtre des prisons des femmes est estimé nécessaire car l'ouverture sur la cour intérieure permet aux femmes occupées à des activités artisanales textiles de procurer des cordages aux prisonniers.

La seconde grande thématique de la communication porte sur plusieurs cas de projets inaboutis de constructions ou de reconstructions d'édifices, révélateurs des conceptions administratives et corporatives de la bonne distance entre les deux types d'espaces. La conception fonctionnaliste et utilitariste de l'édifice public, consubstantielle à la *forma mentis* technique des ingénieurs, est aussi fréquente chez les administrateurs de la monarchie. Elle donne la priorité à l'adaptation du bâtiment - en termes de localisation, définition d'ensemble, distribution interne et dimension des pièces - aux besoins du service monarchique. Cette conception est patente dans les projets, réalisés ou non, de construction d'édifices judiciaires avec prisons intégrées à la fin du XVIII^e siècle. Les propositions du pouvoir royal suscitent souvent des conflits car elles heurtent la conception patrimoniale de l'édifice portée par les compagnies. En effet, elles le conçoivent - pour reprendre l'expression révélatrice des juges de Tulle - comme l'« ouvrage successif d'eux et de leurs pères ». Autrement dit, les magistrats défendent un attachement patrimonial au palais de justice, inséré de longue date dans un quartier central de la ville, chargé d'histoire et de mémoire, précieux héritage des luttes et soins de leurs ancêtres. L'analyse de plusieurs projets de (re)constructions d'édifices permet d'appréhender en pratique les conceptions distinctes des officiers et des administrateurs, c'est-à-dire l'articulation variable entre « projet » corporatif et « projet » administratif. La notion de « projet » - empruntée au géographe Roger Brunet - est intrinsèquement liée à la notion de distance : c'est le projet porté par les différents acteurs et impliquant une transaction entre eux qui dévoile les significations données à la distance, lui donne sens et révèle le souci à son égard³. En l'occurrence, il porte surtout sur le degré de proximité souhaitable des prisons et les critères de la bonne distance en termes de sécurité, commodité et décence.

Le cas de Gap concerne un projet inabouti, soutenu par le pouvoir municipal, d'agrandissement des prisons et du tribunal du bailliage qui doit permettre une spécialisation des espaces d'enfermement et une meilleure répartition des prisonniers. Le problème central réside ici, non pas tant dans l'état matériel de l'édifice estimé satisfaisant, que dans le manque de place à la fois dans les prisons et l'auditoire. Les documents et plans dressés par l'ingénieur en chef des ponts et chaussées en 1788 attestent du souci de préserver la séparation existante entre espace carcéral au rez-de-chaussée et espace judiciaire au premier étage tout en augmentant la surface disponible grâce à l'achat d'une maison contiguë. Ils mentionnent différents types d'espaces carcéraux et la nette séparation entre hommes et femmes (deux prisons civiles selon le genre, trois cachots...) au rez-de-chaussée, et de nouvelles pièces à construire au premier étage (« dépôt d'archives », greffe...). Le cas d'Aurillac constitue un projet, ici aussi inabouti, de désimbrication entre espace carcéral et espace juridictionnel. La comparaison du plan de l'auditoire et des prisons selon leur état avec celui dessiné pour le projet montre en détail la dissociation recherchée. L'imbrication en 1777 apparaît patente entre espaces d'enfermement, de circulation et de conservation des archives des institutions. Le rez-de-chaussée comprend vestibule d'entrée, diverses prisons, greffes du présidial et de l'élection. Le premier étage abrite les salles des deux juridictions sans être uniquement juridictionnel. Le plan prévisionnel indique deux modifications notables : transfert des prisons du premier étage au rez-de-chaussée ; déplacement des deux greffes au premier étage. La mise à distance protectrice de leurs archives justifie ce changement de localisation. L'exemple de Tulle correspond au cas de figure de l'opposition d'une compagnie seconde, adepte d'une conception patrimoniale du palais de justice, envers un projet monarchique de construction en dehors du centre de la cité d'un bâtiment administratif unique pour l'État de justice, l'État de finance et l'État carcéral. En effet, la proposition, portée par l'intendant Turgot en 1765-1768, de « translation » du présidial dans la maison d'un particulier révèle la divergence patente entre les conceptions étatique et robine. Adossé au savoir technique des ingénieurs, le commissaire du roi défend la rationalité de son projet, permettant de « rapprocher les

³ Roger Brunet, "Les sens de la distance," *Atala* (2009): 13-32.

prisons du palais », et sa fonctionnalité, avec « un seul bâtiment à entretenir ». La compagnie conteste avec vigueur le projet d'un édifice unique - regroupant présidial, élection et prisons - et en situation périphérique. Le corps présidial rejette le choix de la maison en arguant notamment du danger inhérent à la présence de prisonniers et de juges au sein d'un même lieu inadapté. La compagnie s'oppose à une délocalisation perçue comme un déclassé pratique et symbolique du palais de justice hors du centre urbain. En revanche, elle n'est pas opposée *ipso facto* à l'aménagement fonctionnel d'un édifice public : elle est favorable au déplacement avantageux des prisons.

Nobility, Commoners, Bandits. The Identities of Prisoners through Graffiti

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In the last decades, graffiti has become a frequent subject of research, at the centre of international and multidisciplinary studies. It can no longer be dismissed as a mere youthful or protest gesture, as was often the case in the second half of the 20th century, and even less as a purely vandalistic act, but rather as a genuine expression of human ingenuity and as a product of that need to communicate which is characteristic of humankind. Within a chronology stretching from prehistory to the present day¹, there is obviously a wide variety of graffiti, ranging from devotional graffiti - the most common - to chronicle graffiti, which record personal or public events, whether of everyday life or of exceptional significance (such as the death of a king or the outcome of a battle)². Many graffiti authors were simply eager to leave a mark of their passing, a «Hic fuit» on a church fresco, on the wall of a place of worship - whether public or private - or directly on the bare rock of a cave³. What unites the various types of graffiti is the realisation that they can serve as historical sources in their own right, capable of shedding light, through their analysis, on aspects of the past that would otherwise remain hidden in traditional sources⁴.

Among the many types of graffiti, prison graffiti obviously has distinct and, in some respects, unique characteristics. Prisoners would scrawl them in environments that were often crowded, dark, dirty and stifling, on small sections of wall, using makeshift tools. They were driven, as some scholars have suggested, by a desire to show they were still alive despite the hardships, to express their emotions, to challenge the judges' verdicts or, quite simply, to combat boredom and keep their minds occupied during the long hours of imprisonment. Prison graffiti, still preserved today in hundreds of locations both within and outside Europe, can therefore provide historians with a wealth of information, if not regarding the prisoners' identities, then at least concerning their origins, their cultural background and their writing skills (sometimes even in verse), the forms of popular devotion to which they were attached, the causes and conditions of their detention, and, as mentioned, their emotions. The graffiti are also fundamental sources for reconstructing the history of the places where they are preserved, unique markers, in many cases, that allow us to understand how certain spaces - within civil buildings or castles, private mansions or public buildings - were used, for a certain period and under specific conditions, as prisons as well⁵.

The identity of prisoners in early modern prisons is often difficult to ascertain. Especially in cases where paper documentation relating to individual cases has not been preserved in archives, or has never been produced, tracing an identikit of prisoners is a difficult challenge. The graffiti left by those same prisoners on the walls of their cells may be the only useful clue to finding out more about their authors. These marks have left a material trace, albeit often

¹ Troy Lovata and Elizabeth Olton, eds., *Understanding Graffiti. Multidisciplinary Studies from Prehistory to the Present* (Routledge, 2015); Chloé Ragazzoli, et al., eds., *Scribbling through History. Graffiti, Places and People from Antiquity to Modernity* (Bloomsbury, 2018); Laure Pressac, ed., *Sur les murs. Histoire(s) des graffitis* (Éditions du Patrimoine, 2018); "Historias sobre muros: grafitos, graffitis, espacios de reclusión y espacio público," *Artigrama* 38 (2023).

² Luisa Miglio and Carlo Tedeschi, "Per lo studio dei graffiti medievali. Caratteri, categorie, esempi," in *Storie di cultura scritta. Studi per Francesco Magistrale*, ed. Paolo Fioretti (CISAM, 2012), 605-28; Giuseppe Mrozek Eliszczynski, "Una fonte sottovalutata. Note introduttive sui graffiti di età medievale e moderna," in *Tracciare il passato. I graffiti come fonte per la storia medievale e moderna*, ed. Giuseppe Mrozek Eliszczynski (Edizioni di Storia e Letteratura, 2025), XI-XX.

³ Carlo Tedeschi, "Hic fuit. Scratching names on Sacred Walls", in *Writing Names in Sacred Spaces. Inscriptions in the West, from Late Antiquity to the Early Middle Ages*, eds. Estelle Ingrand-Varenne, et al. (Brepols, 2023), 167-85.

⁴ Mrozek Eliszczynski, *Tracciare il passato*.

⁵ From the now extensive bibliography on the subject, see at least: Joël Candau and Philippe Hameau, eds., "Cicatrices murales. Les graffiti de prison," *Le Monde alpin et rhodanien. Revue régionale d'ethnologie* 1-2 (2004); Giovanna Fiume, "Soundless Screams: Graffiti and Drawings in the Prisons of the Holy Office in Palermo," *Journal of Early Modern History* 21 (2017): 188-215; Antonio Castillo Gómez, "Secret Voices. Prison Graffiti in the Spanish Empire (16th-18th centuries)," *Quaderni storici* 1 (2018): 137-63; Johann Petitjean, "Inscribing, Writing and Drawing in the Prisons of the Inquisition. Methodological Issues and Research Perspectives on Graffiti," *Quaderni storici* 1 (2018): 15-37; Raffaella Sarti, ed., "Stones, Castles and Palaces to Be Read. Graffiti and Wall Writings in Medieval and Early Modern Europe," *Journal of Early Modern Studies* IX (2020); Veronique Plesch, "Graffiti: Captivity and Freedom," *The Maine Arts Journal* (2021).

ephemeral and easily perishable, of the passage of people whose existence would otherwise have been completely lost⁶.

This speech will focus on Abruzzo, a region that is generally overlooked in studies. The two northernmost provinces of the Kingdom of Naples (*Abruzzo Ultra* and *Abruzzo Citra*) formed the border with the Papal States for centuries and, thanks to their mountains and forests, long provided refuge for bandits and various types of criminals. But beyond this, in Abruzzo there were cities, such as L'Aquila or Chieti, and the strong power of the feudal nobility, with certain families dominating the scene: the Acquaviva, Dukes of Atri; the d'Avalos, Marquises of Vasto and Pescara; the Caracciolo, Princes of San Buono. Other families, usually linked to different parts of the Italian peninsula, also possessed substantial fiefdoms in Abruzzo: among them were the Farnese, the family of Pope Paul III, that, largely thanks to the wife of the Duke Ottavio Farnese - Margaret of Habsburg - administered a vast territory for centuries, the so-called Farnese States of Abruzzo.

In these northern provinces of the Kingdom of Naples, many were imprisoned in secular or ecclesiastical prisons, housed within palaces or castles, on the orders of judges appointed by the king, the local bishop or feudal lord. In the absence of archival documentation, graffiti is almost the only source for investigating the identity of prisoners, their social background, their level of education and, of course, the reasons why they ended up in prison.

The presentation will focus on three cases, all selected from the more than 150 sites in Italy that preserve prison graffiti and which have been surveyed by the scholars participating in the research project *The Dream of Freedom: Writing in Confinement in Early Modern Italy (15th–19th centuries)*, based at the University of Chieti-Pescara under the guidance of Carlo Tedeschi⁷. The first case concerns the prisons of the castle of L'Aquila, known as the *Calabozo*, which contain a wealth of graffiti left mainly by patricians from L'Aquila, arrested at the behest of the Spanish authorities. The castle, damaged by the 2009 earthquake, has only recently reopened its doors to visitors and preserves a heritage that constitutes a collection of invaluable sources for reconstructing the history of the city and its aristocratic and commercial elites⁸. The second case under consideration concerns the rooms used as a prison in the Palazzo Farnese in San Valentino in Abruzzo Citeriore, where prisoners of humble origins were held, on the orders of those who administered justice on behalf of distant feudal lords. This is one of the centres that formed part of the aforementioned Farnese States of Abruzzo. Finally, the third case will focus on the cells of the fortress of Civitella del Tronto, where the royal authorities typically imprisoned bandits and all those who attempted to cross the border with the Papal States illegally.

By highlighting the similarities and differences between these three cases, this paper will seek to demonstrate that the graffiti we can still admire today was created by a wide variety of people. Not only members of the lowest strata of society, the so-called subaltern classes⁹, but also members of traditionally privileged groups, such as the nobility. The very fact of being able to write and leave a trace of one's presence on the wall of a prison marks the difference between the creators of these graffiti and the vast majority of a population which, throughout the modern era, lived in conditions of total illiteracy. The three cases under consideration will thus demonstrate, once again, just how graffiti are historical sources extraordinarily rich in fascination and information for historians who are willing and able to interpret them.

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⁶ Mrozek Eliszczynski, *Tracciare il passato*.

⁷ Marco Albertoni, "Screnim: un progetto di censimento dei graffiti carcerari d'eta moderna quali fonti storiche da conservare e valorizzare," *Digitalia*, 2 (2024): 181–90.

⁸ Mauro Congeduti, "Il castello come luogo di detenzione: il 'calabozo'", in *Fortezze d'Europa. Forme, professioni e mestieri dell'architettura difensiva in Europa e nel Mediterraneo spagnolo*, ed. Angela Marino (Gangemi, 2003), 281–89.

⁹ Anna Clara Basilicò, "'Becoming' Subalterns: Writing and Scribbling in Early Modern Prisons," *Journal of Early Modern Studies* 13 (2024): 81–102; Pablo Ozcáriz Gil, "Los grafitos históricos como voz de los desfavorecidos," *Huarte de San Juan. Geografía e Historia* XXXI (2024): 7–17.

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Objects of Exile: The Materiality of Theodulf of Orléans's Confinement (c. 818–821)

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Introduction

This paper argues that exile in the Carolingian world must be understood not merely as a juridical sanction or a spatial displacement, but as a material process: a progressive disconnection from the networks of objects through which power was constituted, negotiated, and made visible. Objects are not passive markers of status but active instruments of accreditation and discredit. To be integrated into circuits of exchange—of gifts, liturgical furnishings, tribute, and written artefacts—was to occupy a recognised position within the political and social order; to be excluded from them was to lose that position in concrete and measurable ways.

This approach builds on scholarship on gift exchange and material culture in late antiquity and the early Middle Ages, inspired by Marcel Mauss¹. Such studies have demonstrated that the circulation of objects—*munera*, *exenia*, ecclesiastical goods—constituted a fundamental language of social relations. Yet this historiography has rarely addressed the inverse process: what happens when an individual is forcibly removed from these circuits. The exile of Theodulf of Orléans offers a revealing case study of this dynamic.

Theodulf: Career and Fall

Theodulf is attested in Francia from the late 780s in the entourage of Charlemagne. His Hispanic origins—most likely Zaragoza—have been confirmed by the linguistic features of his works, including the “Spanish symptoms” identified by Ann Freeman in the *Libri Carolini*². Appointed bishop of Orléans around 798, he also held the abbacies of Fleury and Saint-Aignan. His ties to Charlemagne were exceptionally close: he accompanied the sovereign to Rome in 800, participated in the assemblies that led to Leo III's reinstatement, and was present at Charlemagne's testament in 811—listed after the archbishops but before the ordinary bishops³. As a poet, theologian, and *missus dominicus* for judicial inspections in southern Francia—documented in his *Contra iudices*⁴—Theodulf occupied a nodal position in Carolingian intellectual and political life.

The revolt of Bernard of Italy in 817 led to his deposition and exile. The Royal Frankish Annals name him alongside Anselm of Milan and Wilfred of Cremona among those implicated, without explaining how a bishop of Orléans could have meaningfully collaborated from such a geographical distance⁵. Peter Godman proposed that the association may have served as a convenient justification for a removal that had become politically necessary⁶. Tigolet has shown how the rise of Count Matfrid and Louis's Aquitanian entourage contributed to dismantling Theodulf's network⁷. Theodulf died in exile, most likely in 821 at Le Mans.

The Pallium as Material and Juridical Token

Among the material attributes defining Theodulf's episcopal identity, the pallium occupies a singular place. Received from the pope's own hands during the visit to Rome in 800, it was not a sign of metropolitan jurisdiction—Orléans remained within the province of Sens—but a personal distinction, a visible token of his proximity to Charlemagne⁸.

¹ On gift exchange and object networks in early medieval politics, see Arnoud-Jan Bijsterveld, *Do ut des: Gift Giving, Memoria, and Conflict Management in the Medieval Low Countries* (Verloren, 2007); and the essays in: Wendy Davies and Paul Fouracre, eds., *The Languages of Gift in the Early Middle Ages* (Cambridge University Press, 2010).

² Ann Freeman, “Further Studies in the Libri Carolini,” *Speculum* 40 (1965): 203–89, at 276–78.

³ Einhard, *Vita Karoli*, chap. 33, in *Vie de Charlemagne*, eds. Michel Sot and Christiane Veyrard-Cosme (Les Belles Lettres, 2014), 84–87.

⁴ MGH, *Poetae Latini Aevi Carolini I*, ed. Ernst Dümmler (Weidmann, 1881), 493–517.

⁵ MGH, *Annales regni Francorum, a. 817–818*, ed. Friedrich Kurze, MGH SS rer. Germ. VI (Hahn, 1895), 147–48.

⁶ Peter Godman, *Poets and Emperors: Frankish Politics and Carolingian Poetry* (Oxford University Press, 1987).

⁷ Claire Tigolet, *Théodulf d'Orléans (vers 760-821). Histoire et mémoire d'un évêque carolingien* (Brepols 2023), 197–213; Mayke de Jong, *The Penitential State: Authority and Atonement in the Age of Louis the Pious, 814–840* (Cambridge University Press, 2009), 21.

⁸ Steven A. Schoenig, *Bonds of Wool: The Pallium and Papal Power in the Middle Ages* (Catholic University of America Press, 2016); Tigolet, *Théodulf d'Orléans*, 97–99.

Under Charlemagne, only two other non-metropolitan prelates had received it: Angilram of Metz and Hildebald of Cologne, both as archchaplains.

That Theodulf was acutely conscious of the pallium as a visible, representable object is confirmed by the apsidal mosaic of his private oratory at Germigny-des-Prés (c. 806), centred on the Ark of the Covenant and reflecting his engagement with the *Opus Caroli regis contra synodum*⁹. The pallium was also, as Gregory of Tours illustrates, an object susceptible to mobilisation in circuits of exchange and obligation: it could be pledged as a *pignus* in negotiations between competing parties¹⁰.

In exile, the pallium became a juridical argument. In the poem addressed to Modoin, Theodulf invokes the moment of its reception explicitly: *Solius illud opus Romani praesulis exstat, / Cuius ego accepi pallia sancta manu*¹¹. As Tignolet observes, Theodulf uses this bond to establish the pope as his natural judge, bypassing the provincial ecclesiastical hierarchy¹². According to Charles Cuissard, this constitutes the earliest recorded episcopal appeal of this kind in the Carolingian world¹³. A material object—the woollen band worn across the shoulders—functioned as a juridical token capable of restructuring power relations even in conditions of confinement.

A Comparative Case: Fortunato II of Grado

A structurally illuminating contrast is offered by Fortunato II, patriarch of Grado († 825), whose career unfolds almost exactly in parallel with Theodulf's exile¹⁴. His so-called *testamentum* lists an extraordinary range of objects across the churches and monasteries of the Grado region: altar furnishings, reliquaries, *cortinas historiales*, gold and silver vessels, liturgical vestments, crowns, copper cauldrons, hemp, hides, iron chests, bearskin coverings, wine, grain, and horses—claiming them as donations to the churches of Grado rather than personal property, which suggests actual ownership was contested. Unlike Theodulf, Fortunato pursued an active strategy of material reorientation, redistributing his accumulated authority to secure his memory and his see.

What connects the two cases is the central role of episcopal objects—liturgical furnishings, vestments, vessels—as both the substance of conflict and the medium of its resolution. For Theodulf, the pallium remained the one portable object of episcopal dignity available in exile: deployed as a juridical argument precisely because all other material and institutional resources had been stripped away.

Conclusion

The argument of this paper can be stated as a single thesis: objects function as instruments of accreditation and discredit. Theodulf's exile was not merely a spatial displacement or a juridical sentence but a progressive disentanglement from the circuits of object exchange through which Carolingian authority was constituted and maintained.

This material dimension of exclusion is already visible in Theodulf's *Contra iudices*, which is above all a catalogue of improper object transactions: gifts accepted from litigants, bribes disguised as hospitality, tributes extorted from the poor. The corruption denounced there and the exclusion enacted by his own exile are mirror images of the same phenomenon—in both cases, what is at stake is the integrity of the networks of people and objects through which authority is produced. Spatially, his exile enacted a contraction of agency: the forced localisation of a transregional actor who had built his authority through movement, court presence, and participation in networks of exchange and counsel. The pallium—sacred garment, representational object, and potentially pledgeable thing—was the one material token of his former accreditation that remained available in confinement. In early Carolingian conflict, objects do not merely accompany power: they constitute it, and their redistribution enacts its restructuring.

⁹ Ann Freeman and Paul Meyvaert, "The Meaning of Theodulf's Apse Mosaic at Germigny-des-Prés," *Gesta* 40 (2001): 125–39.

¹⁰ Gregory of Tours, *Libri Historiarum X*, ed. Bruno Krusch and Wilhelm Levison, MGH SS rer. Merov. I.1 (Hahn, 1951).

¹¹ Theodulf, *Poème LXXII Ad Modoinum episcopum*, vv. 65–66, MGH *Poetae* I, 565.

¹² Tignolet, *Théodulf d'Orléans*, 114.

¹³ Charles Cuissard, *Théodulfe, évêque d'Orléans, sa vie et ses œuvres* (Herluison, 1892).

¹⁴ Yuri A. Marano, *Le fortune di un patriarca: Grado altomedievale e il "testamento" di Fortunato II* (Viella, 2022).

Rowers, Statuses and Things in the Galleys of Spain (16th century) [La chiourme, les statuts et les choses dans les galères d'Espagne (XVI^e siècle)]

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In the sixteenth-century Hispanic Monarchy, the galley was a primary space of confinement. From the late fifteenth century onwards, these oar-driven vessels became the destination for thousands of men condemned to serve as rowers. There, they laboured alongside a heterogeneous workforce composed of free and coerced individuals—wage earners, slaves, and prisoners of war. Taken together, they formed the rowing crew, known as the *chusma* (chiourme in French), which was categorised within the Spanish fleet as *esclavos* (enslaved rowers), *forzados* (convicted rowers), and *buenaboyas* (salaried rowers). Despite differences in legal status, these men shared the same living spaces, were subjected to similar coercive practices, and interacted with the same objects and material environment. This study focuses on these objects. By approaching the sixteenth-century galley through its material dimension, it seeks to understand how physical things contributed to transforming the galley into a space of confinement, how domination was enacted through material practices, and how such objects shaped the lived experience of the rowers.

Yet this line of enquiry faces a significant limitation: the nature of the sources. The rowers themselves left no known written testimony. As a result, their material world must be reconstructed through records produced by the very institutions that confined them. The sources consulted here derive from the administrative structures governing the Galleys of Spain and their crews¹. As a royal squadron, the fleet generated a specific documentary corpus reflecting the Monarchy's modes of governance, now preserved primarily in the Archivo General de Simancas. These records include account books, muster rolls, and galley inventories, as well as correspondence, reports, petitions, and proposals submitted to the King, which in turn elicited decrees and orders issued through the Councils of the Crown.

References to objects in relation to the rowers are ubiquitous in these sources. Physical goods were fundamental to the squadron's governance. However, engaging with them requires a shift in perspective: rather than simply identifying which objects were recorded, it is necessary to consider why they were recorded in the first place. This entails examining the purposes of the documents and the bureaucratic practices that shaped them². Material culture thus becomes a means of addressing political questions. Within the context of confinement, objects and their uses were inextricably bound to power and to specific modes of domination—mechanisms that extended well beyond direct violence³ and were articulated through everyday material practices.

In early modern societies, social order was structured by inequality⁴. From a contemporary legal perspective, access to rights—and the obligations attached to them—defined one's position within society, as did total or partial exclusion from such rights⁵. In the galleys, slavery and judicial sentencing provided the justification for obliging both enslaved enemies and condemned subjects to serve the King without remuneration. The legal alterity represented by all these statuses was a distinct legal situation, rather than a state of lawlessness⁶. Within this unequal framework, material objects played a role in defining legal statuses and regulating access to certain resources⁷. This article therefore

¹ The Galleys of Spain was one of the royal squadrons that the Crown of the Hispanic monarchy had in the Mediterranean from the early sixteenth century, and navigated the coastlines of the Crowns of Castile and Aragon. Francisco-Felipe Olesa Muñido, *La organización naval de los estados mediterráneos y en especial de España durante los siglos XVI y XVII* (Editorial Naval, 1968), 1: 504–16.

² Catherine Richardson, "Written Texts and the Performance of Materiality," in *Writing Material Culture History*, eds. Giorgio Riello and Anne Gerritsen (Bloomsbury, 2014), 45–58.

³ Falk Bretschneider, "Violence et obéissance : la place et le rôle des châtiments corporels dans les établissements d'enfermement aux XVIII^e et XIX^e siècles," in *Enfermements. Volume II: Règles et dérèglements en milieu clos (IV^e-XIX^e siècle)*, eds. Isabelle Heullant-Donat, et al. (Éditions de la Sorbonne, 2015).

⁴ Giacomo Todeschini, "Servitude et travail à la fin du Moyen Âge. La dévalorisation des salariés et les pauvres 'peu méritants'", *Annales. Histoire, Sciences Sociales* 70, no. 1 (2015): 81–89.

⁵ Tamar Herzog, *Defining Nations: Immigrants and Citizens in Early Modern Spain and Spanish America* (Yale University Press, 2003); Simona Cerutti, *Étrangers. Étude d'une condition d'incertitude dans une société d'Ancien Régime* (Bayard, 2012).

⁶ António Manuel Hespanha, "Fazer um império com palavras," in *O Governo Dos Outros. Poder e diferença no império português*, eds. Ângela Barreto Xavier and Cristina Nogueira da Silva (Imprensa de Ciências Sociais, 2016).

⁷ Simona Cerutti et al., eds, *La cité des choses: une nouvelle histoire de la citoyenneté* (Anacharsis, 2024), 10.

examines the role of objects—chains, food, clothing, and medicines—in the construction of social order aboard the galleys. It explores how materiality can offer a perspective “from below” on structures of domination, asking how rowers lived within this system, how objects illuminate forms of power beyond overt violence, and how domination was articulated through the differential distribution of goods among the rowing crews.

I. The materiality of domination: surveillance and maintenance

Surveillance formed a cornerstone of the material framework of confinement in the galleys. The propensity of enslaved and convicted rowers to attempt escape was widely acknowledged by contemporaries⁸. On land, confinement relied on sealed doors, barred windows, and enclosed spaces. The galley, by contrast, posed a different challenge. Its structure consisted of an open deck lined with rows of benches along a central gangway, where officers and crew circulated⁹. In such an exposed environment, where rowers, soldiers, and officers coexisted, the question arises: which objects rendered the galley a space of confinement for the *chusma*?

Chains were central to this system. In galley inventories, alongside rigging, artillery, sails, and cooking cauldrons—typically one for the rower’s food—, shackles appear consistently. Their use, however, was neither uniform nor automatic. Not all rowers were restrained in the same way; practices varied according to the nature of their work, their degree of social dislocation (closely tied to belonging and spatial mobility), and their perceived risk of escape. Those considered most likely to flee were kept in heavy irons, while others wore only *calcetas* (iron leg-rings) without fully restricting their movement, allowing them to perform some tasks outside the galleys. Alternative arrangements could also substitute for physical restraint, including bail systems, the provision of replacement slaves, or networks of shared responsibility that guaranteed the value of the rowers. Conversely, if a rower managed to escape, this could trigger a chain of responsibility. Those responsible for guarding him—soldiers, *alguaciles*¹⁰, captains, or other officers—could then be punished in his place, even being chained and forced to row as substitutes for the escaped rower.

The second key dimension of this materiality concerned the maintenance of the rowing crew, including the provision of food, clothing—shirts, jackets, breeches, and blankets—and medical care. The obligation to provide for the rowers was stated in several royal orders to galley officers. This obligation, however, was not new. On the galleys, convicts and slaves were considered dependents of the monarch (their *dominus*). As such, it was his responsibility to provide them with food and clothing—an obligation rooted in the Roman legal tradition of *patria potestas*, which required a master to care for those under his authority¹¹.

The distribution of such goods was, however, unequal. Records indicate that rowers performing specialised tasks—such as sawyers, blacksmiths, carpenters, or musicians—received additional rations of biscuit, wine, and pantry provisions. Labour thus functioned as a primary axis of internal hierarchy in the allocation of material resources. Within this system, even minor material distinctions acquired significant hierarchical meaning¹². Consequently, forms of domination emerged that extended beyond physical coercion, as institutional rules made use of the inmates’ tendency to obey in exchange for material, social, or symbolic rewards¹³.

II. The use of objects: coercion and resistance

Rowers themselves actively engaged with material objects to shape their living conditions, negotiate their positions, and, at times, resist their coerced situation. Slaves and convicts participated in the production, repair, and management of goods: they tailored clothes, forged tools, maintained weaponry, engaged in shipbuilding, and even performed as musicians on the galleys. Evidence also suggests that some had access to writing materials, while others could manipulate visible markers of status—for instance, appearing unchained or dressed as officers—in order to alter their social position.

In this context, galley registers played a crucial role. These documents, which recorded names, physical descriptions, sentences, and trades, were central to the organisation of social order aboard the galleys. As physical papers that were held and kept, these records were a key component of the institutional framework of confinement, determining an individual’s legal and social status. For instance, contemporary complaints reveal that, during the compilation of muster rolls, royal slaves sometimes passed themselves off as privately owned slaves or even as convicts—believing they could more easily be ransomed. These muster rolls also documented specialised skills, which could secure improved rations and greater mobility. Conversely, being identified as an *arráez* (a Barbary corsair captain) or a renegade (a Christian

⁸ Luis Carlos Amezcua Amezcua, “Derecho de evasión y principio de humanidad: notas de Francisco Suárez sobre la obligación penal y la fuga de presos,” *Anuario de filosofía del derecho*, no. 31 (2015): 123.

⁹ Francisco-Felipe Olesa Muñido, *La galera en la navegación y el vombate: el buque suelto* (Junta Ejecutiva del IV Centenario de la Batalla de Lepanto, 1971), 1–68.

¹⁰ The alguacil was the royal officer responsible for the custody and maintenance of the chains.

¹¹ Fr. Wycisk, “‘Alimenta’ et ‘victus’ dans le droit romain classique,” *Revue historique de droit français et étranger* 50, no. 2 (1972): 205–28.

¹² Natalia Muchnik, *Les prisons de la foi. L’enfermement des minorités (XVIe–XVIIIe siècle)* (Presses Universitaires de France, 2019), 81.

¹³ Christian G. De Vito and Adam S. Fagbore, “Introduction: Punitive Perspectives on Labour Management,” *International Review of Social History* 68, no. 31 (2023): 1–14.

convert to Islam) entailed stricter controls and the denial of any prospect of release. Since status was recorded within these documents, these category manipulations could have significant consequences. Moreover, the presence—or absence—of a written judicial sentence could determine how long a man remained in the galleys. Without such a document, some rowers were treated as if they were serving for life. Conversely, certificates issued by physicians or surgeons could enable the release of those deemed “useless” (*inútil*) for service. In this way, a rower’s fate depended largely on the material records produced by the squadron’s officers. Control over the production and validation of documents placed considerable power in the hands of royal officers, facilitating practices such as the extortion of illicit payments in exchange for the drafting or alteration of records.

* * *

The shackling of rowers and the provision for their maintenance thus formed two complementary dimensions of the same system of domination. Royal power over dependents entailed both a right of possession and an obligation of care. This duality did not operate abstractly, but was enacted through material means. The same logic that justified the use of chains also underpinned the provision of food, clothing, and basic necessities. Royal power, in this sense, was materially embodied through objects.

From this perspective, the material things played a decisive role in shaping the nature of confinement within the galley fleet. Hierarchies were constructed and expressed through objects: through the use of shackles, the allocation of clothing, and access to food rations. These distinctions were recorded and reinforced through documentary practices. By examining the galley through its material dimension, it becomes possible to uncover a range of lived experiences that complicate rigid legal categories such as “slave” or “convict”, and instead reveal the flexible and context-dependent ways in which domination was exercised.

Escapes from the “Zucht- und Waisenhaus” St. Leonhard in St. Gallen, 1663–1798

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The workhouse

The “Zucht- und Waisenhaus St. Leonhard” – in the following paper called “workhouse”¹ – was opened in 1663 in the old monastery St. Leonhard in St. Gallen. Several factors motivated the city to establish such an institution.² The Holy Spirit Hospital, which was responsible for the orphans until the 17th century, was overloaded with children and that was no longer tenable. Initially, the workhouse served only as a workplace for the orphans, who continued to be housed in the Holy Spirit Hospital. At the same time, the authorities sought to address the issues of begging and so-called “slovenliness”, a term used for people who did not conform to social norms. They wanted to educate these individuals to be obedient and good workers. Over time, orphans also came to live in the workhouse, and the distinction between “slovenly” individuals and orphans gradually blurred. For this reason, the term “inmates” is used here to refer to both children and adults. In St. Gallen, the inmates carried out different forms of textile work, which changed over time, always with the aim of increasing the institution’s economic efficiency.³

The workhouse was both a place of refuge and a place of punishment. Alongside forced admissions, there were also voluntary ones. The institution offered emergency care in the form of shelter, simple food and basic medical treatment. In the early modern period, parents were responsible for financing their children’s education. Families unable to afford this sometimes placed their children in the workhouse, hoping they would receive an education there or be placed in an apprenticeship. Although some individuals entered voluntarily, the majority of inmates were confined against their will.⁴

Permeable walls

This contribution focuses less on the institution itself and more on the stories of escape from it. Throughout its existence, there were numerous escape attempts and acts of resistance against admission. This raises several questions: Where and why were the walls permeable? What motives and possible grievances prompted escapes? What tools or strategies were used? Was there a connection between the disciplinarian’s⁵ violence and an increase in escape attempts? What was daily life like for the inmates, and what forms of interaction or rule-breaking occurred? Were voluntarily admitted individuals treated differently?

These questions point to the need to look beyond formal regulations and examine the workhouse as a lived environment. A closer look at the physical structure of the building and the everyday practices within it reveals how inmates identified and exploited opportunities to escape.

Various structural weaknesses made escapes possible.⁶ Some inmates broke holes in the walls; others took advantage of doors left open by mistake. Inmates who behaved well were granted certain freedoms. Some worked outside the institution, either in a factory or for a master craftsman, and were free to come and go. Volunteers and those considered trustworthy were sometimes allowed outside to smoke or to receive visitors – opportunities that could be used to flee.

¹ There is no precise English equivalent; the term could also be rendered as “house of correction”. However, since the historical sources themselves occasionally refer to the “Zucht- und Waisenhaus” as a “workhouse” this term is used here.

² The city had various role models in Europe and in Swiss cities such as Zurich, Basel and Bern.

³ Schöb, “Umgang mit Waisen und ungehorsamen Kindern in der Frühen Neuzeit. Kinder im Zucht- und Waisenhaus St. Leonhard im 17. und 18. Jahrhundert,” in *Kindheit in der Ostschweiz*, ed. Historischer Verein des Kanton St. Gallen. Neujahrsblatt 164. FormatOst, 2024.

⁴ The article is based on a wide variety of sources from the “Stadtarchiv der Ortsbürgergemeinde St. Gallen”, in particular: Protokolle des Zucht- und Waisenhauses, Ratsprotokolle, Verordnenprotokolle, Ordnungen des Zucht- und Waisenhauses. The text is based on Noëmi Schöb’s doctoral thesis, which is still in progress. The sources are listed in more detail there.

⁵ In the sources, the disciplinarian was referred to as the “Zuchtmeister”.

⁶ Schwendimann Mühlheim, “Gefangen im Schallenhaus: Strafvollzug in der Stadt Bern 1775–1817”, *Berner Zeitschrift für Geschichte und Heimatkunde* 77, no. 1 (2015): 28.

Lack of material resources

Examining the material conditions helps explain why someone might risk an escape. Sophie Abdela notes that poor living conditions – insufficient food, inadequate housing, and economic hierarchies – can fuel collective unrest.⁷ This is also evident in the workhouse in St. Gallen. Complaints about poor nutrition and hygiene were frequent. Conditions were extremely harsh: illnesses were common, and hygiene standards were appalling. Although the link between cleanliness and health was known – for example, the belief that foul air from latrines caused disease – measures were not always taken conscientiously. Sick inmates were rarely exempted from work.

Sleeping arrangements were also problematic: three children had to share a single sack of hay; only in 1687 was this reduced to two to prevent the spread of disease. Scurvy was widespread due to poor nutrition and the rationing or absence of fresh produce such as vegetables, fruit, or meat. For a long time, inmates were fed almost exclusively “Mus”, a type of oatmeal sometimes enriched with vegetables or other grains, along with a little bread. This led to weakness and pallor. Only at the insistence of a doctor was the diet slightly improved, with additional bread, occasional meat, and side dishes such as beans or milk.

In addition to material deprivation, the violence of the disciplinarian also drove people to flee. Punishments such as foot shackles, beatings, solitary confinement, and public humiliation were common.⁸

Stories of escape

For inmates who had been detained in the workhouse for a longer period of time, the risk of escape was higher. According to Sophie Abdela, this is unsurprising: long periods of detention strengthened solidarity, as they allowed inmates to form lasting social bonds and gain insight into the institution’s inner workings. Only after several months did stable networks emerge that enabled collective action. Repeated exposure to poor conditions and authoritarian control also sharpened inmates’ awareness of material issues. Their protests targeted not only escape but also concrete improvements, such as demands for better food – transforming resistance from impulsive acts into strategic efforts.⁹

These social bonds and demands for improvements are evident in the following examples. In 1778, five inmates accused the disciplinarian Peter Rheiner of beating a sick inmate so severely that he died. The authorities, however, believed Rheiner and merely issued a warning. Complaints continued to accumulate: his maid, Maria Engler, fled, claiming that Rheiner was harsh and intolerable. Her successor, Anna Maria Weyermann, also fled shortly after taking the position.

In July 1781, several inmates attempted an escape. They exploited structural weaknesses by breaking a hole in the wall beneath the window of the men’s dormitory. They tied together a piece of cloth to lower themselves down the exterior wall. The cloth tore, causing one escapee to fall dangerously; he was severely injured and died the same night. Two inmates managed to flee, while the others were captured and confined.

In the aftermath, the involved inmates were placed under strict surveillance and punished with foot shackles. The authorities ordered structural reinforcements to secure the dormitories. During subsequent interrogations, several inmates voiced serious complaints against Rheiner: poor and insufficient food,¹⁰ harsh labor conditions, withheld earnings, and violent treatment. Rheiner was reminded of regulations, which were adjusted as a result, but he faced no further consequences.

Earlier in the institution’s history, the disciplinarian Georg Stäheli faced more severe consequences when the inmate Georg Schlumpf escaped in 1676. Schlumpf fled during a church service held outside the institution. At the time, Stäheli was attending the *Musikkollegium* in St. Mangen. The council dismissed him for failing in his supervisory duties, noting that several inmates had already escaped under his watch.

Over the centuries, inmates used various tactics to escape. In 1764, one inmate stole the keys from the disciplinarian’s daughter at the market, attacked her from behind, choked her so she could not speak, and threatened to kill her. Using the keys, he freed another inmate and the two escaped. Another inmate promised three others money and food if they helped him flee. He had smuggled money and a silver watch chain into the institution. After his first escape attempt failed, he made a second attempt, during which he attacked the disciplinarian with an iron bar. As punishment, the institution sought to send him overseas for military service. However, he died one month later at the age of 23.

⁷ Sophie Abdela, “Quand la prison s’embrase: révoltes et révoltés carcéraux (Paris, XVIIIe siècle).” *Crime, Histoire & Sociétés* 26 (2022): 25–50, <https://doi.org/10.4000/chs.3359>.

⁸ Between 1750 and 1769, the authorities imposed additional penalties on 80 % of inmates who were involved in an escape.

⁹ Abdela, “Quand la prison s’embrase.”

¹⁰ Their poor nutrition can be proven by the reports, as there are reports of several cases of scurvy during this period. The causes are mistakenly attributed to the cleanliness of the dormitories and toilets.

Conclusion

Poor hygiene and nutrition – essentially a lack of material resources – as well as the violence of the disciplinarians contributed significantly to escape attempts. In the examples given, and in many others, complaints about violence led only to superficial inquiries; disciplinarians were usually believed and faced consequences only after repeated incidents. Structural defects and certain freedoms granted to inmates also created opportunities for escape.

Workhouses were not merely places of discipline but also lived environments with daily routines, interactions, rule violations, acts of resistance, and conflicts. Many inmates defied the rules, risked escape, and resisted authority.¹¹

With the French invasion in 1798, all inmates were released and the institution was closed – at a time when criticism of the inadequate care and accommodation of orphans together with “slovenly” labelled people was growing louder.

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¹¹ Falk Bretschneider, “40 Jahre nach Surveiller et punir – was bleibt? Michel Foucaults Monument der Sozialwissenschaften und die Historiographie des Gefängnisses.” In *Überwachen und Strafen: Neuere Entwicklungen im Justizvollzug*, ed. Nicolas Queloz, et al. (Stämpfli Verlag, 2018), 1–32; Falk Bretschneider, “Zuchthaus”, in *Enzyklopädie Der Neuzeit Online*, 2019, https://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/enzyklopaedie-der-neuzeit/zuchthaus-COM_387883; Martin Dinges, “Frühneuzeitliche Armenfürsorge als Sozialdisziplinierung? Probleme mit einem Konzept”. *Geschichte und Gesellschaft* 17, no. 1 (1991): 5–29; Falk Bretschneider et al., “Vorwort” In *Orte Der Verwahrung: Die innere Organisation von Gefängnissen, Hospitälern und Klöstern seit dem Spätmittelalter*, ed. Gerhard Ammerer et al. (Leipziger Universitätsverlag, 2010); Sophie Abdela, “Vivre l’enfermement: pratiques, expériences et parcours de détention (XVIe-XIXe siècles).” *Criminocorpus* [En ligne] 23 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.4000/criminocorpus.13169>.

Confinement(s) and Circulation(s): Prisons in Early Modern South Asia

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Despite the recent surge of interest among historians to investigate the practices of incarceration and penalty before the period described by Foucault as the “birth of prison”, much of that enthusiasm has coalesced around investigation of European practices of incarceration.¹ As a result, the history of incarceration and penalty resembled a history of penal reforms in the Western world. The situation is not helped by the scholarship from non-European contexts. Much of the work on non-European histories of prisons and confinements still trace their evolution to colonial intervention and modalities of governance.² Therefore, the “diffusionist perspective”, i.e. imprisonment and prisons emerging from the West and then spreading onwards still dominates non-European historiographies. Importantly, these works show the considerable transformation and modification in what were essentially European practices and traditions of penalty, in colonised society and non-European cultures. As a result, the conflation of early modern confinement with European practices of penalty has become deeply embedded. Much of the conversation about early modern forms of incarceration has come to focus on the bridewells, the workhouses, the Bagnes etc, and the shifting back the chronological rupture from the mid-eighteenth to the sixteenth century. The paper does not argue for a consideration of non-European and non-colonial context merely for the sake of it. There is much scope and need for a chronological and geographical extension of the domain. Such an extension would be of much benefit in bringing out interesting parallels and divergences in the trajectories of global histories of confinement and prisons in a period of global early modernity.

My paper shows how “prison” and “confinement” was not organised around a single central institution such as the Bagnes or workhouses. In early modern Western India, practices of confinement and imprisonment took place across different spaces and acquired different modalities, each serving different and overlapping functions between c.1500-1800. For this reason, it is difficult to pinpoint an exact practice of confinement that would fit every instance of its usage in early modern India. This peculiarity of the practice was shaped by the singular and unique local and economic circumstances in which precolonial, autochthonous rulers as well as European officials resorted to them.

The paper uses the archival records of autochthonous states that dominated Western India between 1500 and 1800. In this period, western India was under the control of local Islamic Sultanates of Bijapur, Ahmednagar and then the Marathas. At the same time, along the littorals and the coastline of Western India, there were many important European factories in Bombay, Surat, Konkan etc. These carefully preserved archival records from the Sultanate, and the Maratha state consists of administrative records, royal injunctions and orders, legal suites, family papers and memoirs and petition that provide a useful snapshot of widespread use of imprisonment, as well of its importance as an extractive machinery in the military-fiscal complex. Also critical are the administrative records of forts such as *Raigad* and *Sinhagad*, i.e. the two most important forts of the region which provide a valuable and vivid picture of everyday commercial and social life within the forts and the prisoners there. Lastly, the paper also uses European sources such as the British factory records and records from the Bombay province which contained many everyday details of the running and maintenance of these factories. The paper utilises the conceptual and methodological benefits of recent writings on global labour history, especially the ones that foreground the role of coerced migration.³ But the paper

¹ Norval Morris and David J. Rothman, eds., *The Oxford History of the Prison: The Practice of Punishment in Western Society* (Oxford University Press, 1995); Pieter Spierenburg, *The Spectacle of Suffering: Executions and the Evolution of Repression: From a Preindustrial Metropolis to the European Experience* (Cambridge University Press, 1984); see also Mary Gibson, “Global Perspectives on the Birth of the Prison,” *American Historical Review* 116, no. 4 (October 2011): 1040–1063.

² See Sophie Abdela, “Prisons on the Edge: Perspectives on the Late Medieval and Early Modern History of Confinement in the Francosphere,” *The English Historical Review* 139, no. 598–599 (2024): 868–887; Frank Dikötter and Ian Brown, eds., *Cultures of Confinement: A History of the Prison in Africa, Asia, and Latin America* (Cornell University Press, 2007). See also Ricardo D. Salvatore and Carlos Aguirre, eds., *The Birth of the Penitentiary in Latin America: Essays on Criminology, Prison Reform, and Social Control, 1830–1940* (University of Texas Press, 1996); Peter Zinoman, *The Colonial Bastille: A History of Imprisonment in Vietnam, 1862–1940* (University of California Press, 2001); Florence Bernault, ed., *A History of Prison and Confinement in Africa*, trans. Janet Roitman (Heinemann, 2003).

³ Clare Anderson, ed., *A Global History of Convicts and Penal Colonies* (Bloomsbury Academic, 2018); Christian G. De Vito, Clare Anderson, and Ulbe Bosma, “Transportation, Deportation and Exile: Perspectives from the Colonies in the Nineteenth and Twentieth Centuries,” *International Review of Social History* 63, S26 (2018): 1–24.

brings a much-needed historiographical addendum to it by bringing in a conversation on non-colonial and pre-colonial contexts by de-coupling it from colonial governance. Colonial governance therefore stands in my paper as but merely one modality that inscribed penal mobility. Additionally, the paper also leans on the conceptual framework of monetisation and commercialisation in early modern and early colonial India. Much of the discussion there has rather regrettably, not considered the role of coercion and penal mechanisms such as confinement. Money use and increase in economic transactions and the development of the market seems to have followed a trajectory that responded to international trade and growth in occupational mobility.⁴ The violence and penalty embedded in the process that tied a predominantly agrarian exchange system to the requirements of perpetual warfare and military undertakings also need to be explored. The study will demonstrate how the entwined phenomena of coerced mobility and commodification shaped experiences, function and the material realities of confinement.

Forts

In the context of unrelenting warfare, the forts became places where prisoners were lodged. The forts were central to economic activities, petty commodity production, military manufacture and trade. Forts in early modern Western India basically served as fortified urban centres. Forts were home to army barracks, stables, encampments, markets, residences, royal court, temples and entertainment halls. The prison within the fort, known variously as "*Turung*" or "*Bandikhana*", aided the process of urbanisation and military utility. Within the prison, spaces and facilities allotted to the prisoners depended on their social status. An imprisoned noble or a military chief would be accompanied by his entire retinue (including slaves, wives and children) who all took residences and lived with him in the prison. It, therefore, reproduced the household and familial quarters within the confines of the prison. On the other hand, ordinary individuals could find themselves imprisoned together within dungeons in a very narrow space. Filth and lack of spaces reminded them of their status. The prisons in the forts served two important function - it ensured through coercive and violent means, the monetisation of social relations and the commodification of work. I claim in the paper that confinement in early modern Western India must be placed alongside other coercive mechanisms such as enforced production of cash crops, taxation and collection of tribute that pushed the circulation of money and transaction in cash. The fort was also used to subdue recalcitrant elites and members of nobility, and to enable state expansion and projection of royal power in the region. In that sense, forts became a tool aimed at restricting migration for work and criminalising vagrancy. Almost ironically, the forts enabled coerced mobility of the enslaved individuals for construction and military production. The fort prisons were also a place where all forms of merchants, artisans and non-coerced workers used consistently moved through, as elite prisoners required proper maintenance and performance of their routine chores, as they literally recreated their households within the prison.⁵

Factories

The British and other colonial powers were also operating in the centuries between the sixteenth and nineteenth centuries in Western India even as they did not possess absolute control over the region, which happened in c. 1818. They operated through chartered trading companies, i.e. the East Indian Companies. These companies operated through factories, which were organised as trading hubs. These factories were fortified outposts of the European powers on the coastline of India where the European legal and penal writ ran large. Even as these factories organised warehousing and trading of commodities between India and Europe, they contained prisons. Those convicted for theft, cheating etc within English factories were kept in these prisons and were often shipped onwards to British colonies such as St. Helena as slaves. Additionally, it also confined debtors whom they released after extracting the money. If the money was not forthcoming, they also joined the ships going to the islands as slaves. Importantly, the factories were the place where the agents and factors (officials in charge of other/rival European factories) were regularly lodged and released after a ransom from their colonial counterparts. The prisons or dungeons in these fortified factories were cramped spaces that were not meant to hold large numbers.⁶ The famous, or rather infamous "black hole of Calcutta" was a small prison within the British factory in Fort William which became well known in June 1756 when between around 64-124 British troop, who were confined within the prison as a result of the capture of the fort by the local ruler, died overnight due to suffocation and stroke.

Homes and Lockups

Homes could also be turned into spaces of confinement by the autochthonous rulers. House arrest was an important method of extraction of fines and other forms of outstanding payments due to the state or nobility. At the same time, it was also used as a tool to prohibit the defection of military leaders and government bureaucrats, along with inducing them to return back to the service using the house arrest of their family members and kin. This practice existed across various autochthonous states from the fifteenth century onwards, in Western India. In a practice reminiscent of

⁴ Frank Perlin, "Of White Whale and Countrymen in the Eighteenth-Century Maratha Deccan: Extended Class Relations, Rights, and the Problem of Rural Autonomy Under the Old Regime," *Journal of Peasant Studies* 5, no. 2 (1978): 172–237.

⁵ See *Selections from the Satara Raja's and the Peishwas' Diaries* [SSRPD], prepared by G. C. Vad, 9 vols. (Bombay: 1902–1911); *Selections from the Peshwa Daptar* [SPD], edited by G. S. Sardesai, 45 vols. (Government Central Press, 1930–1934).

⁶ East India Company Factory Records, India Office Records (G), British Library, London.

confinement on the forts, these individuals were sometimes confined in their domestic spaces together with their families. Lastly, the lockup of the police (*Chavadi*) in bigger cities under autochthonous rulers had places for confinement. These were especially used to imprison those who were criminalised for specific acts such as adultery and/or vagrancy, before selling them off to buyers. As such, like European factories, the *Chavadis* also became an intermediate holding space for prisoners and a node along their larger movement and circulation. The *chavadis* also made punishment profitable and monetary. Much of the money therefore obtained was credited to the police in-charge of large urban centres.

Through such an analysis, the paper shows how, rather than having an institutional focus, early modern confinement could operate via dispersed spaces such as forts, factories among several others. Together, these spaces were pushing through a “many headed hydra” of monetisation of social and penal processes and circulation and mobility of bodies. At the same time, these diverse and dispersed nature of the spaces also meant that penal and legal pluralism was embedded in the very mechanism of these prisons. This also helps us understand how different the experience and material realities of the prisoners in the early modern period could be according to their social status. While elites could have their domestic and familial spaces recreated inside the forts, those who were not fortunate enough to pay their way out of it found themselves either in overcrowded dungeons, gasping for breath and light or worse, packed off to a distant island or to the house of their buyers.

Inside and Outside the Cloister: A Geography of Latin Devotion and of the Social Entanglements of the Franciscan friars in 15th-century Venetian Crete

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1. Introduction: Latin Devotion in a multi-confessional world

In the Venetian maritime possessions of the Eastern Mediterranean, the expression “Latin devotion” denotes the religious practices of a minority group composed of Roman Catholic faithful who also constituted the ruling elite, primarily Venetian settlers established after the Fourth Crusade¹. This group stood in contrast to the majority of the population, which remained adherent to the Greek Orthodox Church despite Venetian rule and the enduring schism with the Patriarchate of Constantinople².

In territories such as Crete, Corfu, Euboea, and parts of the Peloponnese³, this confessional division was institutionalized through the replacement of Orthodox bishops with Latin prelates, who were often non-resident⁴. Consequently, pastoral care was inconsistently provided, and liturgical practices frequently overlapped: Latin and Greek communities shared rites and ceremonies⁵, while Greek clergy were permitted to officiate according to the Eastern rite under nominal papal primacy⁶. Over time, processes of social and cultural integration—particularly through mixed marriages—contributed to a gradual attenuation of confessional boundaries⁷. Nevertheless, in Crete a degree of Latin religious identity persisted until the Ottoman conquest of the mid-seventeenth century, especially in urban centers such as Candia, Rethymnon, and Chania⁸.

This persistence was further supported by the presence and missionary activity of Western mendicant orders, including the Franciscans and Dominicans⁹. Through the adaptation of former Byzantine monastic structures and the foundation of new convents, these friars contributed significantly to reshaping the religious landscape of Venetian

¹ Chryssa Maltezou, “The historical and social context,” in *Literature and society in Renaissance Crete*, ed. David Holton (Cambridge University Press, 1991).

² Cristina Setti, “Sudditi fedeli o eretici tollerati? Venezia e i ‘greci’ dal tardo Medioevo ai consulti di Paolo Sarpi e Fulgenzio Micanzio,” *Ateneo Veneto* 201, no. 13.2 (2014): 145–82.

³ Or the so-called “Venetian Romania”, Freddy Thiriet, *La Romanie vénitienne au Moyen Âge. Le développement et l’exploitation du domaine colonial vénitien (XIIe-XVe siècles)* (De Boccard, 1959).

⁴ Especially starting from the period of the Great Western Schism (1378-1417), see Freddy Thiriet, *Études sur la Romanie greco-vénitienne (Xe-XVe siècles)* (Variorum Reprints, 1977), 208–12 and 496–504 (article no. XII).

⁵ But of course, not always and everywhere, see Evangelia Skoufari, “Aspects of religious coexistence: the historiography of the Orthodox and Catholic Churches in the Ionian Islands during the period of Venetian domination.” in *The Ionian Islands. Aspects of their history and culture*, ed. Anthony Hirst and Patrick Sammon (Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2014), 264–75. For the sharing of the most common religious rites in Venetian and Ottoman Levant, see Aspasia Papadaki, *Cerimonie religiose e laiche nell’isola di Creta durante il dominio veneziano* (Fondazione Centro Italiano di Studi sull’Alto Medioevo, 2005); Cesare Santus, *Trasgressioni necessarie: Communicatio in sacris, coesistenza e conflitti tra le comunità cristiane orientali* (Publications de l’École française de Rome, 2022), <http://books.openedition.org/efr/31792>.

⁶ This was true especially after the formal reunification of the two Churches in the Ecumenical Council of Florence, which was not recognized by most of the Greek prelates and, conversely, by most of the Greek faithful. See Deno J. Geanakoplos, *Byzantine East and Latin West: two worlds of Christendom in Middle Ages and Renaissance. Studies in ecclesiastical and cultural history* (Harper, 1966).

⁷ Sally McKee, *Uncommon dominion. Venetian Crete and the myth of ethnic purity* (University of Pennsylvania Press, 2000); Cristina Setti, “La contaminazione nel discorso giuridico e sociale: i matrimoni tra greci e latini nella Repubblica di Venezia (secc. XVI-XVIII),” *Acta Histriae* 23 (2015): 43–65.

⁸ Giuseppe Gerola, “Topografia delle chiese della città di Candia,” *Bessarione. Rivista di studi orientali*, 1918.

⁹ Nickiphoros I. Tsougarakis, *The Latin Religious Orders in Medieval Greece, 1204-1500* (Brepols, 2012).

territories, especially in the urban spaces¹⁰. Among them, the Franciscans proved particularly influential¹¹, as evidenced by major establishments such as the Monastery of Saint Francis in Candia¹².

2. The Monastery of St Francis in Candia and its relevance in the 15th century

The main source of this study is an inventory compiled within this cloister between the years 1417 and 1449¹³. It is currently preserved in Venice, at the Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana¹⁴, and very recently it has been published by the scholars Donal Cooper, an expert of Franciscan devotional art and history, and Nickyphoros Tsougarakis, who has long worked on the establishment of Latin Church in medieval Greece¹⁵. I discovered the edition (released just on late 2025) later than the manuscript, which I had consulted during previous research on the economy and material culture of the early modern Minor Observants travelling for and from the Holy Land¹⁶.

One of my findings was that Candia was part of the oldest maritime route which connected the itinerant friars serving in the Ottoman Palestine with their Franciscan headquarters in Jerusalem¹⁷. At least until the 1640s, the port-town of Candia was one leg of the itinerary; the related information circulated through the guardian of the Monastery of St Francis in Candia, while logistical assistance to the travellers was granted by another Minor Observants' hub in the town—the Hospice of St John Baptist located in proximity to the harbour of the town¹⁸. Furthermore, later evidence revealed that from 1452 a specific administrative pattern was established by the secular authorities for the management of the economy of the monastery of St Francis, with the consent of the papacy. This pattern foresaw the presence of a coffer named *Camera di Cristo*, sometimes intended as an office, whose tenants were three lay procurators appointed by the local Venetian *reggimento*¹⁹.

Apparently, the presence of a lay administration represented a later stage of the management of the friars' collective property. From the point of view of 17th-century sources, this fact seems the logical adaptation of the cloister community to the *jurisdictionalist* ideology spread among the Venetian patriciates. It consisted in a mentality according to which the State had to keep under its own control both the economic and legal life of Catholic ecclesiastical communities about issues pertaining the secular sphere²⁰. But if we rest on 15th-century sources, this development was rather consistent with the application of the pronounced pauperism of the Franciscan family of the Minor Observants, which was gradually taking the hegemony within the Order of St Francis²¹.

Recent scholarship has argued for this second strand of interpretation. In particular, the Nickyphoros Tsougarakis and Donal Cooper have stated that the very existence of the inventory is to attribute to the creeping conflict between the Conventual friars and the Movement of the Observance, which during the first decades of the 15th century was rooted all over the Franciscan communities throughout Europe²². In the case of St Francis in Candia, a charge of mismanagement, supposedly brought up by the Observants before the secular authorities, made it necessary to appoint three lay procurators to draw a list of the belongings and of the revenues of the Monastery, and to check on their subsistence²³. Therefore, it seems that the revenues and the use of paraments and liturgical objects were managed by the friars themselves by appointing someone within their community to this purpose²⁴. Whether the case, it is true that even in other Franciscan families and communities dispersed through European states there was a general

¹⁰ Giuseppe Gerola, "Topografia delle chiese della città di Candia," *Bessarione. Rivista di studi orientali*, 1918.

¹¹ Giuseppe Gerola, "I francescani in Creta al tempo del dominio veneziano," *Collectanea Franciscana* 2, no. 3–4 (1932): 301–25 (no. 3) e 445–61 (no. 4).

¹² Gerola, "Topografia delle chiese della città di Candia;" Gerola, "I francescani in Creta."

¹³ Gerola, "I francescani in Creta," 314.

¹⁴ BNM, mss Lat., cl. IX, cod. 186 (3400).

¹⁵ Donal Cooper e Nickyphoros I. Tsougarakis, "The Fifteenth-Century Inventories of the Friary of St Francis, Candia. A New Edition and Commentary," *Frankokratia* 6 (2025): 205–83.

¹⁶ The occasion was a contribution given to the ERC_COG-H2020 Project HOLYLAB – *A Global Economic Organization in the Early Modern Period: The Custody of Holy Land through its Account Books (1600-1800)* (Grant Agreement 101001857, whose Principal Investigator is Felicita Tramontana (Università Roma Tre, Italy). I communicated the first result of this research in a conference paper, that is Cristina Setti, "Venice and the Custody of the Holy Land between the 16th and the 17th Centuries. Political, Economic and Jurisdictional Entanglements in the Eastern Mediterranean," *The Venetian State, the Greek Territories and their Stories (13th-18th Cent.)*, Conference in Honour of Anastasia Papadia-Lala (1-3 November 2023, NKUA) (Athens), to be published.

¹⁷ Sandra Toffolo, "Encounters in Renaissance Venice: Exchange, Communication, and Interaction between Jerusalem-Bound Pilgrims and Local Residents," *Annali dell'Istituto storico italo-germanico in Trento* 49, no. 1 (2023): 49–72, <https://doi.org/10.7387/107762>.

¹⁸ Setti, "Venice and the Custody."

¹⁹ *Ibidem*.

²⁰ Setti, "Sudditi fedeli."

²¹ Giacomo Todeschini, "Carita profitto nella dottrina economica francescana da Bonaventura all'Olivi," *Franciscan Studies* 60 (2002): 325–32.

²² Cooper and Tsougarakis, "The Fifteenth-Century Inventories," 209–12.

²³ *Ivi*, 212 and 212n.

²⁴ I could find further evidence of this in ASVe, Senato, Deliberazioni, Roma ordinaria, Filze, folder 68, 8th March 1636, that I used in my previous (but unfortunately still unpublished) study, Setti, Venice and the Custody.

tendency to delegate the administration of the cloisters to laymen, variably called *procuratores* or *amici spirituales*²⁵. These were fundamental intermediaries between the confined communities and the local agents who could satisfy their non-spiritual necessities in conformity with the Rule of Francis—that is its strict prevention about the use of money, whose only purpose was to sustain the primary needs²⁶.

Hence, the inventory of the properties of Saint Francis in Candia is relevant not just to search for insights about the material life of the friars of the Monastery but also to identify who were the mediators of this materiality in Crete regardless of the appointment of the three lay procurators. Indeed, the recorded entries tell us something about the provenance and the estate of its donors and benefactors, as well as about the possible relationships between their own social groups and usual cliques.

3. The structure of the inventory and its usefulness as a source for confined communities

The inventory is composed of four parts (or *quires*, as mentioned in its critical edition). These are divided according to the different typologies of the items its entries record:

- a) Liturgical objects and vestments (list of materials and donors per month).
- b) Annual bequests and single donations, including revenues and real estate properties (also these entries are listed per month).
- c) Repeated and reviewed list of the bequests and donations, in a later version.
- d) List of the books of the library of the monastery²⁷.

In each of the *quires* the first draft of the inventory, dating back to 1417, is clearly distinguishable from later interpolations and corrections²⁸. Moreover, the first free parts are structured according to the monthly cadence of the revenues, alms-gathering, or material donations²⁹. However, the diverse function of the listed objects and categories implied a different logic of recording. Roughly speaking, the compilers adopted slightly different recording patterns, which can be like a domestic inventory of objects (i.e. the list of paraments) and to a catalogue (i.e. the list of the books of the library)³⁰. I observe that the *quire* related to the bequests and donations can resemble more to an account book or extract—following the very basic pattern of religious accounts a *partita semplice*, which during the Middle Ages was proper to ecclesiastic bookkeeping³¹.

In this paper I will focus on this 'accounting' *quire*, which is the richest in information about the intermediate nodes of the network that in fact sustained the convent. My aim is to show firstly how most donors came from a core group of noble families which for some reasons wish to distinguish themselves as benefactors of St Francis in Candia. I will then evaluate these possible reasons, as well as how far this endorsement benefitted the life of the confined friars. This will be done through the exam of the quantity, quality and recurrence of the giving of money, material objects and primary goods, as well as of the geographical ubication of the landed and feudal properties of the kinships involved—an element that could help us to trace the extent of the actual connections of the cloister. To catch the position of the intermediaries, I will also consider other key elements, such as the names of the notaries, whose recurrences reveal an insisted specialization of some of them in the bequests to Saint Francis, with a context of a port-city where several of such professionals were active. Finally, I will discuss the gendered character of the donors, since many of them were widows or devoted women, and the significance of their role as economic mediators of the material needs of the friars.

²⁵ Ludovic Viallet, "Procurateurs et 'personnes interposées' chez les Franciscaines," in *Économie et religion. L'expérience des ordres mendiants (XIIIe-XVe siècle)*, ed. Nicole Bériou and Jacques Chiffolleau (Presses Universitaires de Lyon, 2009), 661–705.

²⁶ Todeschini, "Carita profitto."

²⁷ This has been published earlier and separately analyzed by scholars. See Giorgio Hofmann, "La biblioteca scientifica del monastero di San Francesco in Candia nel medio evo," *Orientalia Christiana Periodica* 8 (1942): 317–60; Nickiphoros I. Tsougarakis, "The Library and School of the Franciscans in Candia," *Frankokratia* 6 (2025): 180–204.

²⁸ Cooper and Tsougarakis, "The Fifteenth-Century Inventories."

²⁹ *Ibidem*.

³⁰ *Ibidem*.

³¹ Pierre Gervais, "Comptabilité et profit: comment saisir les pratiques comptables de l'époque Moderne," *Comptabilité(S): Revue d'histoire des comptabilités* 14 (2021): 1–26.

The Materiality of Confinement. Gift-Giving and Conventual Networks in Early Modern Solothurn (17th and 18th Centuries)

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Introduction

At first glance, early modern women's convents appear to epitomise the very notion of a "confined space". Surrounded by high and seemingly insurmountable walls, these institutions separated those living within them from the outside world. The walls restricted the physical mobility of the people both inside and outside the convent, with clear rules governing who could enter and leave this secluded space. Yet the situation was more complex than it might initially appear. Approaching convents through the lens of materiality invites us to reconsider the nature of cloistral confinement.

Convents and Confinement

Over the last three decades, an increasing interest in the role of women religious in early modern Catholic societies in Europe and beyond has led to a reassessment of assumptions that had previously gone unquestioned. Historians have examined female convents in relation to their significance for familial economies of honour, their function as "bastions of chastity and prayer";¹ and their role as sites of commodity production and material exchange. In doing so, historians have (metaphorically) broken through convent walls that had once been deemed impenetrable and have begun to reintegrate these institutions into the "world."

One event that has profoundly shaped the historiography of women's convents (and must be addressed when discussing the lives of early modern religious women) is the Council of Trent. Held between 1545 and 1563 in the Italian cities of Trento and Bologna, the council tackled church reforms and defined the Catholic Church's position in response to the Protestant Reformation. In its final session, the council also debated the role of women religious in the Catholic church and emphasised the importance of enclosure for nuns living in convents, thereby transforming the (once ungendered) ideal of seclusion into a gender-specific characteristic that significantly reshaped the lives and identities of women religious.²

Since their emergence as a subject of women's history, early modern convents have frequently been examined in relation to the norms of enclosure imposed by the council. Numerous studies have focused on the ways in which church authorities enforced enclosure and nuns resisted it in the wake of the council.³ However, while the normative authority of the decrees adopted at the Council of Trent is beyond dispute, it is important to note the gap between prescriptive norms and local practice.⁴ This paper does not seek to deny the numerous instances of "forced monachisation", as discussed, for example, by Anne Jacobson Schutte.⁵ Nevertheless, it is important to emphasise that the convent did not constitute a prison for every woman living in these institutions.⁶ Indeed, many nuns struck a balance between the

¹ Mary Laven, *Virgins of Venice. Broken Vows and Cloistered Lives in the Renaissance Convent* (New York, 2003), xxiv.

² Elizabeth A. Leffelt, "Spatial Discipline and Its Limits. Nuns and the Built Environment in Early Modern Spain," in *Architecture and the Politics of Gender in Early Modern Europe*, ed. Helen Hills (Aldershot, 2003), 131–49, here 145.

³ It is a narrative supported by studies such as: Isabel M. R. Mendes Drumond Braga, "Enfermement et résistance. Les Religieuses portugaises et la transgression aux XVIIe et XVIIIe siècles," in *Les paradoxes de l'enfermement dans l'Europe moderne (XVIe–XVIIIe siècles). Espagne – France – Portugal*, ed. Vanda Anastácio et al. (Montpellier, 2019), 71–84; Luisa Candau Chacón, "Femmes et enfermements conventuels. Évasion, adaptation et rejet d'un destin imposé (Andalousie occidentale, XVIIe et XVIIIe siècles)," in *Les paradoxes de l'enfermement dans l'Europe moderne (XVIe–XVIIIe siècles). Espagne – France – Portugal*, ed. Vanda Anastácio et al. (Montpellier, 2019), 55–70; Silvia Evangelisti, "'We Do Not Have It, and We Do Not Want It'. Women, Power, and Convent Reform in Florence," *The Sixteenth Century Journal* 34 (2003): 677–700; Francesca Medioli, "An Unequal Law. The Enforcement of Clausura Before and After the Council of Trent," in *Women in Renaissance and Early Modern Europe*, ed. Christine E. Meek (Dublin, 2000), 136–52.

⁴ Amy E. Leonard, "Female Religious Orders," in *A Companion to the Reformation World*, ed. Po-Chia R. Hsia (Oxford, 2004), 236–54, here 241–42.

⁵ Schutte also points out that the concept of "forced monachisation" should be applied with caution: Anne Jacobson Schutte, *By Force and Fear. Taking and Breaking Monastic Vows in Early Modern Europe* (Ithaca, 2011). The issue became increasingly relevant in contexts where a very large proportion of (elite) women lived in convents, as was the case in Venice: Jutta Gisela Sperling, *Convents and the Body Politic in Late Renaissance Venice* (Chicago, 1999).

⁶ On the connection between convents and prison, see: Isabelle Heullant-Donat, Julie Claustre, and Élisabeth Lusset, "Introduction. Clastrum et carcer. Pour une histoire comparée des 'enfermements,'" in *Enfermements. Le cloître et la prison (VIe–XVIIIe siècle)*, vol. 1,

normative ideal of withdrawal from the world and the very real and necessary integration of their convent in the local economy. It is against this backdrop that this paper examines the significance of material objects for conventual practices of enclosure.

Crafting Nuns and their Gifts

Drawing on textual and material sources from three enclosed women's convents in the Swiss town of Solothurn in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, this paper examines stories of baking and crafting nuns and their practices of gift-giving. It asks how material objects enabled communities of religious women to sustain social networks that connected them with the world beyond the convent walls. I argue that nuns employed routines of gifting—the transfer of largely self-produced material objects—to maintain ties with family members and friends over time. In this way, material objects emerge as media capable of transgressing the boundaries of what might otherwise appear, from a purely architectural perspective, to be a confined space.

The nuns of the three Solothurn convents—the Visitandines, the Capuchins, and the Franciscans—were diligent producers of a wide variety of gifts which they shared with those around them. Visitation reports indicate that nuns used their skills in needlework and handicrafts not only for the production of liturgical vestments, but also to create “vanity gifts” (*présents de vanité*) for family members and friends. At the same time, they honoured the tradition of *étrennes*, a New Year's gift-giving practice, to present their network of supporters with homemade sweets and confections.

The Solothurn nuns were no exception in this regard: As Marta Manzaneres Mileo has demonstrated in her study of Barcelona, nuns and their convents were widely known for their expertise in the production of sweet delicacies across early modern Europe and beyond.⁷ According to Edmund Wareham, gift-giving functioned as an innovative strategy of symbolic communication through which convents reminded the world beyond their walls of their presence. His study on the Cistercian nuns of Günters-thal and their tradition of gifting gingerbread shows that these baked goods rendered the connection between convent and society visible. The gingerbread constituted a tangible, palatable and olfactory sign that women's convents were by no means isolated institutions.⁸ Rather, such objects had the potential to produce, shape, and sustain the worldly integration of women's religious communities. At the same time, however, these objects contributed to the maintenance of enclosure, as they not only underscored but also materialised the nuns' absence from the face-to-face society (*Anwesenheitsgesellschaft*) beyond the convent.

Materiality Matters

Materiality thus assumed multiple roles. On the one hand, gifted objects materialised relationships. On the other, the gifts' materiality itself was of crucial importance, as many items circulating within the nuns' networks consisted of perishable foodstuffs and other ephemeral goods. This is hardly surprising, as food—according to Loek Luiten—stood at the centre of early modern sociability. Food gifts could be used to strengthen ties with acquaintances and potential allies, since their value lay less in their monetary worth than in their regular and continuous distribution.⁹

The materiality of these gifts thus played a productive role in shaping gift-giving practices, as the ephemeral nature of edible offerings directly influenced the kind of relationships they sustained. In this sense, the materiality of food gifts reflects the nature of conventual social networks; the gifts' perishability required a regular exchange, while the nuns themselves had to continually assert their “visible absence” behind convent walls in order to remain present within their social network. Temporality (of materiality) therefore emerges as a key factor in the constitution of sociability within early modern religious communities.

In conclusion, material objects enabled early modern nuns to maintain connections with individuals and groups of people beyond the convent walls as well as to sustain their social network, despite (or precisely because they were) living a confined life behind walls. Objects—gifts of all kinds—thus rendered (convent) walls permeable, while simultaneously contributing to the performative maintenance of these boundaries. The practice of gift-giving among nuns and their networks ultimately prompts us to ask to what extent these so-called “confined spaces” of early modern women's convents were in fact confined.

ed. Julie Claustre, Isabelle Heullant-Donat, and Élisabeth Lusset (Paris, 2011), 15–35. The difference between women religious and prison inmates becomes particularly striking when considering hermits and recluses: Anna Benvenuti, Jérôme Nicolas, Isabelle Heullant-Donat, and Julie Claustre, “Cellanae et reclusae dans l'Italie médiévale. Modèles sociaux et comportements religieux,” in *Enfermements. Le cloître et la prison (VIe–XVIIIe siècle)*, vol. 1, ed. Julie Claustre, Isabelle Heullant-Donat, and Élisabeth Lusset (Paris, 2011), 249–60.

⁷ Marta Manzaneres Mileo, “Sweet Femininities. Women and the Confectionery Trade in Eighteenth-Century Barcelona,” *Gender & History* 34 (2022): 1–16, here 1–2.

⁸ Edmund Wareham, “The Hierarchy of Gingerbread. Gift-Giving at Christmas in Medieval Convents,” 2020, <https://www.seh.ox.ac.uk/blog/the-hierarchy-of-gingerbread-gift-giving-at-christmas-in-medieval-convents>.

⁹ Loek Luiten, “Friends and Family, Fruit and Fish. The Gift in Quattrocento Farnese Cultural Politics,” *Renaissance Studies* 33 (2019): 342–57.

Air, soleil, murs. Enfermement et protection de la santé dans les *Carceri Nuove* de Rome (XVIII^e siècle)

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La matérialité de l'espace carcéral constitue une entrée privilégiée pour interroger le poids des considérations sanitaires dans la gestion des prisons à l'époque moderne.¹ C'est à travers cette perspective que cette intervention aborde le cas des *Carceri Nuove* de Rome, en s'appuyant sur la documentation conservée aux Archives d'État de Rome. L'objectif est d'examiner comment s'articulaient, dans la pratique administrative et architecturale, les exigences de sécurité et de protection de la santé des détenus et du personnel.

Achevées en 1655 à l'initiative d'Innocent X, les *Carceri Nuove* furent les premières prisons romaines conçues spécifiquement à des fins de détention. Le projet répondait à une double ambition : réaffirmer l'autorité pontificale face à la noblesse romaine, qui contrôlait l'une des principales prisons de la ville, et incarner un idéal de justice tempérée par la clémence et la charité. L'édifice, de quatre étages, s'élevait sur la via Giulia, un des principaux axes de la Rome moderne. Il accueillait hommes et femmes dans des espaces différenciés selon la gravité du délit : les détenus pour délits mineurs étaient logés dans des dortoirs collectifs appelés *larghe*, tandis que les accusés de crimes plus graves occupaient les cellules *segrete*, soumises à un régime bien plus restrictif. La charité, principe fondamental de l'Église catholique à l'époque de la Contre-Réforme, trouvait son expression dans la conception même de l'édifice, dont un brouillon d'épigraphe prévu pour orner l'entrée résume bien l'idéal : le nouvel édifice était destiné à soulager les âmes et les corps des détenus. Cet idéal se concrétisait par une attention à la santé tant sur le plan curatif que préventif. La prison disposait d'un personnel médical permanent et de deux infirmeries organisées selon le régime de détention. La dimension préventive était quant à elle directement inscrite dans les choix architecturaux : le site, l'orientation du bâtiment, la disposition des ouvertures, tout fut pensé pour assurer une bonne ventilation et une exposition solaire suffisante. L'édifice se distinguait ainsi par des espaces relativement vastes, un réseau d'égouts, des cours intérieures avec fontaines permettant aux détenus de prendre l'air, et des fenêtres favorisant l'exposition solaire et la circulation de l'air.

Le principe de la salubrité devait cependant aller de pair avec celui de la sécurité, entendue comme prévention des évasions, surveillance des prisonniers et limitation des communications avec l'extérieur. La question des évasions se révéla particulièrement préoccupante : la première fuite fut enregistrée à peine un an après l'ouverture de la prison, et les décennies suivantes virent se multiplier des épisodes similaires, imputables à la fragilité des murs autant qu'à l'insuffisance de la surveillance. À l'automne 1784, des rumeurs faisant état de projets d'évasion collectifs conduisirent à ordonner aux gardiens de veiller chaque nuit pour déjouer les tentatives de fuite et intercepter les conversations des détenus. Ce renforcement de la surveillance eut des répercussions inattendues : exposés au froid hivernal dans des espaces mal protégés, plusieurs gardiens tombaient régulièrement malades et se retrouvaient incapables d'assurer leur service. Dans un mémoire adressé à la Reverenda Camera Apostolica, l'organe chargé de la gestion financière des États pontificaux, ils réclamèrent des manteaux, en faisant valoir que les frais de soins et de remplacement auxquels leurs maladies donneraient lieu dépasseraient largement le coût d'un tel équipement. Le trésorier acquiesça, mais le problème se répéta en 1787 : les vêtements fournis deux ans plus tôt, de mauvaise facture et incapables de protéger du froid, s'étaient révélés inadaptés, et de nouveaux vêtements furent obtenus avec la même justification. Ces épisodes, en entrouvrant une fenêtre sur la prison comme lieu de travail, révèlent la logique qui sous-tendait la prise en charge sanitaire : protéger la santé des gardiens relevait moins d'une sollicitude charitable que de la nécessité de maintenir une surveillance efficace. La tutelle de la santé apparaît ainsi comme un corollaire fonctionnel de la sécurité, indissociable de considérations administratives et financières.

Ce lien entre les deux impératifs valait également pour les prisonniers, et se trouvait explicitement formulé dans la rhétorique institutionnelle. Un mémoire rédigé en 1764 par les administrateurs des *Carceri Nuove* soulignait que les

¹ Sur la médecine en milieu carcéral : Joe Sim, *Medical Power in Prisons: The Prison Medical Service in England 1774-1989* (Open University Press, 1990); Richard Creese, William Randolph Bynum, and Joe Bearn, eds., *The Health of Prisoners: Historical Essays* (Brill, 1995); Peter McRorie Higgins, *Punish or Treat? Medical Care in English Prisons 1770-1850* (Trafford, 2007).

pontifes avaient toujours poursuivi deux objectifs dans la conception et l'implantation des prisons : la sécurité, pour une garde rigoureuse des détenus, et la salubrité ainsi que la ventilation, pour la préservation de ceux qui y étaient enfermés. Ces principes furent mis à l'épreuve des faits et argumentés avec une clarté particulière lors d'un litige qui opposa le gouverneur de Rome à la confraternité du Gonfalone. Celle-ci avait entrepris de surélever son siège, situé en face des Carceri Nuove, en y ajoutant une loggia, des mezzanines et un clocher. Le gouverneur, responsable de la gestion des prisons, s'y opposa vigoureusement. Il exigea l'interruption immédiate des travaux et la démolition de ce qui avait déjà été érigé, au nom du double préjudice que la construction causerait : la facilitation des communications entre détenus et extérieur, d'une part, et la dégradation de l'ensoleillement et de la ventilation du bâtiment, d'autre part. Il invoquait un droit qu'il avait déjà exercé contre deux propriétaires riverains ayant tenté de modifier des bâtiments à proximité de la prison. Les enjeux étaient doubles : établir la nature exacte du préjudice allégué, et déterminer si les exigences de la prison pouvaient légitimement primer sur celles d'une confraternité. La dispute mobilisa médecins, chirurgiens, architectes et juristes.

Les experts mandatés par le gouverneur conclurent que la surélévation nuisait à la fois à la sécurité et à la salubrité de la prison. Sur le premier point, une expérimentation dédiée démontra que les derniers étages des deux édifices permettaient une communication visuelle et verbale mutuelle, ce qui était particulièrement grave : aux étages supérieurs des prisons se trouvait l'infirmerie *segreta*, réservée aux détenus soumis au régime le plus restrictif, dont l'isolement se voyait ainsi compromis. Sur le second point, les architectes soutinrent que le nouvel édifice obstruait la circulation de la tramontane et réduisait l'exposition solaire du bâtiment. Le médecin et le chirurgien de la prison précisèrent les conséquences de cette situation : la nouvelle construction priverait non seulement les infirmeries, mais aussi la salle centrale et le quartier des femmes de l'ensoleillement hivernal et des vents orientaux dont les propriétés étaient jugées bénéfiques pour la qualité de l'air. Leurs occupants se verraient ainsi condamnés à vivre dans un environnement vicié et humide, propice au développement de maladies. L'un des architectes mandatés fit valoir, de son côté, un argument d'ordre économique : les maladies susceptibles d'être causées par l'insalubrité de l'environnement représenteraient une charge financière considérable pour les caisses pontificales. Comme pour la santé des gardiens, la protection des corps des détenus se justifiait ainsi autant par des considérations de rationalité gestionnaire que par des principes sanitaires.

Le recours à l'expertise des architectes en matière de salubrité s'inscrivait dans une longue tradition de réflexion théorique sur les rapports entre orientation des bâtiments, circulation de l'air et santé qui avait progressivement affirmé les bienfaits de la ventilation.² Au XVIII^e siècle, cette réflexion connut un développement ultérieur : Francesco Milizia et Girolamo Maria Fonda, auteurs de traités influents destinés à la formation des architectes, insistaient sur la nécessité d'intégrer des savoirs physiques et naturalistes pour optimiser l'exposition solaire et la circulation de l'air dans les édifices publics. Elle se nourrissait parallèlement d'un savoir médical qui, depuis le XVI^e siècle, avait placé la salubrité de l'air au cœur de la médecine préventive. Héritée de la tradition hippocratique, cette préoccupation fut réarticulée au XVIII^e siècle dans un cadre épistémologique renouvelé, intégrant les apports de la physique et de la chimie, à une époque où la médecine se voyait reconnaître un rôle politique croissant dans le gouvernement des États européens.³ La salubrité, et notamment la ventilation des lieux d'enfermement, était ainsi devenue un enjeu technique et politique à l'échelle du continent. La prison londonienne de Newgate en offre un exemple emblématique : après une épidémie de *jail fever* en 1750, on y installa un système de ventilation mécanique conçu par le chimiste Stephen Hales, déjà appliqué auparavant à bord des navires négriers.⁴

Quant à la dispute en question, la confraternité refusa aussi bien d'interrompre les travaux que de démolir ce qui avait déjà été construit, et l'affaire fut portée devant le tribunal de la Sacra Consulta. En 1765, celui-ci ordonna une nouvelle expertise architecturale dont les conclusions contredisaient celles avancées par le gouverneur : la surélévation, modeste en hauteur et partielle dans son emprise, ne compromettait ni l'ensoleillement ni la ventilation de la prison de façon significative, et la distance entre les deux bâtiments rendait toute communication effective illusoire. Un avis juridique rédigé pour l'occasion vint compléter ce tableau : sur la question de la ventilation, il s'appuyait sur une décision antérieure du tribunal de la Rote romaine relative à un séminaire pour faire observer que dans de nombreux *luoghi pii* de Rome la tramontane ne soufflait que d'un seul côté sans que cela compromît leur salubrité. Il rappelait par ailleurs que le siège d'une confraternité (au même titre qu'un hôpital, un monastère ou un collège) constituait un *luogo pio* jouissant du même statut juridique que les prisons, sans que l'une pût revendiquer de primauté sur l'autre.

² Alessandro Nova, "The Role of the Winds in Architectural Theory from Vitruvius to Scamozzi," in *Aeolian Winds and the Spirit in Renaissance Architecture*, ed. Barbara Kenda (Routledge, 2006), 70–86.

³ Maria Pia Donato, "The Afterlife of the Non-Naturals in Early Eighteenth-Century Hippocratism: From the Healthy Individual to a Healthy Population," in *Conserving Health in Early Modern Culture: Bodies and Environments in Italy and England*, ed. Sandra Cavallo and Tessa Storey (Manchester University Press, 2017), 158–82; Ferdinando Abbri, *Le terre, l'acqua, le arie. La rivoluzione chimica del Settecento* (Il Mulino, 1984).

⁴ Aleksandr Bierig, "Forced Air: Environmental Control and Colonial Expansion in Eighteenth-Century Britain," in *Land Air Sea: Architecture and Environment in the Early Modern Era*, ed. Jennifer Ferng and Lauren Jacobi (Brill, 2023), 136–72.

Interroger la matérialité de l'espace carcéral à travers le prisme de la protection de la santé permet ainsi de mettre en lumière la pluralité des logiques qui gouvernaient la gestion de la prison. Rhétorique de la charité et de la clémence, impératifs de contrôle et considérations économiques ne s'y opposaient pas mais se combinaient et se conditionnaient mutuellement, formant un ensemble dans lequel sécurité et salubrité constituaient deux dimensions indissociables d'une même pratique institutionnelle. Le litige avec la confraternité l'illustre avec une netteté particulière : leur articulation y nécessita la mobilisation croisée de savoirs médicaux et architecturaux, révélant comment la gestion de l'espace carcéral engageait des compétences professionnelles spécialisées et complémentaires. L'issue de l'affaire éclaire en outre la place qu'occupait la prison dans l'équilibre politique, juridique et urbanistique de la ville : loin de jouir d'un statut privilégié, elle se trouvait soumise aux mêmes règles que les autres institutions qui composaient le tissu urbain romain, sans que ses exigences, pourtant reconnues comme légitimes et pieuses, ne pussent s'imposer sur celles des autres *luoghi pii* de la ville.

Solace of the Imprisoned: Abbasid Ethical Discourses on Incarceration

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Al-Buḥturī:

If you are veiled from sight, do not be amazed—

The moist pearl lies hidden in the oyster.

If they oppress you for a time, wait in hope.

The Lord of the Throne will yet show you kindness. (*Uns al-Masjūn*, p. 128).

This paper reflects on the meaning of prisons and prisoners as a political and ethical question through a late Abbasid-era Arabic text. It reflects on confinement through the lens of carceral humanitarianism, while also attending to the materiality of carceral space and its embodied experience. By carceral humanitarianism, I refer to the process by which practices of confinement are morally and legally normalized through limits on coercion, the ethical recognition of the prisoner as a subject of justice, and acts of care. In this framework, imprisonment emerges as a dual site: an instrument of sovereign power and a field of humanitarian concern.

The institutional prison in the premodern Muslim Middle East did not emerge in a single moment but went through a long process in which confinement was gradually brought under the control of the administrative and security apparatuses of the state in the course of the 8th and 9th centuries. It seems that the emergence of prison buildings in the ninth century produced a gradual depersonalization of imprisonment. The appearance of prison personnel, such as directors, warders, guards, and gatekeepers, indicates the formation of a chain of command and the integration of the prison into the government and police apparatus.

Although we lack satisfactory information on the internal organization of prisons, we know that collective confinement in prisons was the norm. Large, shared spaces housed substantial numbers of detainees together. Individual cells existed but were exceptional and usually reserved for detainees of rank or those condemned to especially harsh conditions. This was a spatial translation of the social hierarchies and political vulnerabilities that the sources register. In the Muṭbaq of Baghdad, for instance, used for “political prisoners,” two modes of confinement coexisted: crowded communal areas for the majority and separate rooms described as more spacious and cleaner for high-status prisoners. In other prisons, we encounter the use of wells and narrow crevices to inflict hardship.

The primary evidence in the legal and historical archive suggests that incarceration from the late eighth century onward operated within two distinct but intersecting jurisdictions: the sharī‘a and siyāsa, with the latter encompassing not only the administrative control of prisons but also the sphere of discretionary punishment (extra-legal, secular, siyāsa, ta‘zīr) as exercised by political authority. This division, which may be named for the sake of legibility as legal vs. political, was functional and practical rather than formally codified, yet it structured both the legal meaning and the institutional practice of confinement. The distinction between the two is significant because it articulates a separation between judicial authority and political authority and thereby introduces a moral and normative check on political power.

Within the domain of sharī‘a jurisdiction, imprisonment had a limited role. It was not a prescribed penalty and therefore did not constitute a fixed punishment attached to specific offenses. It was rather procedural and instrumental, such as detention for debt when solvency was disputed, pre-trial custody, and contempt of court. Siyāsa, or political imprisonment, on the other hand, included the ruler’s discretionary power to punish outside the procedural framework of the sharī‘a, and it was in this domain that incarceration became a central coercive tool. Political enemies, rebels, dissenters, and those accused of threatening public order could be confined on the basis of the ruler’s judgment without recourse to the evidentiary and procedural constraints of the courts.

The material regime of imprisonment was structured by chronic scarcity, a condition already implicit in the earliest phases of carceral practice and persisting into the urbanized prison of the high caliphal period and beyond. Narrative sources and adab compilations describe prisoners emerging emaciated from prison, with uncut hair, soiled clothing, and an offensive odor, their physical condition bearing witness to the length of their detention. Material comfort was not a right but a negotiable commodity. Rations were reduced to coarse barley, sometimes mixed with ashes or

accompanied only by salted water. Those with access to money or patronage could secure a mat, a lamp, a cleaner garment, or more nutritious food; those without endured hunger, filth, and exposure.

The chain functioned as the principal technology of immobilization. Light would have been scarce and unevenly distributed, often available only to those who could purchase a lamp, while darkness, vermin such as snakes and scorpions, and the constant sounds of coughing and crying created an environment in which sensory deprivation and physical vulnerability became part of the punishment. In prison, the boundary between human and animal habitation was minimized, and the prisoner was reduced to a condition of bare survival. Descriptions of the Muṭbaq emphasize narrowness, heat, and the absence of light to the point that confinement is likened to burial alive.

Yet this regime of deprivation did not produce a sealed institution. From its earliest form in house imprisonment to the formal prisons of later centuries, the carceral space remained porous and socially active. The same economy of mediation that supplied food and clothing enabled prisoners even to conduct business, recover debts, lend money, and maintain networks of patronage. The circulation of goods through the guards, the entry of visitors, the drafting of petitions, and the granting of temporary releases all attest to the connection of the prison to the wider urban economy.

A case in point is al-Buḥturī's *the Solace of the Imprisoned and the Relief of the Distressed*. The book represents the prison as both an architecture of power and a contested ethical space where humanitarian critique of political authority continually negotiates its limits. The author appears to have lived in the transitional decades between the twelfth and thirteenth centuries in Aleppo and Damascus. From some internal evidence, we know that the book was written in prison, and in stages, as circumstances permitted.

The work is divided into eight chapters, one of which, "On Imprisonment and Exile and the Emergence from Constriction to Ease," is directly related to imprisonment and the largest. The material is organized methodically into thematic sections devoted to patience, endurance, injustice, hope, self-discipline, and faith under conditions of suffering. The work assembles a wide range of materials. It brings together Qur'ānic passages, prophetic reports, aphorisms, and narratives featuring figures drawn from across intellectual and political history: Plato, Aristotle, Alexander, Anūshirwān, as well as prophets, caliphs, rulers, bureaucrats, military commanders, scholars, Sufis, and poets. Nearly half of the volume is composed in verse.

The content produces not merely a literary anthology, but a parallel discursive environment, an imagined space that compensates for the deprivation of imprisonment and enables prisoners to situate their own suffering within a broader moral and historical horizon. The addressee is not an abstract ethical subject; rather, it is the prisoner himself, and one who has experienced imprisonment and seeks orientation. Consolation, therefore, is not ornamental; it corresponds to a concrete social and existential need.

Al-Buḥturī must have had access to writing materials (pen, ink, and paper) and likely to books, given the breadth of references contained in the work. At the same time, the presence of occasional mistakes of attribution suggests that part of the material may have been drawn from memory. The conditions of his confinement must also have allowed for the preservation of written pages, implying a relatively secure space within the prison environment.

The book does not directly describe prison architecture or systematically discuss conditions of confinement, yet a considerable amount of information emerges indirectly. We encounter references to small cells, shared spaces housing multiple prisoners, wells used for confinement, lack of light, heavy chains placed on ankles or binding the hands, and minimal daily rations, often little more than bread and water. The environment appears oppressive and uncertain, shaped by the varying conduct of guards and intermediaries, the possibility of communication with the outside world, described as "life" in contrast to the prison, which is likened to death, and the indeterminate duration of confinement, which could extend for years or even decades.

The narrative articulates a conception of imprisonment that is fundamentally ethical and existential rather than institutional, disciplinary, or juridically totalizing. Prison appears not as a closed apparatus that produces docile bodies through surveillance, normalization, and continuous observation, but as a condition that reorganizes the moral relation of the subject to time, affliction, divine justice, and the self. The author explicitly redefines incarceration as a reversal of its apparent meaning: what outwardly signifies deprivation becomes "the springtime of intimacy" and "the repose of my heart and the refuge of my soul."

This ethical framing allows us to see both analogy and distance from liberal and poststructuralist theories of prison and imprisonment. There is no equivalent claim that imprisonment improves the subject for the sake of society, nor that it operates as part of a generalized carceral continuum extending across schools, barracks, hospitals, and workshops. Instead, incarceration remains contingent and morally ambiguous precisely because it is not fully juridically internalized. It does not automatically generate social stigma or a fixed criminal identity. In fact, imprisonment can enhance moral authority. The prison is therefore not a machine for producing normalized subjects but a liminal condition in which worldly power is relativized, and the ethical subject reconstitutes itself in relation to transcendence. Where the poststructuralist prison operates through visibility and the internalization of surveillance, al-Buḥturī's prison produces an inward turn, an opacity to power, and a form of subjectivity grounded in endurance rather than normalization.

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Concluding Remarks: From Escapes to Globalisation – A Material History of Confinement

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Firstly, I would like to thank Nathalie and Anna Clara for inviting me to share these three days in such stimulating company. The price to pay for this privilege is to deliver some concluding remarks—or, better yet, opening perspectives—on this very dense conference.

Summarizing the questions addressed during this conference in just fifteen minutes is a daunting task. Therefore, I have chosen not to quote each speaker individually or revisit their illuminating examples. Instead, I will limit my reflections to seven overarching questions.

By focusing on **materiality and confinement**, the organizers have invited us to reconsider the place of human (and animal) confinement in premodern societies. This shift involves three methodological and epistemological operations:

- **Broadening the perspective:** moving from dominant narratives shaped by the persistent image of the (penal) prison—or the prisoner as an artefact of the penal system—towards a diversity of confinement spaces and practices across the *longue durée* and on a global scale.
- **Changing our gaze on confinement:** interrogating sources through the lenses of visual, material, sensory, emotional, or archival “turns” offers new insights into the “e-motion” provoked by the experience of voluntary or involuntary bodily constraint.
- **Adding a measure of reflexivity:** questioning the research interest of examining confinement, particularly in societies where such practices have been extended to the majority of the population or to specific groups (e.g., mass deportation, epidemics).

I will outline these reflections through seven key elements: **Escapes, Writing, Places, Things, Rituals, Evolution, and Globalisation.**

1. Escapes

To “de-carcerate” our vision of confinement in societies before the eighteenth century, escapes can serve as a backdoor to understanding the confinement experience.

Escapes are a way to shed light on the materiality of confinement. Escaping constitutes a disruptive human act that exposes the interactions between the escapees, their *modus operandi*, as well as their past and present relationships with custodians or jailers. Fundamentally, escaping is a spatial displacement (going out) that is constrained by material obstacles: locked doors, walls, fences, buildings, pipes, caves, or rooftops.

Escaping may include the use of force to overcome these obstacles; sometimes, it involves personal ingenuity, practical knowledge, social exchanges, technical skills, or using the properties of confining spaces to find a way out. More dramatically, escapes from confinement can become definitive—through the loss of one’s mind or even one’s life (in suicide cases). Escaping is also a social act: by creating a scandal, it generates administrative, police, or judicial documentation that brings to light the (hitherto invisible) materiality of confinement and the social relations that accompany it.

2. Writing

A second entry point into confined spaces is the practice of writing. Writing about the prison experience—or writing in prison—is not a recently discovered activity. Historians are familiar with the numerous written testimonies from prominent and literate individuals, religious or political leaders, rulers, criminals, or communities who documented their confinement. In the ancient Mediterranean, the Sinicized world, or medieval Islamic societies, philosophers, prophets, disgraced Chinese mandarins, Muslim rulers, and scholars wrote poems and treatises during their forced confinement. However, the surviving texts rarely evoke their personal experience as confined individuals.

Fortunately, in preserved spaces of confinement—such as heritage buildings, as demonstrated by various projects in Spain, Italy, and France—scholars have rediscovered the scientific potential of another form of detainee expression: **graffiti**. Not writing *about* prison, but writing *on* the walls of confinement.

As the contributions on graffiti have shown, collecting, analyzing, dating, and interpreting these inscriptions opens fruitful perspectives. However, this work requires precise technical expertise and collective effort, for which the traditional skills of historians and archaeologists—such as epigraphy or paleography—are renewed by new technologies (photography, scanning, material analysis, AI).

Firstly, graffiti provide evidence that a natural or built space has been used for confinement, whether for religious minorities, elites, or criminals. Secondly, while many textual sources or archives have been relocated and reorganized by librarians or archivists over the centuries, graffiti remain among the rare written or graphic documents preserved in their original production environment.

Interpreting graffiti is a complex task. When archival material exists—such as administrative documents, judicial files, or prison registers—, they can help historicize the epigraphic material. As a material practice, writing on walls is a performative act. Graffiti tell the stories of the appropriation of space, self-testimony, protests against the authorities, and even the sacralization of space. They reveal acts of supernatural (religious or magical) agency in the context of a fixed daily life, sketching a symbolic economy of supernatural connection within a material world of subjugation.

Graffiti also highlight gender issues. The absence of graffiti by women, even in spaces where women were largely present, raises questions about the differential occupation of public space—a phenomenon well-documented in contemporary spaces of confinement (prisons, asylums, camps...).

3. Places

Another traditional area of knowledge that requires revision is the diversity of confinement places. Across more than twenty contributions, we explored castles, forts, towers, arsenals, galleys, convents, monasteries, factories, workhouses, hospitals, private houses, islands, and isolated territories. The existing historiography expands this list even further to include mines, caves, military camps, and labor camps.

We need therefore a finely tuned understanding of the historical and multifunctional uses of these spaces. A typology of confinement spaces should not merely catalog sites but should instead offer a **comprehensive network analysis** of the patterns and variations in each spatial, material, and cultural configuration of confinement.

In many premodern societies, the primary distinction lies between:

- **Spaces of temporary custody** for “prisoners,” often centered around a jailer’s family in unaffordable, inherited medieval buildings, filled with the circulation of people and objects;
- **Institutionalized, medium- or long-term confinement spaces**, such as late Antiquity monasteries, early modern workhouses (*Zuchthäuser*), large city prisons (Seville, Rome, Venice, Paris, London), or maritime confinement places, *bagnes*, and galleys. Each of these spaces developed economic, social, and political networks within and around fixed sites of confinement.

For example, Mediterranean galleys present a complex economy of forced labor, involving various categories of people: voluntary rowers, prisoners of war, persecuted minorities, or criminal convicts.

An evolutionary approach to the concrete must also account for—like the palimpsests of graffiti—the stratification or superimposition of various systems of control and “cultures of confinement.” For instance, the configurations and experiences of galleys in the summer at sea or during wartime contrast sharply with those of the *bagne* (penal colony) in the city during winter or peacetime.

In the processes of early modern globalization, the expansion of confinement technologies combined remnants of ancient slavery cultures with new repressive administrations (e.g., inquisitions, marines) or economic units of exploitation (e.g., monasteries, factories, plantations).

4. Things, Objects, Artefacts

Many contributions have focused on a **history through things or objects**. Artefacts are not merely passive items; they can be seen as **social agents**. Their existence influences human interactions, as highlighted by the concept of “affordance”¹ or actor-network theory², giving rise to an actual “social life of things.”³ The example of Flemish rowers petitioning the King of Spain for their liberation based on the (documented) loss of their sentence is illuminating.

¹ Jenny L. Davis, *How Artifacts Afford. The Power and Politics of Everyday Things* (MIT Press, 2020).

² Bruno Latour, *Reassembling the Social: An Introduction to Actor-Network-Theory* (Oxford University Press, 2005).

³ Arjun Appadurai, *The Social Life of Things: Commodities in Cultural Perspective* (Cambridge University Press, 2014).

Keeping records is crucial for managing the rowers' contracts or their sentences—and, more broadly, for supporting the global enterprise of workforce management.

A typology of artefacts can be elaborated as follows:

- **Objects that are imposed by the custodians** on the confined population (locks, chains, shackles, clothing) and that express relations of domination;
- **Prohibited objects** of various kinds (money, food, drugs, clothing, raw materials, artefacts that could serve as tools for survival or as weapons for revolt or escape). Today, every prison houses a small museum of such objects, confiscated by the guards. These collections reflect the jailers' fear of contestation, subversion, or attack, as well as protests against the prison prohibitions—and, above all, the custodians' obsession with security.

Between obligation and prohibition, certain artefacts were tolerated, clearly expressing the resilience, selfhood, or agency of the confined individuals. During this conference, we learned about amulets, bags, religious signs, and books. Other objects became resources for survival (e.g., drugs such as opium) or the basis for an underground or tolerated exchange economy (e.g., coffee, tobacco, ordinary tools, souvenirs).

5. Rituals

Objects are often connected to ritual practices. Whether in monasteries, workhouses, disciplinary institutions, *bagnes*, penal colonies, asylums, or prisons, we observe certain "*rites of passage*" at the entrance and exit of confinement.

Some of these rites are imposed by the authorities: shaving heads, chaining, "uniform-ing" inmates with specific clothing, changing names by assigning confinement names or numbers. These practices, well-described by institutional anthropologists, serve as markers of a "**total institution**"—or, more accurately, a **totalizing institution**.⁴

Other rites are imposed from below by the confined individuals themselves, such as hazing or "courtoisie" practices. These are crucial for understanding the "**confinement shock**" or the "**prisonization**" effect.⁵ Unfortunately, such practices leave few traces, except in the trials of jailers for abuse.

The transformation of an ordinary peasant, artisan, city dweller, young boy or girl into a monk, nun, inmate, rower, or prisoner must be maintained daily through **disciplinary ritual practices**: controlling the movement (e.g., walking in circles or lines), displacing bodies from one place to another, rationing hygiene, light, or speech.

Most of these coercive practices target the **body**. They humiliate the confined population, create a "**collective body**" of subalterns, and sharpen the differentiation between groups of confined individuals, custodians, and free people. At the core of the confined spaces, the infinite variations of disciplinary punishments serve as a reminder of the role of violence in the deprivation of freedom.

Facing these disciplinary actions, the confined population retain a **limited but real agency**. Escapes, revolts, or sabotages depend largely on the material possibilities of the space, the personal skills of certain inmates, and the quality of the social interactions between the rulers and the ruled. Less visible are the practices of avoidance: corruption, bribery, negotiation, or threats, which occasionally surface in public scandals or the trials of the custodians or religious superiors. Investigations into specific spaces—monasteries, workhouses, inquisitorial prisons, women's refuges—confirm the numerous social exchanges that occur *within, through, and around* the walls of confinement spaces.

6. Evolutions: Disruptions and Continuities

I will summarize a few classical observations on some major changes that occur in European societies:

- **Monastic confinement** is a practice inherited from early Christian communities in the eastern Mediterranean and the development of a Christian culture of religious discipline;⁶
- The **Reformation** and the secularization of the poor relief led to the creation of a network of confinement institutions, such as the *Zuchthäuser* (discipline houses);⁷
- The **eighteenth century** saw a change in the scale and gender balance of confinement institutions in Western societies. Many governments created or rebuilt correction houses, now hosting hundreds of inmates confined by administrative, private, or judicial decisions. Inspired to varying degrees by Beccaria's proposals, governments supported the replacement of banishment, corporal punishment, and death penalties with medium- and long-

⁴ Erving Goffman, *Asylums: Essays on the Social Situation of Mental Patients and Other Inmates* (Doubleday, 1961).

⁵ Donald Clemmer, *The Prison Community* (Holt, Rhinehart & Winston, 1940). Gresham Sykes, *Society of Captives: A Study of a Maximum-Security Prison* (Princeton University Press, 1958).

⁶ Julia Hillner, *Prison, Punishment and Penance in Late Antiquity* (Cambridge University Press, 2015).

⁷ Pieter Spierenburg, *The Prison Experience. Disciplinary Institutions and their Inmates in Early Modern Europe* (Amsterdam University Press, 2007).

term prison sentences. They used the growing capacity of correction houses to confine more juveniles and women.

- Consequently, the use of **traditional sovereign pardons** by families or authorities became a way to manage the growing number of confined individuals in prisons, asylums, and private institutions.
- The **progressive transformation of local prisons into public institutions**, along with the role of administrators and social lobbying groups (e.g. confraternities), brought cameral sciences and Enlightenment ideas to the forefront of the debates on prison reform and poor relief. This placed the control, renovation, or repurposing of confinement institutions on the political agenda of bourgeois nation-states.

All these evolutions were already underway during the period that Foucault identified as the birth of the **penal prison**.

7. Globalisation and Materiality

Materiality can help revise attempts to build a global history of confinement over the *longue durée*. By highlighting the variety of forms of bodily constraint throughout Western history, many contributions have enriched our understanding of premodern confinement practices and their persistence during the penal reforms of the late *Ancien Régime* and the revolutionary times.

On a global scale, at the beginning of the nineteenth century, different logics of control gave rise to two major “ideal” types of spatial configurations of constraint:

1. The **domestic home or convent**;
2. The **galleys, penal colonies, and concentration/deportation camps**.

Today, these configurations interpenetrate in state-run prison archipelagos, but they are the product of the accumulation of historical practices and various functions.⁸ As we know, confinement as punishment emerged in the first Middle Eastern cities with sedentarization. The aggregation of punishment—through penance and prison in monasteries—and penal deportation flourished in colonial empires, both in the West and Asia.

A **global history of incarceration** must determine the extent to which the practices have been imported, or whether local practices have persisted or been adapted within contemporary systems. Before Western colonization, in Islamic, Sinicized, or African societies, confinement remained a marginal technique for managing populations or punishing criminals. In contrast, capital or corporal punishment—and even unpaid fines—were more commonly discussed and spectacularized. Spatial confinements, such as banishment and social exclusion, were established as possible penalties in many societies, though they were rarely the subject of justificatory, moralizing, utilitarian, or reform discourses.

By combining the materialities of objects, actors, and experiences of confinement examined during this conference, it would be possible to write a **long-term history** that integrates the discourses on confinement, the legal and social functions of imprisonment, spatial dependencies, the materiality of places, and the profiles of the populations under constraint. This would contribute, from the bottom up, to an **alternative history of humankind**, based on concrete practices of physical constraint, deprivation of liberty, and domination.

N.B.: Ce texte a été pensé, rédigé, délivré oralement et réécrit par l'auteur. Il a ensuite été corrigé par recours à l'IA PICCOLO sur le plan syntaxique, grammatical et stylistique, tout en conservant le ton et la structure d'une conclusion de colloque. Les modifications visent à fluidifier la lecture, corriger les répétitions, les erreurs de syntaxe et les formulations maladroites.

⁸ Christian de Vito, Alex Lichtenstein, “Writing a Global History of Convict Labour”, In: *Global Histories of Work*, edited by Andreas Eckert (De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2016), p. 49-89.